

Energy Technological Review

Deliverable D2.2

Alberto Landini¹, Tommaso Zerbi¹, John Morrissey², Stephen Axon²

¹ *Stam s.r.l., Genoa, Italy*

² *Liverpool John Moores University, Liverpool, UK*

 <http://www.entrust-h2020.eu>

 [@EntrustH2020](https://twitter.com/EntrustH2020)

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 657998

Document Information

Grant Agreement #:	657998
Project Title:	Energy System Transition Through Stakeholder Activation, Education and Skills Development
Project Acronym:	ENTRUST
Project Start Date:	01 May 2015
Related work package:	WP 2: Mapping of energy system
Related task(s):	Task 2.2 Characterisation of the technological regime & emerging innovations
Lead Organisation:	University College Cork
Submission date:	15 October 2016 (revised and updated)
Dissemination Level:	PU – Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
25 Jan 2016	Alberto Landini (STAM)	All Partners	A
12 Oct 2016	Alberto Landini (STAM)	Niall Dunphy (UCC)	B (revised and updated version)

Table of Contents

About the ENTRUST Project.....	6
Executive Summary.....	7
1 Deliverable context	8
1.1 Overview of Work Package 2.....	8
1.2 Objectives of Task 2.2.....	8
1.3 Aims of Deliverable 2.2.....	9
1.4 Deliverable structure.....	9
2 Defining the Energy System / Regime	10
2.1 Profiling the Energy Regime for the ENTRUST Project	10
2.2 Understanding the Technological Dimension of Energy: The Supply Chain Perspective	10
2.3 Defining the Energy Supply Chain	11
2.4 Overview of critical energy supply chain elements	12
2.5 Renewable Energy Supply Chains	14
3 Measuring Supply Chain Performance	15
3.1 Summary of Literature Findings on Key Performance Indicators	15
3.2 Defining KPIs for the Energy Supply Chain	18
3.3 Synthesis of Review Insights: Defining KPIs for ENTRUST Task 2.2	19
3.4 KPIs evaluation process	24
4 Energy production	25
4.1 Electricity	25
4.2 District heating.....	48
5 Energy transportation and distribution.....	55
5.1 Electricity	56
5.2 Oil	59
5.3 Gas.....	62
5.4 Coal.....	65
6 Energy storage.....	68
6.1 Electricity	69
6.2 Oil	75
6.3 Gas.....	76
6.4 Coal.....	80
6.5 Heat storage.....	81
7 Energy end users	85
7.1 Lighting	87
7.2 Micro CHP	92
7.3 Building heating	96
7.4 Ventilating	102
7.5 Air conditioning.....	105
7.6 Building monitoring, automation and control.....	109
7.7 Transport	116
8 Conclusion and synthesis.....	120
9 Bibliography	122

List of Tables

Table 1: Framework of Ideal KPIs to Characterise Energy Supply Chains	20
Table 2: Framework of Selected KPIs to Characterise Energy Supply Chains	21
Table 3: KPIs for production, Transportation-Distribution and Storage phases	22
Table 4: KPIs for End-user stage – HVAC systems	23
Table 5: KPIs for End-user stage – Lighting and Transport systems	23
Table 6: KPIs evaluation for non-renewable energies.....	32
Table 7: KPIs evaluation for renewable energies.....	47
Table 8: KPIs evaluation for district heating technologies.....	54
Table 9: KPIs evaluation for electricity T&D	58
Table 10: KPIs evaluation for oil T&D	61
Table 11: KPIs evaluation for natural gas T&D	63
Table 12: KPIs evaluation for coal T&D	67
Table 13: KPIs evaluation for electricity storage	74
Table 14: KPIs evaluation for gas storage	79
Table 15: KPIs evaluation for heat storage	84
Table 16: KPIs evaluation for lighting technologies.....	89
Table 17: KPIs evaluation for lighting control systems.....	91
Table 18: KPIs evaluation for micro CHP technologies.....	95
Table 19: KPIs evaluation for building heating technologies.....	101
Table 20: KPIs evaluation for ventilating solutions.....	104
Table 21: KPIs evaluation for air conditioning technologies.....	108
Table 22: KPIs evaluation for building automation and control systems	115
Table 23: KPIs evaluation for private transport vehicles	118

List of Figures

Figure 1: Generic Renewable Energy Supply Chain Process	15
Figure 2: SMART criteria for KPI selection and application	16
Figure 3: Production of primary energy, EU-28, 2013	25
Figure 4: Net electricity generation, EU-28, 2013	26
Figure 5: Hydroelectric dam scheme	34
Figure 6: Tidal barrage scheme	36
Figure 7: DTP scheme	38
Figure 8: Concentrator PV panel.....	43
Figure 9: Dry steam power station scheme.....	44
Figure 10: CHP compared with separated power and heat generation	50
Figure 11 Coal stacking position	80
Figure 12: Molten salt system	82
Figure 13: European final energy consumption by sector.....	85
Figure 14: Stirling engine schematic view in Alpha, Beta and Gamma configurations	94
Figure 15: Condensing boiler scheme.....	98
Figure 16: Heat pump cycle scheme.....	99
Figure 17: Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery scheme	103
Figure 18: Chiller process schematic view	106
Figure 19: HVAC control systems typologies	111

About the ENTRUST Project

ENTRUST is mapping Europe's energy system (key actors and their intersections, technologies, markets, policies, innovations) and aims to achieve an in-depth understanding of how human behaviour around energy is shaped by both technological systems and socio-demographic factors (especially gender, age and socio-economic status). New understandings of energy-related practices and an intersectional approach to the socio-demographic factors in energy use will be deployed to enhance stakeholder engagement in Europe's energy transition.

The role of gender will be illuminated by intersectional analyses of energy-related behaviour and attitudes towards energy technologies, which will assess how multiple identities and social positions combine to shape practices. These analyses will be integrated within a transitions management framework, which takes account of the complex meshing of human values and identities with technological systems. The third key paradigm informing the research is the concept of energy citizenship, with a key goal of ENTRUST being to enable individuals overcome barriers of gender, age and socio-economic status to become active participants in their own energy transitions.

Central to the project will be an in-depth engagement with five very different communities across Europe that will be invited to be co-designers of their own energy transition. The consortium brings a diverse array of expertise to bear in assisting and reflexively monitoring these communities as they work to transform their energy behaviours, generating innovative transition pathways and business models capable of being replicated elsewhere in Europe.

For more information, see <http://www.entrust-h2020.eu>

Project Partners:

University College Cork, Ireland

- Cleaner Production Promotion Unit (Coordinator)
- Institute for Social Science in 21st Century

Liverpool John Moores University, UK

LGI Consulting, France

Integrated Environmental Solutions Ltd., UK

Redinn srl, Italy

Enerbyte Smart Energy Solutions, Spain

Stam srl, Italy

Coordinator Contact:

Niall Dunphy, Director, Cleaner Production Promotion Unit, University College Cork, Ireland

t: + 353 21 490 2521 | e: n.dunphy@ucc.ie | w: www.ucc.ie/cppu

Executive Summary

WP2 aims to undertake an extensive characterisation of the European energy system. Following the actors and actor-networks analysis realised during Task 2.1, the work performed during Task 2.2 represents a further step towards the complete energy system characterisation, as it provides a detailed overview on the technological forces currently driving it.

D2.2 focuses on the technical /technological elements of the Energy Socio-Technical regime, to contribute significant and robust evidence on what constitutes a regime. In order to do this, a supply chain perspective was adopted. The rich literature on the topic was reviewed and synthesised, and on this basis it was deemed most appropriate to apply a Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) approach in order to assess and characterise the energy supply chain. A best practice methodology for defining and applying KPIs was pursued; for this reason, an extensive review of the academic literature in this area was conducted and is presented in this deliverable. From this review, a means of identifying KPIs to characterise the Energy Supply Chain was developed, synthesising insights from state of the art knowledge on this. Developed KPIs represent a comprehensive and innovative means of characterising the Energy Supply Chain according to a myriad of multi-dimensional criteria; typically supply chains are characterised only in narrow or single dimensional ways. Through these steps, evidence on the technological elements of the Energy Supply Chain is produced, enabling a fuller understanding of this aspect of the energy regime, and presenting a critical part of the case-book through which the Energy Socio-technical regime will be defined in ENTRUST.

In order to present the technological review in a clear and structured way, the complex and interconnected structure of the energy supply chain was divided into its 4 main stages, (i.e. Production, Transportation & Distribution, Storage, and End User). For each stage, an introductory description of the current situation at European level is provided, in order to give the reader a contextual view of the discussed topic. Then, the main technical solution currently implemented are detailed, describing their functionalities, fields of implementation and other critical aspects such as, for example, environmental impact.

The information provided during those sections is then completed through the KPIs tables, which provide a clear comparison between the analysed technologies on a multiple level. Consistency through all the deliverable is guaranteed thanks to the definition of specific themes for the KPIs, which have been used as guidelines for all the evaluation tables. In order to better address each stage of the supply chain and each energy type particularities, though, a specific set of KPIs was defined for each considered group of technologies.

The technological review provided in this deliverable D2.2, together with the specific KPIs evaluation proposed at the end of each section, gives a clear understanding of the current technological forces driving the European energy system and as such is further contribution to the multi-disciplinary characterisation approach taken in WP2 of the ENTRUST project.

1 Deliverable context

1.1 Overview of Work Package 2

As per the Description of Action:

WP2 aims to undertake an extensive characterisation of energy system actors. A basic map of energy systems will be produced consisting of key actors, a description of their key roles, and critical strategic points of interaction, consistent with a practice based approach. Actor-network theories will be applied to develop insight into stakeholders' interactions; communities of energy use and the energy supply chain as a cascading, interlinked ecosystem/network of linked and interacting stakeholders. This work package will involve a comparison of energy system profile for diverse energy technologies, including an analysis of how synergies can be found between them regarding evolution, market, policies and uptake/acceptance.

Work Package 2 (WP2) seeks to inform and outline the scope for subsequent WPs. It aims to provide an initial mapping of significant factors that need to be taken into account when aiming to understand and foster a transition in the energy system. It focuses on two perspectives in particular – on the actors and their key interactions; as well as on technological, economic and political systems (energy technologies, market and policies). WP2 proposes to map and illustrate the capacity of actors to change the energy system, as well as how the system and its outputs constrain actors' capacity to act. The technological review performed through all the energy supply chain stages will play a fundamental role in understanding which are today's possibilities and limitations of the energy system and its possible future development.

1.2 Objectives of Task 2.2

As per the Description of Action:

Task 2.2 aims to characterise energy system technological regime, its driving forces and main challenges and opportunities. This task will identify the main technologies used along the energy supply chain, from generation, to transport, distribution until the end user. New and emerging energy technologies, renewables, energy conservation measures (ECM) and retrofit solutions, micro-generation, etc. will be identified through a technological review, augmenting information captured through the stakeholder analysis from task 2.1. These technologies and processes will be reviewed and key performance indicators will be defined to ascertain their potential value.

T 2.2 "Characterisation of the technological regime & emerging innovations" aims at moving forward the energy system analysis started with T2.1, where the main actors and actor-network influencing the European energy system have been investigated.

In this Task the main and emerging technologies for each stage of the supply chain will be analysed, providing details on their functioning, their advantages and disadvantages and their role in the current energy system. Technologies of the same category will be then compared through key performance indicators, in order to provide a better view of the possible future scenarios in the European energy system.

1.3 Aims of Deliverable 2.2

As described in section 1.2, this deliverable is focused primarily on technological aspects, but is developed to sync with, and complement, outputs captured through the analysis of stakeholders produced for Task 2.1. Deliverable 2.2 reports on the research activities of Task 2.2 by concentrating on the following key areas:

- The primary technologies used along the energy supply chain across generation, transport, distribution and end-user stages are identified.
- New and emerging energy innovations are described, including new technologies, renewable energy innovations, energy conservation measures (ECM) and retrofit opportunities.
- A review of best practice for the development of Key Performance Indicators is conducted to facilitate state of the art regime characterisation, with goals of consistency, integration and representativeness.
- A set of Key Performance indicators essential for D2.2 are defined on a systematic, targeted and step-wise manner; these are developed thematically to enable comparison across disparate technologies and spatial contexts / countries.
- Discreet Key Performance Indicators are developed and applied for each of the supply chain stages. Particular attention is given to the end-user stage due to the unique character of this stage and its critical important in behaviour change initiatives.
- A comprehensive and integrated characterisation of the energy supply chain is produced.

1.4 Deliverable structure

The deliverable is built as follows:

- **Supply chain definition:** This section gives an overview on what is considered as energy supply chain and what technological categories have been analysed in this document
- **Key Performance Indicators definition:** This part details the selection process for the key performance indicators that will be used throughout this deliverable to evaluate the reviewed technologies.
- **Analysis of the energy supply chain technologies:** The energy supply chain has been divided into its 4 main stages (Production, Transportation and Distribution, Storage, End user) and, for each one of those, the main technologies have been considered and reviewed.
- **Synthesis and conclusion**

2 Defining the Energy System / Regime

2.1 Profiling the Energy Regime for the ENTRUST Project

Sustainability transitions are characterised by substantially enhanced ecological efficiency within new socio-technological configurations (Coenen *et al.*, 2012). Within a sustainability transition context, an energy transition can be defined as a switch from an economic system dependent on one or a series of energy sources and technologies to an alternative paradigm (Crabbé *et al.*, 2013). From an energy perspective, it is increasingly apparent that current energy systems are unsustainable across a myriad of social, economic, and environmental criteria (Grübler, 2012), so much so that an energy transition to a low-carbon model is necessary to meet the challenge of climate change and to bring human activities back within ecological boundaries (Meadowcroft, 2009; Solomon and Krishna, 2011).

With the transitions literature, systems in transition are commonly represented as socio-technical regimes; defined as relatively stable configurations of institutions, techniques and artefacts, as well as rules, practices and networks that determine the 'normal' development and use of technologies (Rip and Kemp, 1998; A. Smith *et al.*, 2005). A focus on regimes recognises that organisations and technologies are embedded within wider social and economic systems (Rip & Kemp, 1998). Socio-technical systems are thus conceptualised as clusters of aligned elements, such as technical artefacts, knowledge, markets, regulation, cultural meaning, rules, infrastructure (Kern, 2012).

For the purposes of the ENTRUST project, it is necessary to develop a comprehensive profile of what we deem to be the energy system socio-technical regime. This will be completed in an integrated and multi-dimensional manner across a range of Work Packages and Deliverables; a full profile of both social and technical elements will emerge across this work, ultimately contributing to a comprehensive whole. Namely, WP2 (T2.1 & T2.2), WP3 (T3.1-3.4), WP4 (T4.1 & T4.3) and WP5 (T5.3) will all provide robust evidence which cumulatively will be applied to inform the ENTRUST project's profile of the Energy System socio-technical regime.

2.2 Understanding the Technological Dimension of Energy: The Supply Chain Perspective

Single, or standalone, business entities are almost non-existent today; more commonly, organisations belong to a network of entities at different stages in a supply chain¹. The output of one stage is the input to another; consequently, the environmental decisions made at one stage of a supply chain are affected by those made at prior stages and will affect those made in subsequent stages (El Saadany, Jaber, & Bonney, 2011). Although new technology, products, markets and retail formats remain critical to competitive advantage, supply chain performance improvements very often promise the greatest positive impact on economic profit and shareholder value, due to a traditional under-realisation of supply chain potentials (Stank, Dittmann, & Autry, 2011). Sustainable supply chains (SSC) are a key component of sustainable development in which key environmental and social performance measures act as key criteria for supply chain membership, while competitiveness is maintained through the delivery of value to end users (Taticchi, Tonelli, & Pasqualino, 2013). However, extending the supply chain to include sustainability concerns, including issues such as remanufacturing and recycling, adds complexity to supply chain design as well as potential strategic and operational issues (Sivadasan, Efstathiou, Calinescu, & Huaccho Huatuco,

¹ A supply chain is a complex network involving many stakeholders (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011).

2004; Taticchi *et al.*, 2013). The issue of competing goals and objectives would appear to be a central challenge to sustainability debates, and this is certainly evident in the case of sustainable supply chains (Shepherd & Günter, 2006). Supply chain managers interact with multiple decision makers. In addition, the reconciliation of the mitigation of environmental impacts and delivery of social benefits, together with value across stakeholders in a multi-party supply chain is a very complex task (Taticchi *et al.*, 2013). Practices such as just-in-time implicitly privilege certain metrics, which may or may not be aligned with the current strategic objectives (Shepherd & Günter, 2006). For example, whilst just-in-time encourages low inventory levels, this may conflict with the strategic goal of increased supply chain flexibility (Ibid.) or indeed with de-materialisation and energy reduction imperatives of sustainability. In addition, existing measurement systems for evaluating the performance of supply chains tend to be static rather than dynamic (Shepherd & Günter, 2006).

Coordinating the levels (suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, *etc.*) of a supply chain is necessary to deliver products and/or services to customers that conform to their requirements (including environmental ones) (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). A supply chain can be described as optimised when the operations of the manufacturer and retailers are coordinated (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). However, there remain a plethora of barriers to supply chain optimisation, particularly with regard to sustainability criteria. Many firms retain a traditional “functional” view of the supply chain, seeing it only as the area responsible for the logistics of material flow, and are thus unable to make the strategic link between supply chain performance and shareholder value (Stank *et al.*, 2011). Environmental concerns have been examined and treated separately in supply chain functions and there is as yet no integrative approach nor mechanism that measures, controls, and improves the environmental aspects of an entire supply chain (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). In fact, there is a dearth of research on the environmental performance of the supply chain as a whole. No studies exist which quantify the quality of the environmental performance of a supply chain (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). Optimising inventory in a supply chain, while taking environmental factors into consideration, is a vital research area; as much for energy supply chains as for supply chains of the manufacturing sector (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011).

2.3 Defining the Energy Supply Chain

The traditional supply chain is defined as an integrated manufacturing process wherein raw materials are manufactured into final products, then delivered to customers (via distribution, retail or both) (Beamon, 1999b). Essentially, supply chains represent the movement of materials as they flow from their source to the consumer. There are 4 main elements that constitute the energy supply chain. These are: (1) the generation of energy; (2) transmission of energy over long distances; (3) the distribution of energy to consumers; and (4) the consumption of energy.

For simplicity, as literature is much more consistent on the electricity supply chain, we are going to refer to the electrical case in order to provide a clearer example to the reader. This can be done since, with the exception of the specific technologies considered, the structure and stages of the supply chain are comparable for all types of energy.

Electricity can be generated from fossil fuels such as coal, oil and gas, or renewable sources such as hydro and wind power. Following generation, bulk electricity is transported via extra high voltage electricity transmission lines. The voltage of bulk-transmitted energy is reduced via substation transformers that convert high voltage electricity to low voltage for distribution. In many examples, there are often a number of distribution substations that reduced the voltage of electricity for distribution to consumers. Following this, electricity is then circulated through distribution lines that carry energy to ground level transformer stations or low voltage street mains that travel along underground wires directly to homes and businesses. This energy directly passes through an energy meter, which records the amount of energy used in homes

and businesses to provide an accurate assessment of the amount of energy consumed, which the energy provider can then charge for.

In energy supply planning and supply chain design, the coupling between long-term planning decisions like capital investment and short-term operation decisions like dispatching present a challenge, waiting to be tackled by systems and control engineers. The coupling is further complicated by uncertainties, which may arise from several sources including the market, politics, and technology (Lee, 2014). Supply chains are characterised by the interaction of multiple-actors, which is the case for energy supply chains as for any other, and the level of co-operation across organisational boundaries can be a key determinant of success. For instance, Wagner & Schaltegger (2004) report that firms with shareholder value-oriented strategies have a more positive relationship between environmental performance and different dimensions of economic performance than firms without such strategies. Manufacturers are looking to suppliers to work co-operatively in providing improved service, technological innovation and product design, for instance (Gunasekaran, Patel, & Mcgaughey, 2004). Energy supply chain optimisation therefore presents a major challenge due to the multi-scale nature and significant uncertainties (Lee, 2014).

2.4 Overview of critical energy supply chain elements

2.4.1 Introduction: Energy production

2.4.1.1 Electricity

Electricity is produced by renewable (e.g. solar, bioenergy, wind) and non-renewable (e.g. coal, oil, natural gas) sources of energy. Accounting for these elements of the energy supply chain for this Deliverable, there are a multitude of different technologies that are used including wind turbines; photovoltaic panels; steam engines; fuel cells; diesel engines; solar panels; ground source heat pumps; and elements that make up power plants including alternators, turbines and electrical generators.

2.4.1.2 District heating

Traditionally, homes have been heated with wood, the most easily obtainable source of heat, and more recently with natural gas and oil. Today in Europe, the predominant way in which to heat homes is through gas boilers rather than electric storage heater and oil burners, as this is a cheaper source of heating for domestic buildings. This section concentrates on different technologies used in centralised solutions for district heating. When it is possible to implement, district heating provides some advantages over single building solutions, since it helps save energy and thus reducing pollutant emissions in the air. The presence of a single bigger central unit provides a simpler and more efficient control, avoiding wastes in fuel consumption.

As a particular way to generate heat through recovery of electrical power plants exhaust gases, cogeneration is considered in this chapter as well. Cogeneration, or combined heat and power, is the use of a heat engine or power station to generate electricity and useful heat at the same time. It is a thermodynamically efficient use of fuel, as in the separate production of electricity some energy is discarded as waste heat. Common combined heat and power plant types are gas turbines, biofuel engines, biomass, steam turbine and nuclear power plants.

2.4.2 Introduction: Energy transportation and distribution

Energy transportation and distribution usually occurs through a series of technologies. After electricity is generated at a power station, it is transported through overhead and underground cables to step up transformers, which carry electricity across large distances, before entering residential buildings through

step-down transformers, transmission sub-stations, and local distribution sub-stations. These networks use components such as power lines, cables, transmission lines, substations, circuit breakers, capacitor banks, transformers and switches.

2.4.3 Introduction: Energy storage

One of the distinctive characteristics of the power sector is that the amount of electricity that can be generated is relatively fixed over short time periods, although demand fluctuates throughout the day. Electricity storage devices can manage the amount of power required to supply customers at times when need is greatest during peak load. Such devices can also help renewable energy, whose power cannot be controlled by grid operators. Energy storage devices can provide frequency regulation to maintain the balance between the network's load and power generated; achieving a more reliable power supply for high tech industrial facilities. Energy storage systems provide an array of technological approaches for managing power supply to create a more resilient energy infrastructure, bringing cost savings to end-users.

2.4.4 Introduction: End user technologies

This Deliverable focuses on end-user technologies, especially 'private citizen technologies' that are shaped by the energy-specific behaviours and practices of these same individuals. Lighting, transport, heating, ventilation, air conditioning and control systems were all considered, and are discussed below.

2.4.4.1 Lighting

Lighting technologies are heavily influenced by social practices and behaviours. The relevance of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on lighting technologies and control systems is explored, particularly those related to efficiency and energy consumption, including halogen and LED lightbulbs. Other aspects of lighting controls may include occupancy sensors, time-locks, and photocells hard-wired to control fixed groups of lights independently. Lighting control systems, however, refers to an intelligent networked system of devices related to lighting control, including dimmers, timers, photocells, occupancy sensors. Increasing demand for energy efficiency from end-users reflects desires to reduce energy consumption and costs.

2.4.4.2 HVAC

Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning (HVAC) and their control systems relate to the technologies of indoor and vehicular environmental comfort, notably to ensure thermal comfort and acceptable indoor air quality. HVAC systems are important in the design of buildings, particularly large domestic buildings, skyscrapers and offices, ensuring safe building conditions with respect to temperature and humidity. HVAC systems use multiple technologies, including solid fuel, liquid and gas heaters, heat pumps, dehumidifiers, fans, stand-alone air conditioning units, solar panels and many others.

2.4.4.3 Transport

In most Western European countries, such as the UK, over a third of energy consumed by individuals is used for transportation. This is often characterised by private transport use such as cars rather than public transport such as buses, rail and plane. Private transport, and some public transport (e.g., buses), can operate with diesel, gasoline, hybrid or electric sources of energy, yet significant cost barriers exist with the adoption of hybrid and electric vehicles. Whilst gasoline and diesel cars are predominant, the number of hybrid and electric private vehicles has increased four-fold across the European Union. Latest developments in private and public transport use include advanced range capabilities for hybrid and electric vehicles without the need for a plug-in capability.

2.5 Renewable Energy Supply Chains

Renewable Energy (RE) is a resource that is naturally regenerated over a short time scale and derived directly from the sun (such as thermal, photochemical, and photoelectric), indirectly from the sun (such as wind, hydropower, and photosynthetic energy stored in biomass), or from other natural movements and mechanisms of the environment (such as geothermal and tidal energy) (Cucchiella & Adamo, 2013). Like many typical supply chains, the elements of RE supply chain include the physical, information, and financial flows. From the physical flow perspective, industry's increasing awareness of green manufacturing processes, logistics, and products has become relevant to its supply chain management performance (Wee, Yang, Chou, & Padilan, 2012). Total global investment in RE reached USD 257 billion in 2011, up from USD 220 billion in 2010. (Cucchiella & Adamo, 2013). Recent estimates indicate that about 5 million people worldwide work either directly or indirectly in the RE industries: 22% of these based in the European Union (Cucchiella & Adamo, 2013). Cucchiella and Adamo note that the potential of renewable energy is significant but action on many fronts is required for this potential to be realised, including:

- Fostering the competitive market and research in the RE sector
- Promotion of networks of distribution, advanced storage technology and energy efficiency
- Development of production processes with a low carbon footprint
- Reuse, recycling and energy recovery from goods
- Participation of citizens in energy system design and management.

The design and shaping of supply chains is of considerable importance in renewable energy sectors. The effectiveness of such design efforts may determine the establishment and growth of a sustainable energy subsystem (Genus & Mafakheri, 2014). For example, design decisions determine the overall structure of the bio-fuel production network through capacity investment, production technology and location choices. They can be considered as one-time decisions, or multi-stage decisions to be made at various time points over a planning horizon. On top of these, there are short-term decisions on the procurement of biomass, processing, and distribution of products (Lee, 2014). The support structure that feeds into the success of all areas of renewable power manufacturing is therefore the backbone that creates success or failure for manufacturers. To succeed in the RE market, any manufacturer must look at who they choose to partner with for support and answer the question: "What benefits does this company, product, material or service provide?" (Laird, 2012). Like traditional sources of electric power generation, each RE type is limited by the inherent characteristics of the energy source. Intermittency, variability, and manoeuvrability are three key variables of RE resources that require effective management and control. In addition, due to the nature of RE, a second conversion process to save energy for use in off-hours is necessary (Wee *et al.*, 2012). The RE supply chain links the source of energy with other applications. The performance of the RE supply chain relates to its conversion efficiency which includes storage, distribution, efficiency and secondary application efficiencies (Wee *et al.*, 2012). The increasing role of renewable sources such as wind and solar necessitates the use of a fine-grained time scale for accurate assessment of their values. Use of storage intended to overcome the limitations of intermittent sources puts further demands on modelling and optimisation challenges, including numerical challenges that arise from the multi-scale nature and uncertainties (Lee, 2014).

Figure 1: Generic Renewable Energy Supply Chain Process (Wee *et al.*, 2012)

3 Measuring Supply Chain Performance

3.1 Summary of Literature Findings on Key Performance Indicators

Supply management involves managing upstream supply chain, including procurement or purchasing; involving make-or-buy decisions, outsourcing decisions, virtual enterprise operations, selecting suppliers, in-sourcing, and off-shoring (Angappa Gunasekaran & Spalanzani, 2012). At the organisational level, competing in complex and continuously changing environments requires a dynamic approach to measure, monitor, and manage organisational performance in its multiple dimensions (Taticchi *et al.*, 2013).

A performance measure, or set of performance measures, is used to determine the efficiency and/or effectiveness of an existing system, as well as comparing alternative systems (Beamon, 1999b), including management alternatives across the system. Performance measures and metrics open up the possibilities of looking at the best alternatives and decisions (Angappa Gunasekaran & Spalanzani, 2012). An important component in supply chain design and analysis is the establishment of appropriate performance measures. However, choosing an appropriate supply chain performance measure is difficult due to the complexity of these systems (Beamon, 1999a). Traditional supply chain systems identify a number of measures that are typically concerned with customer satisfaction or cost. However, moving towards more nuanced and meaningful performance measures are vital for supporting sustainable energy transitions (Lehtonen, 2013). An effective set of performance measures and metrics (PMM) are critical for successful implementation of sustainability programmes and actions over both the short and long term (Angappa Gunasekaran & Spalanzani, 2012). Such **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** have different types of application and influence; in the energy supply chain, KPIs can be applied internally (for own workings and calculations); externally (*e.g.*, communication with policy institutions and stakeholders); and support further decision-making (*e.g.*, use in official reports and evaluating progress) (Lehtonen, 2013). **Good performance indicators are direct, objective, quantitative, disaggregated as well as being practical and useable**

(Carlucci, 2010). Shahin and Mahbod (2007) put forward SMART criteria for KPI selection and application, that is Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-sensitive indicators (Figure 2).

Figure 2: SMART criteria for KPI selection and application, after (Shahin & Mahbod, 2007)

Performance metrics or KPIs provide us with an overall visibility of the supply chain and help in assessing the accuracy of supply/demand plan (*e.g.*, forecast accuracy), and the execution performance (*e.g.*, actual sales versus forecast plan). KPIs reveal the gap between plan and execution and offer opportunities to identify and correct potential problems (Chae, 2009), or to help steer supply chain performance in new directions (low environmental impact)². Performance measurement or monitoring offer vital feedback information on the performance of the supply chain (Chae, 2009). A measurement system should facilitate the assignment of metrics to where they would be most appropriate. For effective performance measurement and improvement, measurement goals must represent organisational goals, and the metrics selected should reflect a balance between financial and non-financial measures that can be related to strategic, tactical and operational levels of decision making and control (Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2004).

There has been increasing attention given to non-financial performance measures alongside financial measures (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011), an aspect which to date, has seen a dearth of research. Little attention has been given to measuring performance in the context of Sustainable Supply chains for instance (Taticchi *et al.*, 2013)³. Few studies provide a performance measurement (PM) inter-organisational perspective involving the key supply chain stakeholders, for instance (Taticchi *et al.*, 2013). There have been relatively few attempts to systematically collate measures for evaluating the performance of supply chains. Moreover, there is a lack of consensus over the most appropriate way to categorise them (Shepherd & Günter, 2006). Consistent criticisms highlight the limits of available performance measurement for supply chains (Shepherd & Günter, 2006; Taticchi *et al.*, 2013). These include:

- Lack of connection with strategy;

² The integration of sustainability considerations urgently requires the adaptation of business processes and new ways of thinking about corporate performance measurement, according to Searcy *et al.* (2005)

³ Performance measurements and metrics in SCM have not received due attention from both researchers and practitioners (Gunasekaran & Chung, 2004).

- Focus on cost to the detriment of non-cost indicators;
- Lack of a balanced approach (*e.g.*, insufficient focus on customers and competitors);
- Lack of system thinking (that encourages local optimisation).

Typical measurement systems for manufacturing supply chains, for example, encourage short termism; they lack strategic focus and fail to provide adequate information on what competitors are doing through benchmarking (Shepherd & Günter, 2006). However, performance measurements and metrics have an important role to play in evaluating performance and setting future course of actions and objectives (A. Gunasekaran & Chung, 2004), particularly when addressing pressing sustainability imperatives. The SCOR model proposed by the Supply-Chain Council (2013) suggests to measure performance based on five key supply chain processes; *plan, source, make, deliver and return* (APICS Supply Chain Council, 2015; Taticchi *et al.*, 2013).

From a business and economic perspective, Cabeza *et al.* (2015) suggest that a KPI is a performance measurement that evaluates the success of a particular activity. Success can be either the achievement of an operational goal (*e.g.*, zero defects, custom satisfaction, *etc.*) or the progress toward strategic goals. Selecting the right KPI relies upon a good understanding of what is important to the application/technology/*etc.* Aspects such as the present state of a technology and its key activities need to be assessed and are core to the selection of the KPIs (Cabeza *et al.*, 2015). Cabeza *et al.* (2015) note that KPIs are extensively used in business and financial assessments, and are gaining more importance in technical assessments. Key characteristics of KPIs include:

- Quantitative or qualitative indicators: The KPI may be measurable by giving a magnitude value (quantitative) or by giving a qualitative description without scale.
- Leading and lagging indicators: The KPI predicts the outcome of a process (leading KPI) or presents success or failure post hoc (lagging KPI).
- Process stage indicators: The KPI measures the amount of resources consumed during the generation of an outcome, represents the efficiency of the production of the process, or reflects the outcome or results of the process activities.
- Directional indicators: The KPI specifies whether or not one technology/application is being promoted and getting better – typically in the context of important performance parameters, *e.g.*, carbon reduction.
- Financial indicators: The KPI takes into account the economic aspects of one technology/ application.

Utilising KPIs in a meaningful way across the supply chain is essential to record, measure and manage areas that need to be improved. For example, utilising numerical performance systems or using readily available data applied over a long time-period (or as a time-series) can provide a more meaningful assessment of energy supply chains than simplistic qualitative evaluations such as “good”, “adequate” and “poor” (Beamon, 1999a). Yet such measures can often be impractical for use by certain stakeholders if these do not provide clear, concise and relevant messages that are accessible to a wide range of energy understandings and literacy.

A typical firm already has a certain number of KPIs, such as return on investment for assessing its financial performance, but supply chain related KPIs have not been widely adopted and businesses are typically uninformed of them (Chae, 2009). However, there remains a lack of practical guidelines on how to develop KPIs, and an understanding of how to define KPIs for their supply/demand chain remains lacking at the operational level (Chae, 2009).

3.2 Defining KPIs for the Energy Supply Chain

3.2.1 Key Performance Indicator Design and Development Process

An indicator design process provides a step-by-step guide for the development of indicators (Searcy, Karapetrovic, & McCartney, 2005). Further, Searcy et al. (2005) forward the following process for indicator development:

- Developing a conceptual framework
- Identifying the key issues that must be addressed
- Developing indicator selection criteria
- Developing a draft system of indicators

In terms of energy supply chains, Gunasekaran *et al.* (2004) indicate a number of areas that could be used as a framework for sustainable energy supply chain performance measurement. These include: (1) an evaluation of the supply links; (2) an evaluation of the delivery links; (3) measures for delivery performance; (4) the flexibility of the supply chain to provide energy that meets the individual demands of the consumer; and (5) cost-based analysis that relates to elements surrounding returns on investment and information processing costs. Measuring the greenness of a system in general, or a specific supply chain, should be flexible to allow changing priorities with changing industries or products (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). With respect to thermal energy storage (TES) KPIs, Cabeza *et al.* (2015) identify a substantial policy and practice gap. Up until now, only KPIs for TES in solar power plants and in buildings can be found. While Cabeza *et al.* (2015) quantify and compare these existing KPIs, they also indicate that TES can only be implemented by policymakers if more KPIs are identified for more applications.

Production sustainability includes managing the processes with sustainable inputs such as energy, people, equipment and machines with the objective of reducing waste, rework, inventory and delays as well as reducing carbon emissions (Angappa Gunasekaran & Spalanzani, 2012). Measuring the energy efficiency performance of equipment, processes and factories is the first step to effective energy management in production (May *et al.*, 2015). May *et al.* (2015), address the challenge whereby current industrial approaches lack the means and the appropriate performance indicators to compare energy-use profiles of machines and processes, and for the comparison of their energy efficiency performance to that of competitors'. May *et al.* (2015) therefore present a 7-step method which supports manufacturing companies in the development of production-tailored and energy-based performance indicators. This 7-step method involves: (1) a definition of the reference production system; (2) identification of different power requirements of the productive resource; (3) analysis of manufacturing states as causes of energy inefficiencies of the productive resource; (4) linking manufacturing states with energy states; (5) building a hierarchical framework of machine's energy consumption; (6) development of environmental-KPIs (e-KPIs); and (7) e-KPI design and management. Examples of such e-KPIs may include lean energy indicators

calculating the net energy consumption over overall energy consumption and overall energy usage whereby net usage energy is divided by energy in operating time (May *et al.*, 2015).

Manufacturing performance is usually assessed in terms of cost, quality, delivery, and flexibility, whereas environmental performance commonly measures the amounts of pollutants released into the air from industrial plants, and hazardous substances transferred from and to other plants/markets that probably end-up as landfill affecting soil and water quality (El Saadany *et al.*, 2011). The proposed method by May *et al.* (2015) supports the identification of weaknesses and areas for energy efficiency improvements related to the management of production and operations. Additionally, this method also strengthens the theoretical base necessary to support energy-based decision-making in manufacturing industries. Step 7 is an important part of this approach. Once the KPI system is designed, it must be managed for the purpose for which it has been created in order to enable the continuous improvement of energy-related indicators (May *et al.*, 2015). Neglecting to do so would lead to a lack of monitoring and measurement resulting in a lack of progress towards sustainability in the energy supply chain.

Finally, the full set of developed KPIs needs to be limited and restricted in number to allow ease of use and interpretation, as well as to enable regular updates and application / management responses. For instance, DEFRA report that 80% of businesses often have 5 or fewer KPIs monitoring environmental performance, DEFRA (2006) promote a voluntary set of guidelines for 22 KPIs (reported in full in DEFRA, 2006).

3.3 Synthesis of Review Insights: Defining KPIs for ENTRUST Task 2.2

The following process was applied to select KPIs for the characterisation of energy supply chains:

1. Key Themes for KPIs were identified, according to sustainability (triple bottom line) principles
2. Themes were divided into *Strategic, Tactical and Operational* dimensions following insights from the literature, and allowing differentiation of indicators at a range of scales
3. For each theme, a set of *Ideal Indicators* was defined for each dimension
4. These were reviewed by multiple project partners and assessed for suitability, level of appropriateness and practicality in implementation
5. Following the internal peer review process and subsequent brainstorming conference calls, some additional indicators were included in the list of *Ideal Indicators* (Table 3)
6. Critical review identified those indicators most suitable to the full indicator development stage as well as those indicators which were deemed unsuitable for development at this point of analysis. At this point of analysis, certain indicators were excluded for a range of reasons, including practicalities such as data availability, ability to concisely communicate indicators and replicability across energy supply chain stages and technologies.
7. A final general selection of KPIs was derived following this process and these were developed to provide a comprehensive characterisation of energy supply chains (Table 4). Main aim of this phase is the definition of the KPI *themes*, which will be used as a common guideline through all the document.
8. Separate to this indicator development process, a discreet set of indicators was developed for each specific stage of the energy supply chain. This deeper level of indicators definition is due to the assessment of the research team that the unique character of each stage and of each category

defined in that stage cannot be addressed in a general and integrative/comprehensive way. This is particularly true for end-user stage, since its critical importance in behaviour change initiatives warranted specific and tailored characterisation through bespoke end-user key performance indicators.

9. Key Performance Indicators for the Production, Transportation-Distribution and Storage stages are presented in **Error! Reference source not found..** KPIs for End-user stage of the energy supply chain are presented in Table 4 and
10. Table 5.

Table 1 presents the initial *Framework of Ideal Key Performance Indicators to Characterise Energy Supply Chains*. The rationale of this table is to maintain the defined themes as a guiding framework across all relevant technologies addressed; to provide consistency and a standardised approach to the characterisation of the energy supply chain as a whole and to ensure that a range of perspectives/scales was provided for each theme investigated.

Table 1: Framework of Ideal Key Performance Indicators to Characterise Energy Supply Chains

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Strategic Level Indicators</i>	<i>Tactical Level Indicators</i>	<i>Operational Level Indicators</i>
Greenhouse gas	<i>Contribution to national GHG profile</i>	<i>Location of emissions arising in supply chain</i>	<i>GHG profile @ operational level</i>
Waste Generation	<i>Contribution to national waste profile</i>	<i>Hazardous Waste?</i>	<i>Waste profile @ operational level</i>
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of produced energy</i>	<i>Cost per installation</i>	<i>Payback for typical investor</i>
Political commitment	<i>International arena</i>	<i>Political landscape</i>	<i>Investment support</i>
Technological Regime	<i>Infrastructure Lifespan</i>	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	<i>Social Acceptability</i>
Resource Outlook	<i>Resource remaining @ current usage</i>	<i>Theoretical resource availability</i>	<i>Level of new uptake /annum</i>
Public Opinion	<i>National public support</i>	<i>Public support monitoring</i>	<i>Acceptance of technology</i>
Consumer Behaviour	<i>National energy programme</i>	<i>Energy behavioural change monitoring</i>	<i>Level of new uptake</i>

Table 2 shows the first stage of ‘filtering’ applied to the full list of ideal indicators, demonstrating the selection of those indicators deemed most suitable for the purposes of D2.2. At this stage of analysis, practical considerations such as data availability, ability to concisely communicate indicators and replicability across technologies were incorporated. Subsequent to this, certain KPI’s were favoured for particular technologies and energy supply chain stages. While a standardised and consistent approach was highly valued in the KPI development process, an element of KPI differentiation was now required at this point, due to the particular characteristics of each technology category analysed. Technology specific KPIs were selected at this step, deemed most compatible with the technology in question and best suited to perform value comparisons were selected at this step.

Table 2: Framework of Selected Key Performance Indicators to Characterise Energy Supply Chains

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Strategic Level Indicators</i>	<i>Tactical Level Indicators</i>	<i>Operational Level Indicators</i>
Greenhouse gas			<i>GHG profile @ operational level</i>
<i>indicators</i>			Tonnes GHG per unit of fuel/energy produced
Environmental impact		<i>Impact level</i>	<i>Type of impact</i>
<i>indicators</i>		High-Medium-Low	Hazardous waste, landscape impact, noise, visual impact, etc.
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of produced energy</i>		
<i>indicators</i>	Levelised energy costs (LEC)		
Political commitment			<i>Investment support</i>
<i>indicators</i>			Available Grants & Policy Support
Technological Regime	<i>Infrastructure Lifespan</i>	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	
<i>indicators</i>	years / infrastructure	years since emergence	
Resource Outlook	<i>Resource remaining @ current levels of usage</i>		
<i>indicators</i>	Years worldwide		
Public Opinion	<i>National public support</i>	<i>Public support monitoring</i>	
<i>indicators</i>	Degree of acceptance of the technology (high-medium-low)	% change of acceptance during last years (growing-stable-decreasing)	

This first table has been used as a base reference and modified in order to better address each supply chain technology particularities. Table 3 shows the final guidelines defined for Energy production, storage, and transportation & distribution.

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators for production, Transportation-Distribution and Storage phases

Theme	Production	Transportation-Distribution	Storage
Environmental impact	GHG profile / Other major type of impact	Major type of impact	Major type of impact
<i>indicators</i>	Tonnes GHG per unit of fuel/energy produced / Impact level	Impact level	Impact level
Capital investment cost	Technology price	Technology price	Technology price
<i>indicators</i>	Levelised energy cost (LEC)	€/km - installation	Levelised cost of stored energy – installation
Performance index	Efficiency in energy transformation	Efficiency in energy transformation	Capacity
<i>indicators</i>	Output energy / Input energy	Energy carried/(carried + consumed + losses)	
Resource outlook / Flexibility	Resource remaining @ current level of usage	Technology flexibility	Technology flexibility
<i>indicators</i>	Years worldwide	Ability to reach different locations	Possibility to install facilities in different locations
Technological Regime	Infrastructure Lifespan	Infrastructure Lifespan	Infrastructure Lifespan
<i>indicators</i>	years / infrastructure	years / infrastructure	years / infrastructure
Technological Regime	Maturity of technology	Maturity of technology	Maturity of technology
<i>indicators</i>	years since emergence	years since emergence	years since emergence
Political commitment	Policies support	Policies support	Policies support
<i>indicators</i>	Available Grants & Policy Support	Available Grants & Policy Support	Available Grants & Policy Support
Public Opinion	National public support & Public support monitoring	National public support & Public support monitoring	National public support & Public support monitoring
<i>indicators</i>	Degree of acceptance of the technology	Degree of acceptance of the technology	Degree of acceptance of the technology

For the end-user phase of analysis, a unique KPI set was required. A specific and tailored characterisation through bespoke end-user key performance indicators was produced. It is worth noting that, as already mentioned above, the end-user stage of the supply chain is comprised of a great variety of technologies, which serve different purposes in different ways. This has resulted in a more variegated and case specific definition of the KPIs used to analyse each category of technologies within this document. The main defined themes have been kept as a common guideline through the entire document, while different KPIs have been defined for each specific case. For the sake of simplicity, not all the defined KPIs are presented in this introductory chapter, nonetheless, it is still possible to provide a general view of the themes and the approach implemented for the end-use stage. Table 4 presents the indicators developed and applied for the end-user stage, focusing on HVAC systems.

Table 5 presents the indicators developed and applied for the end-user stage, focusing on lighting and transport.

Table 4: Key Performance Indicators for End-user stage – HVAC systems

Theme	HVAC (Heating)	HVAC (Ventilation)	HVAC (Air Conditioning)
Environmental impact	Main type of environmental impact	Main type of environmental impact	Main type of environmental impact
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Level of impact</i>	<i>Level of impact</i>	<i>Level of impact</i>
Capital investment cost	Technology price	Technology price	Technology price
<i>indicators</i>	<i>End user device purchase/installation cost [€/kWh] -- payback</i>	<i>End user device purchase/installation cost [€/kWh] -- Years of payback</i>	<i>End user device purchase/installation cost [€/kWh] -- Years of payback</i>
Performance index	End user device efficiency	End user device efficiency	End user device efficiency
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Output energy / Input energy</i>	<i>Output energy / Input energy</i>	<i>Output energy / Input energy</i>
Technological Regime	Infrastructure Lifespan	Infrastructure Lifespan	Infrastructure Lifespan
<i>indicators</i>	<i>years / infrastructure</i>	<i>years / infrastructure</i>	<i>years / infrastructure</i>
Technological Regime	Maturity of technology	Maturity of technology	Maturity of technology
<i>indicators</i>	<i>years since emergence</i>	<i>years since emergence</i>	<i>years since emergence</i>
Political commitment	Policies support	Policies support	Policies support
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>
Public Opinion	National public support & Public support monitoring	National public support & Public support monitoring	National public support & Public support monitoring
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology, increase of the purchasing (high-medium-low/growing-stable-decreasing)</i>	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology, increase of the purchasing (high-medium-low/growing-stable-decreasing)</i>	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology, increase of the purchasing (high-medium-low/growing-stable-decreasing)</i>

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators for End-user stage – Lighting and Transport systems

Theme	Lighting	Transport
Environmental impact	Presence of toxic material requiring disposal	Polluting gas emission
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Yes / No</i>	<i>Kg of CO₂/distance</i>
Capital investment cost	Technology price	Technology price
<i>indicators</i>	<i>End user device purchase/installation investment [€/kWh]</i>	<i>End user device purchase/installation investment [€/kWh] -- Years of payback</i>
Performance index	End user device efficiency	End user device efficiency
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Energy Use (MJ/20 million lumen-hrs)</i>	<i>Cost of 100 km</i>
Technological Regime	Infrastructure Lifespan	Infrastructure Lifespan
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Hours of lifetime</i>	<i>years</i>
Technological Regime	Maturity of technology	Maturity of technology
<i>indicators</i>	<i>years since emergence</i>	<i>years since emergence</i>
Political commitment	Investment support	Investment support
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Policy Support</i>	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>
Public Opinion	National public support & Public support monitoring	National public support & Public support monitoring
<i>indicators</i>	<i>Market share, increase of the purchasing (high-medium-low/growing-stable-decreasing)</i>	<i>Market share, increase of the purchasing (high-medium-low/growing-stable-decreasing)</i>

3.4 KPIs evaluation process

Given the wide field covered by the research, the great number of technologies analysed and the different themes considered in the definition of the KPIs, the data research and final evaluation process has proved to be a complex one. Uniformity is needed among the presented data for all the selected technologies, since the aim of this evaluation is to compare the performances and peculiarities of different technological solutions.

Existing literature performing such an extensive comparison over such a wide range of technological solution is almost entirely absent, however it is possible to find more specific studies on a single technology or a more limited comparison of fewer technologies. When an extensive characterisation of the energy supply chain is performed, most of the time each technology is analysed by itself, without performing a global comparison, as in the case of the IEA Technology roadmaps.

For this reason, the evaluation process has resulted in the collection of extensive data from many different sources, and the reported values are representative of a mean value between the various sources. This is particularly true for less-technical data, such as estimates of the most significant environmental impacts, grants and policy supports, and public opinion. In particular, public opinion statistics were extremely difficult to find, especially for transport or storage technologies, as the media and research attention is mainly focused on electrical power production. Given these limitations the assessment of the KPI of public opinion has been produced by evaluating a number of different parameters such as:

- *Primary energy source*: as statistical data on public opinion for energy production are available, the type of primary energy that the technology uses can be taken as an indicator of public opinion.
- *Market share*: Especially for the end user, market share is a strong indicator of how many people are in favour of that technology.
- *Protest movements*: For transportation and storage technologies, the presence of protests against new installations has been considered as a negative indicator of public acceptance.

The final evaluation, public opinion, cannot be defined with a precise value due to the lack of consistent and official data, and so has been defined by giving a value on a scale from 1 to 5 (Low, Low-Medium, Medium, Medium-High, High).

For the sake of simplicity, the KPIs tables represent functional groups of technologies and do not provide data for every single technology described. The reader can make use of the KPIs tables to have an immediate and clear comparison between different technical energy solutions, with a more detailed description provided in each specific technology section. Here the different existing approaches are presented and detailed describing what makes them different, their specific approach, and what they are most suitable for. In order to better address the general target of the KPIs tables, often a range of values are proposed to the reader (*e.g.* efficiency value of 15-30%), representing the variation between the least, and the most, performing solution. For some particular cases, two different values are proposed for a single KPI, clearly indicating to which technology they refer.

The sources used for completing the KPIs tables are the same as those referenced in the description sections, unless specified differently.

4 Energy production

Figure 3: Production of primary energy, EU-28, 2013 (Eurostat, 2015b)

Primary energy production in the EU-28 is spread across a range of different energy sources. Eurostat data from 2013 show that the most important primary energy source, in terms of the size of its contribution, was nuclear energy (28.7 % of the total). Close to one quarter of the EU-28's total production of primary energy was accounted for by renewable energy sources (24.3 %), with a predominance of Biomass and waste among them. Overall, renewable sources experienced a fast growth over the period 2003-2013, with an increase of 88.4%. The share for solid fuels (19.7 %, largely coal) was just below one fifth and the share for natural gas was somewhat lower (16.7 %). Crude oil (9.1 %) was the only other major source of primary energy production. With an opposite trend with respect to renewable energies, the production of other primary sources generally decreased in this period, mainly for crude oil (-54%), natural gas (-34.6%) and solid fuels (-24.9%).

4.1 Electricity

When considering only electrical energy production, more than one quarter of the net electricity generated in the EU-28 in 2013 came from nuclear power plants (26.8 %), while almost double this share (49.8 %) came from power stations using combustible fuels such as natural gas, coal and oil (Eurostat, 2016). Figure 4 clearly shows the great predominance of nuclear and fossil fuels in the European energy mix.

Figure 4: Net electricity generation, EU-28, 2013 (Eurostat, 2015b)

This data is a direct representation of how the current European energy system is strongly characterised by a centralised production of electricity. Big fossil fuelled, nuclear and hydroelectric power plant produce electricity in specific restricted areas and subsequent transport and distribution is essential to provide electrical energy to the whole territory. Looking at the traditional power plants (fossil fuelled, nuclear and hydroelectric) installed in Europe, it is evident how central generation have a central role in the European energy production system (Hansen, 2001).

Following the growing concern towards environmental problems and GHG emission in the atmosphere, renewable energy has been strongly promoted in Europe during the last decades. Among the renewable energy sources, the highest share of net electricity generation in 2013 was from hydropower plants (12.8 %), followed by wind turbines (7.5 %) and solar power (2.7 %) (Eurostat,2016).

The relative importance of renewable energy sources in relation to EU-28 net electricity generation grew between 2003 and 2013 from 12.6 % to 23.2 %, while there was a relatively small decrease in the relative importance of combustible fuels from 56.4 % to 49.8 % and a larger reduction in the amount of electricity generated from nuclear power plants from 30.9 % to 26.8 %. Among the renewable energy sources, the proportion of net electricity generated from solar and wind increased greatly: from 0.01 % in 2003 to 2.7 % in 2013 for solar power and from 1.4 % in 2003 to 7.5 % in 2013 for wind turbines (Eurostat, 2016).

The fast growth of renewables is resulting in an important change in the energy generation and distribution system, due to the different nature of most renewable energy technologies with respect to traditional fossil fuels, with an increasing popularity of Distributed Generation (DG).

DG is characterised by a variety of energy production technologies integrated into the electricity supply system, and the ability of different segments of the grid to operate autonomously.

Energy systems can be made more robust by decentralising both power generation and control, resulting in an improved protection of the consumers against power interruptions and blackouts, whether caused by technical faults, natural disasters or terrorism. It is likely in the future that many consumers will have intelligent energy management systems based on two-way communication with energy suppliers, but improvements in this direction still need to be done at European level.

Distributed Generation can provide different advantages with respect to the traditional Centralised Generation (IEA, 2012):

- **GHG emissions reduction:** DG is based on a strong implementation of small scale renewable energies, in particular wind and solar, which can guarantee low to almost null air pollution.
- **Improved security:** The presence of many different generation points interconnected on the same grid allow easily overcoming failures and avoiding blackouts.
- **Improved efficiency:** Local generation of energy avoid the energy losses due to transportation and distribution phases, which usually range around 10%.
- **Reduced final costs:** Consumers can provide their own energy, saving transmission and distribution costs, which can account for up to 30% of the final energy price. They can also sell electricity back to the grid when their production exceeds their demand, resulting in a consistent reduction of the energy bill

On the other hand, the path to a correct DG implementation is not straightforward. The electrical grid needs to be amplified and upgraded to allow frequent electricity direction reversion, due to the strong variability of wind and solar, and big investment are needed to perform this restructuration. Moreover, small scale generation do not always result in a reduced environmental impact; when using the same energy source, big plant can reach higher efficiencies than individual solutions, resulting in an overall cleaner system.

DG is going to have a central role in the European energy system in the near future, but a good coordination with central distribution is needed, at least for the next decade. The increasing use of natural gas instead of coal in combination with Carbon Capture and Storage technologies, which are though still far from commercialisation, will contribute to decrease the GHG emissions of traditional plants, while maintaining a strong base to address the energy demand and provide back-up to variable renewable energies.

4.1.1 Coal

Coal has the largest share among fossil fuels for electricity generation. In 2013 the amount of electricity produced in coal fired power plants was the 26.7 % of the total European production (Eurostat, 2016), second only to Nuclear power. This is due to the fact that, even though EU is going towards a carbon free future, coal remains nowadays a very reliable and cheap way to produce electricity. It is also important to notice that coal deposits are present in Europe as well, making coal an even more economically attractive solution, since it helps reducing the energy import dependency of many European Countries.

Coal fired power plants have, on the other hand, several negative impact on the environment (Lako, 2010):

- **GHG emissions:** Firing coal to generate power produces a large amount of greenhouse gases. Coal plants are the primary cause of global warming, with a typical plant generating around 3.5 million tons of CO_2 in a year.
- **Coal storage:** Coal burned by power plants is typically stored onsite in uncovered piles. Dust blown from coal heaps irritates the lungs and often settles on nearby houses and yards. Rainfall creates runoff from coal heaps. This runoff contains pollutants that can contaminate land and water.
- **Water pollution:** In the same way as other conventional steam technologies, coal-fired plants require large amounts of water for steam and cooling, and can negatively affect local water resources and aquatic ecosystem.
- **Coal mining:** Surface coal mining have a strong impact, dramatically altering the landscape, while underground mining is one of the most hazardous of occupations, killing and injuring many in accidents, and causing chronic health problems.

4.1.1.1 **Pulverised Coal combustion (PCC) power plants**

Pulverised Coal (PC) combustion is the technology most widely used today for power generation. Thousands of units exist worldwide, accounting for well over 90% of total coal fired capacity. Different coals can be burned in PC, but this technology may not be best for coals with high ash content.

The coal is crushed and milled to a fine powder and blown into the boiler, where it is burned. The heat produced in the boiler generates steam, which is used to drive a steam turbine and generate electricity.

Grinding the coal into powder increases its surface area, which helps it to burn faster and hotter and reducing waste. Excess air is required to obtain as complete as possible combustion of the carbon (>99%), but modern designs are such to control and stage the addition of air in order to minimise the formation of NO_x. However, a de-NO_x plant may still be necessary to comply with environmental requirements (VV.AA., 2004).

Burning coal generates ash, which is removed and is usually sold to the building industry, where it is used as an ingredient in various building materials, like concrete. The exhaust gases are filtered in the exhaust stack, before being emitted into the atmosphere. The exhaust stacks of coal power stations are built tall so that the exhaust plume can disperse before it touches the ground. This ensures that it does not affect the quality of the air around the station.

Super-critical pulverised coal (SCPC) power plants use supercritical¹ steam as the process fluid to reach high temperatures and pressures, and efficiencies up to 46% (lower heating value, LHV). New ultrasupercritical (U-SCPC) power plants may reach even higher temperatures and pressure, with efficiency up to 50%.

4.1.1.2 **Integrated gasification combined cycles (IGCC)**

In integrated gasification combined cycles (IGCC) a thermo-chemical reaction with oxygen and steam is used to convert coal (or liquid fossil fuels) into a high-pressure syngas consisting of carbon monoxide (CO), hydrogen (H₂), and carbon dioxide (CO₂), with small amounts of hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). After being filtered to remove impurities, the gas is fired in a gas turbine and superheated steam is generated with the exhaust gas in the heat recovery steam generator (HRSG), which drives a conventional steam turbine and produces electricity in a connected second generator. The use of two thermodynamic cycles in cascade (from which the name of "combined cycle") allows gasification-based power systems to achieve high power generation efficiencies, with values rating from 39% to 45% (Lako, 2010).

4.1.2 **Oil**

Even though it has application in almost every aspect of our life, oil is not used so much in electricity generation in Europe. In 2013, only 1.9% of total electrical production came from oil fired power plants and this percentage is decreasing (Eurostat, 2016). This happens because oil is more expensive than coal, while having similar performances and environmental impacts.

Burning oil to generate electricity produces significant air pollution in the forms of nitrogen oxides, and, depending on the sulphur content of the oil, sulphur dioxide and particulates. Similar to coal-fired plants, polluted water used in the process can be reinserted in the environment. Sludge and oil residues that are not consumed during combustion represent a toxic and hazardous waste.

Drilling not only can cause serious geological problems, but also produces a long list of air pollutants, affecting the health and safety of workers and ecosystem. Refineries, too, spew pollution into the air, water and land (in the form of hazardous wastes). Oil transportation accidents can result in catastrophic damage killing thousands of fish, birds, other wildlife, plants and soil.

4.1.2.1 Oil-fired power plants

Oil-fired power plants work in a way similar to coal-fired ones. The main difference occurs at the beginning of the plant process, since the oil can be directly pumped in the boiler, while the coal needed to be crushed and milled first (EDF Energy, 2016a).

The main types of oil-fired power plants are:

- **Conventional steam:** Oil is burned to heat water, creating steam that drives a steam turbine to generate electricity.
- **Combustion turbine:** Oil is burned under pressure to produce hot exhaust gases, which directly spin a turbine to generate electricity.
- **Combined-cycle technology:** Oil is first combusted in a combustion turbine, using the heated exhaust gases to generate electricity. After these exhaust gases are recovered, they heat water in a boiler, creating steam to drive a second turbine

4.1.3 Gas

Natural gas is the cleanest energy source among the fossil fuels and the second most used after coal. In 2013, the 16.6% of the total European electricity production was obtained from natural gas power plants (Eurostat, 2016).

Over the last few decades, impressive advancement in technology has allowed a significant increase of natural gas plant efficiency, with simultaneous reduction of investment costs and GHG emissions. Electrical efficiency of new plants is expected to increase up to 64% by 2020 (Seebregts, 2010). One of the advantages of natural gas plants is flexibility and a fast response to electricity demand changes. In general, they have lower investment costs and higher fuel cost with respect to coal-fired power plants, and the overall economic aspects make coal a more convenient choice. Nonetheless, natural gas has lower GHG emissions, better meeting H2020 targets, and, thanks also to the reduction of gas prices in recent years, is gradually replacing coal in electricity production in Europe.

In particular, some of the advantages of natural gas with respect of coal are:

- **Lower GHG emissions:** Combustion of natural gas, used in the generation of electricity, industrial boilers, and other applications, emits lower levels of NO_x, CO₂, and particulate emissions, and virtually no SO₂ and mercury emissions.
- **Sludge reduction:** Natural gas emits extremely low levels of SO₂, eliminating the need for scrubbers, and reducing the amounts of sludge associated with power plants and industrial processes.
- **Cogeneration:** Natural gas is the preferred choice for new cogeneration applications.
- **Higher efficiency:** Natural gas plants can reach higher efficiency than coal-fired power plants, up to 60% against 48% (Seebregts, 2010).

Even if cleaner than the other fossil fuels, natural gas still has a negative impact on the environment. The principle greenhouse gases emitted include water vapour, carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides, and some engineered chemicals such as chlorofluorocarbons. While most of these gases occur in the atmosphere naturally, levels have been increasing due to the widespread burning of fossil fuels by growing human populations. One issue that has arisen with respect to natural gas and the greenhouse effect is the fact that methane, the principle component of natural gas, is itself a potent greenhouse gas. Methane has an ability to trap heat almost 21 times more effectively than carbon dioxide.

4.1.3.1 **Open cycle gas turbines (OCGT)**

Open cycle gas turbines (OCGT) for electricity generation consist basically of an air compressor and a gas turbine aligned on a single shaft connected to an electricity generator. Natural gas is pumped into the gas turbine, where it is mixed with air and burned, generating heat. Burning natural gas produces a mixture of gases called the combustion gas, which, expanded by heat, move to the gas turbine, providing the needed power to make it spin and mechanical electricity. This mechanical energy is then converted into electricity.

Almost two-thirds of the gross power output of the gas-turbine is needed to compress air, and the remaining one-third drives the electricity generator, resulting in a relatively low electrical efficiency, ranging between 35% and 42% (Seebregts, 2010).

4.1.3.2 **Combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT)**

Combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT) is nowadays the standard technology for new built gas-fired power plants. CCGT plants consist of compressor/gas-turbine groups – the same as the OCGT plants – but instead of discharging hot gas-turbine exhaust into the atmosphere, they are re-used in a heat recovery steam generator (HRSG). Here, water is heated to generate steam that drives a steam-turbine generator and produces additional power. Gas-turbine exhausts are then discharged into the atmosphere at about 90°C. Standard CCGT plants commonly consist of one gas turbine and one steam turbine, while large plants may have more than one gas turbine. Approximately two thirds of the total power is generated by the gas turbine and one-third by the steam turbine. At full-load, CCGT can reach electric efficiency up to 60% (VV.AA., 2004).

CCGT is a mature technology, with many CCGT plants built all over the world in the last 10-15 years. It is one of the dominant options for both intermediate-load (2000 to 5000 hrs/yr) or base-load (>5000 hrs/yr) electricity generation (Seebregts, 2010).

4.1.4 **Nuclear energy**

Nuclear power is the single most used energy source for electricity production in Europe. In 2013, 26.8% of the total electricity produced in Europe came from nuclear power plant (Eurostat, 2016). It is one of the cleanest way of producing electricity, with almost no GHG emissions, much less than most renewable energies and second only to wind. The use of nuclear power plants can also represent a powerful mean to improve energy independence of a Country, reducing the need for fossil fuel importation. This is the case, for example, of France, which has a strong base of nuclear power plants in its own territory.

The advantage of nuclear power with respect to renewable technologies is that it is a continuous source of energy, unlike sun and wind, and can allow for the production of large amount of electricity in order to cover the national demand.

On the other side, nuclear power present some very strong drawbacks, such as the creation of long-lasting radioactive wastes, which require hundreds of thousands of years to disappear, and the catastrophic risk potential if nuclear fuel containment fails. Disasters such as Chernobyl in 1986 or Fukushima in 2011 have shocked the public, which is now afraid of nuclear power.

It is clear how nuclear power is a controversial technology, providing at the same time high advantages and potentially catastrophic disadvantages. In recent years, important European countries, such as France and Germany, have started a program of nuclear power abandoning, following the rising opposition of public opinion.

4.1.4.1 **Nuclear fission power plant**

A nuclear power station makes use of the nuclear energy in uranium atoms to generate electricity. The core part of the plant is the reactor vessel: this is a tough steel capsule where the uranium is stored as rods into

metal cylinders. When a neutron hits a uranium atom, the atom sometimes splits, releasing two or three more neutrons. This process, called fission, release a great amount of heat energy. The fission process is accelerated having the fuel assemblies arranged in such a way that the neutrons released by an atom of uranium are likely to hit other atoms and make them split as well.

The heat generated by the fission reaction is exchanged with high-pressure water, since water needs to stay in liquid form for the power station to work. This pressurised water, with a temperature around 300°C, is moved from the reactor vessel to the steam generator, where it exchange heat with another circuit of lower pressure water. Due to the much less pressure, water in this second circuit is evaporated and steam then passes through a series of turbines in order to generate mechanical energy that will be converted to electricity. The thermal efficiency of a conventional nuclear power station is around 33%.

Nuclear power stations require significant investment to construct, due to the high level of technology and high security standards required, but their relatively low running costs over a long operational life make them one of the most cost-effective solutions for electricity production.

As already said, nuclear power has one of the smallest carbon footprints of any energy source, with the majority of CO_2 emissions coming from construction and fuel processing phases, not during electricity generation (EDF energy, n.a.).

4.1.4.2 *Fusion power*

Nuclear fusion is one of the most promising options for generating large amounts of carbon-free energy in the future. It is the process that heats stars, where atomic nuclei collide together and release energy in the form of neutrons.

The way this process is replicated on Earth to produce energy is by fusing light atoms such as hydrogen at extremely elevated pressures and high temperatures (100 million degrees Celsius). One promising way to achieve such extreme conditions is a particular technique called 'magnetic confinement', where extremely hot gas in the form of plasma is controlled with strong magnets.

Power stations using fusion would have a number of advantages:

- **No carbon emissions:** Fusion reactions only emit small amounts of helium, which is an inert gas that will not add to atmospheric pollution.
- **Abundant fuels:** Deuterium, the element used for nuclear fusion, can be extracted directly from water and tritium is produced from lithium, which can be extracted from the earth's crust. Due to the ease of provision, fuel supplies are almost unlimited.
- **Energy efficiency:** Nuclear fusion is an incredibly efficient process. One kilogram of fusion fuel can provide the same amount of energy as 10 million kilograms of fossil fuel.
- **No long-lived radioactive waste:** Differently from nuclear fission, a limited amount of radioactive waste is generated. In particular, only plant components become radioactive. These can be recycled or dispose of conventionally within 100 years.
- **Safety:** Since only a very small amounts of fuel is used in fusion devices a large-scale nuclear accident is not possible.
- **Reliable power:** In the same way as nuclear fission plants, fusion power plants can generate electricity in continuous and controlled way, at costs similar to other traditional energy sources. Nuclear fission can therefore become an excellent solution to renewable energies variability.

Nuclear fusion is currently at an experimental phase. The International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) is an experimental fusion reactor in the south of France aiming to demonstrate the feasibility of fusion as a viable source of energy (Culham Centre for Fusion Energy, 2012).

4.1.5 KPIs evaluation for non-renewable energies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the non-renewable energy production technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. It helps giving a clear and simple understanding of each technology strength and weakness towards a low carbon future.

The main sources that inform Table 6, below, come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of LCOE (2014), Schlömer *et al.* (2014), Shahriar (2008), Lazard (2014), Honorio (2003) and European Commission (2007).

Table 6: KPIs evaluation for non-renewable energies

Theme	Type of indicator	Coal	Oil	Gas	Nuclear
GHG emissions	<i>Life-cycle emissions level (gCO_{2eq}/kWh)</i>	1001	840	469	16
Environmental impact	<i>Type</i>	GHG emissions	GHG emissions	GHG emissions	Hazardous waste
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	High	High	Medium-high	High
Capital investment cost	<i>Levelised energy cost (€/MWh)</i>	66-151€	297-332€	102-171€	92-132€
Performance index	<i>Efficiency</i>	35-48%	35-45%	32-60%	33-36%
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan (years)</i>	40	40	20 (gas turbine) 40	30-40
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	Mature	Mature	Mature	Mature
Resource outlook	<i>Resource remaining worldwide (years left at current usage level)</i>	107	35	37	-
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Energy Roadmap 2050 2030 climate & energy framework			

		(Each member state is free to take individual decisions on the measures to reach the set objectives)			
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Low	Low	Medium	Low

Non-renewable energies still represent nowadays the great majority of source of electrical energy in Europe. In order to reach the Europe 2020 target of a 20% reduction in GHG emissions, natural gas is increasing its market share replacing coal. It is well visible from the table that a complete replacement of coal with natural gas could decrease the power plants emissions by half, without even considering renewable energies. The lower cost of coal is what keeps it strong on the market. Due to an environmental impact and performances similar to coal, but a higher fuel cost, oil is not much used as a source of energy in power plants. The situation of nuclear energy, as already said, is very controversial: it is one of the technologies with the lowest GHG emission rate and its performances are similar to fossil fuels, allowing for big plants and high level of energy produced. The main drawback of nuclear energy is the hazardous waste it produces, which is the most dangerous among all energy technologies.

4.1.6 Hydraulic

Hydropower is the most common renewable source used for electricity production, with a share of around 13% for net electricity generation at EU level. When considering only renewable energies, Hydraulic power accounts, as of 2013, for the 45.5% of the total electricity produced in Europe (Eurostat, 2016).

It has been used since ancient times for several applications, such as driving watermills or other mechanical devices, and in the late 19th century, hydropower became a source for generating electricity. Today the term is used almost exclusively in conjunction with the development of hydroelectric power.

There are several ways to generate electricity through the use of moving water force, the most known and common being a river flow stream channelled into a power plant turbine. More recently, following the need for cleaner and renewable energy, improvements have been made in tide and wave energy conversion.

4.1.6.1 Hydro Electric power plants

4.1.6.1.1 Conventional impoundment

The most common type of hydroelectric power plant is an impoundment facility. An impoundment facility, typically a large hydropower system, uses a dam to store river water in a reservoir. Water released from the reservoir flows through a turbine, spinning it, which in turn activates a generator to produce electricity.

Figure 5: Hydroelectric dam scheme (Tomia, 2007)

The water may be released either to meet changing electricity needs or to maintain a constant reservoir level.

Conventional impoundment power plants present several advantages with respect to fossil fuel ones, but also some important drawback. In particular, the main pros are:

- **Flexibility:** Hydro turbines have a start-up time of the order of a few minutes, much shorter than for gas turbines or steam plants. Hydropower stations can also be ramped up and down very quickly to adapt to changing energy demands.
- **Low power costs:** The major advantage of hydroelectricity is elimination of the cost of fuel, making its operating cost nearly immune to increases in the cost of fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas or coal. The average cost of electricity from a hydro station larger than 10 megawatts is 3 to 5 euro-cents per kilowatt-hour (Worldwatch Institute, 2012). Operating labour cost is also usually low, as plants are automated and have few personnel on site during normal operation.
- **Reduced air and water pollution:** Since hydroelectric dams do not burn fossil fuels, they do not directly produce greenhouse gases. Also the water passed through the turbine is guided back into the river uncontaminated.

On the other side, the main cons of this technology are:

- **Ecosystem damage and loss of land:** The construction of large dams result in submersion of extensive areas, sometimes destroying biologically rich ecosystems, and causing land erosion. The downstream river environment can be altered as well, since the water exiting a turbine usually contains very little suspended sediment, which can result in scouring of river beds and loss of riverbanks.

- **Siltation and flow shortage:** Heavy particles, transported by the water flow, tend to accumulate in the reservoir. Siltation can fill a reservoir and reduce its capacity to control floods along with causing additional horizontal pressure on the upstream portion of the dam.
- **Relocation:** Due to the submerging of a wide area which was previously habitable, all the people living where the reservoirs are planned need to be relocated.
- **Failure risks:** Due to the huge amount of water confined in a reservoir, failures due to poor construction or natural disasters can have catastrophic consequences. Dam failures have been some of the largest man-made disasters in history.

As of 2015, the largest hydroelectric power station is the Three Gorges Dam in China, with a generating capacity of 22500 MW (News Xinhuanet, 2015). Overall, thanks to the great power generated by falling water and the high energy transformation efficiency, hydropower is suitable for large power plant, accounting for the five largest power stations in the world, in terms of current installed electrical capacity.

4.1.6.1.2 Run-of-the-river hydroelectricity

Run-of-the-river (ROR) hydroelectricity is a type of hydroelectric generation plant whereby little or no water storage is provided and is, therefore, subject to seasonal river flows. Only a small dam is usually built to ensure that enough water enters the penstock pipes that lead to the turbines. This technology is well suited for streams that can naturally sustain a minimum flow throughout the whole years.

When developed with care to footprint size and location, ROR hydro projects can create sustainable energy minimising impacts to the surrounding environment and nearby communities. It still possesses the ability to produce clean energy with no GHG emissions, while at the same time avoiding many of the negative impacts that dams have on the landscape and ecosystem.

On the other side, the plant will operate as an intermittent energy source, highly dependent on seasonal flow and with no possibility to follow the energy demand. Moreover, even if it true that ROR have a reduced impact on the ecosystem, it is not easy to find good areas for their implementation and large plants still present environmental concerns, due to their dimensions.

4.1.6.1.3 Pumped-storage

Another type of hydropower called pumped storage works like a battery, storing the electricity generated by other power sources like solar, wind, and nuclear for later use. When the demand for electricity is low, a pumped storage facility stores energy by pumping water from a lower reservoir to an upper reservoir. During periods of high electrical demand, the water is released back to the lower reservoir and turns a turbine, generating electricity (Energy.gov, 2016).

4.1.6.2 **Tidal power**

Tidal power is a form of hydropower that converts the energy obtained from tides into useful forms of power, mainly electricity. One of the main advantages of tidal power is that tides are more predictable than other renewable sources like wind and solar.

Nowadays tidal energy generators are not yet widely used, due to a relatively high cost and limited availability of sites with sufficiently high tidal ranges or flow velocities. Those factors have been a strong

limit to tidal power growth, but thanks to recent technological developments and improvements, together with the renewable nature of tide power, this type of energy source could play an important role in a future European low carbon energy system (Kempener, 2014).

4.1.6.2.1 Tidal barrage

A tidal barrage is a dam-like structure that is built across the mouth of a river or bay in order to harvest energy from the ebb and flow of tides in the location.

A tidal barrage is usually positioned at an estuary, bay, river, or other ocean inlet and contains gates called sluices that can open and close, in order to control the water flow. At low tide, the gates open and allow the tide to flow into the river as normal as the tide rises. When high tide is reached, the gates are closed and prevent the water from retreating back to the ocean as it normally would. Instead, the water is forced through specific channels that direct it through turbines in order to produce electricity (Evans, 2007). Figure 6 show a schematic view of this process.

Figure 6: Tidal barrage scheme

Tidal barrage is a simple and mature technology and is the most similar to other forms of hydroelectric generation, as the one seen in the previous chapter, that involve a dam to control the water flow.

Unfortunately, there are a number of disadvantages to tidal barrages that have kept them from becoming more popular. The first disadvantage is cost. Building a large dam across the mouth of a river or the inlet of a bay is more complicated and costly than building a dam on a river.

More than the economic impact, the environmental impact of tidal barrages is a serious consideration in their construction. Estuaries, river mouths, and bays are sensitive ecosystems that often represent the spawning grounds for species that may not breed anywhere else. Altering the flow of sea water negatively

affects a number of marine mammals as well as fish, crustacean, and plant life (Renewable Northwest Project, 2006).

4.1.6.2.2 Tidal stream generators

Tidal Stream Generators (also called Tidal Energy Converters) are simple machines that extract energy from the movement of water with the tides. The name derives from the fact that the machines are placed in the path of the tide, called the tidal stream. They are the cheapest and most common type electricity generation from tidal power.

Certain types of these machines function very much like underwater wind turbines, and are thus often referred to as tidal turbines. In fact, tidal stream generation is more similar to wind energy than it is to hydroelectric power generation. Turbines come in many shapes, with both horizontal and vertical axis. The former type is the most commonly used, due to its simplicity, while the latter is to be preferred in settings where the direction of the tidal stream varies, since vertical axis turbines do not need to be directed perfectly into the stream of the tide. Many turbines can run in both forward and reverse directions, in this way taking advantage of both phases of the tide. Since water is 800 times denser than air and thus provides more contact with the blades of the rotor, a water flow rate of 2-3 meters per second (which is about average in most places except at neap tide) would translate into four times more energy for every turn of the turbine as compared to wind (Tidal Power, n.d.).

Since they do not need the construction of a dam to work, tidal streams generators are easy and cheap to implement, can be implemented in already existing structures and their modularity allows small site to be easily expanded. On the other side, due to the smaller velocity of stream involved, they generally cannot produce as much power as barrage systems.

4.1.6.2.3 Dynamic Tidal Power

Dynamic Tidal Power or DTP is the most complicated, least well understood tidal power scheme yet conceived. It makes use of the fact that ocean tides don't operate strictly perpendicular to the shore, but also flow in parallel to the shore. This phenomenon is particularly strong in some areas, such as some Chinese and northern European coasts. Building a barrage perpendicular to the coast, as shown in Figure 7, it would be possible to harvest energy from this type of tides as they flow parallel to the shore.

Figure 7: DTP scheme (TidalPower UK, n.d.)

The red represents relative high water and blue represents relative low water. Shifting in the tide direction, and consequently in the height sides, usually happens every 12 hours.

The system only works if the barrage is at least 30 kilometres long and only if the turbines work in both directions. So far, the system has been proven in theory, but it has never been put to the test and there is no way to be certain the scheme will really work without experiments.

The main advantage of dynamic tidal power is that a single installation could produce from 8 to 15 GW of power, orders of magnitude more than any other tidal energy system (Kempener, R., & Neumann, F. 2014). An 8 GW installation could generate enough electricity in a year for more than three million Europeans. Since it generates power in both tide directions, DTP is stable and more continuous than other forms of tidal energy. Finally, due to its large dimensions, DTP can be combined with other solution such as wind turbines, solar panels, aquaculture and research facilities, and more.

The main disadvantage with DTP is that there is no way to be certain it will work without building a facility, which is very expensive (tens of billions of euros) and presents many engineering difficulties associated with building a 30 km dam out into the ocean. Environmental impacts cannot be determined as well without building one DTP structure, and blocking a large portion of coastal flow may have a tremendous ecologic impact.

4.1.6.3 **Wave power**

Wave power is generated from the bobbing motion of objects that float in the ocean. Energy from the wave crest itself lifts the object against gravity endowing it with potential energy. When the wave crest passes, the object falls into the wave trough, which translates its energy from potential to kinetic. With a mechanical device it is possible to convert this energy into electricity.

Another method of generating energy from waves involves a combination of wind and water energy. Water from the wave rises up inside a chamber, thus displacing air. This, in turn, pushes a small fan that generates electricity. When the water falls, air rushes back into the chamber and turns the fan once again. Such systems are generally only found in small-scale applications (Renewable Northwest, 2009).

The concept of wave energy has good potential, especially due to the fact that waves almost constantly provide power, but has gained little interest compared to other forms of energy generation due to the difficulty of maintaining equipment and generating large enough quantities of electricity at an affordable price. Wave farms that are used for testing the concept of wave power can be found in Portugal, the United Kingdom, Australia, and the United States. Currently, the only real application of wave power is in buoys that have lights or GPS tracking embedded in them.

4.1.6.4 Ocean Thermal Energy

Ocean thermal energy relies on the difference in temperature between the cool deep water of the ocean and warmer surface water, providing power to a heat engine, which can in turn be used to generate electricity. Warm ocean water is either allowed to boil itself or is used to boil a secondary low-boil temperature fluid. The gas that is generated is used to turn a turbine and generate electricity and then condensed back to liquid by cold ocean water so that the cycle can repeat itself. Ocean thermal energy is a continuous renewable energy, since difference in ocean temperature at different depths is always present, making it a good potential solution to provide an electrical base load when other sources as solar or wind are not working (VV.AA., 2011c: 87).

The main technical challenge of Ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC) is to generate significant amounts of power efficiently from small temperature differences. Modern designs allow performance approaching the theoretical maximum Carnot efficiency. Another issue is that getting cold water to the surface requires energy, so some of the energy produced from these systems is lost, making them necessarily less efficient than wave, tidal, or traditional hydropower.

4.1.7 Wind

Wind power is the second most used renewable energy source for electricity production, with a market share, among renewables, of 26.5% in 2013. Between 2000 and 2010 the global capacity of wind industry has increased an average of 30% per year, reaching 200GW installed in 2010, and it is still growing fast today. 2012 was a record year for new onshore wind installations with over 46GW of capacity built in the year. Offshore wind has had a slower growth due to higher installation and running costs, but it is foreseen it will reach nearly 50GW of global capacity by 2020 (Eurostat, 2016). It is no surprise, then, that wind power is becoming an increasingly important in many countries as part of a strategy to reduce their reliance on fossil fuels towards EU2020 objectives.

The main advantage of using wind power is that wind is abundant, inexhaustible, and affordable, making it a good alternative to fossil fuels. It is also one of the cleanest and most sustainable ways to generate electricity as its life cycle greenhouse gas emissions (11.5 gCO₂eq/kWh) are the lowest among renewables and comparable to nuclear power ones.

On the other side, wind is not controllable nor predictable, making it necessary to use it in conjunction with other, more controllable, ways of generating electricity, in order to be able to always sustain the grid energetic demand. The main environmental issue related with wind power is turbines sound and visual impact. Some people living close to wind facilities have complained about sound and vibration issues, while, when it comes to aesthetics, wind turbines can elicit strong opposite reactions (IEA, 2013a). In any case, any new installation needs to be discussed in advanced with the local communities, in order to avoid NIMBY reactions.

4.1.7.1 On-shore wind turbines

Wind turbines are devices used to convert wind kinetic energy into the mechanical rotating energy and finally into electricity. Each wind turbine is a standalone independent unit, this providing high modularity to the technology. They can come in several dimensions and shapes, all belonging to two main concepts, horizontal and vertical rotation axis. Horizontal axis turbines (with three blades) are the most efficient and common type, and have a dominant share on today's market, while vertical axis ones, though presenting some advantages with respect to the other type, are almost abandoned (IEA,2013a).

4.1.7.2 Off-shore wind turbines

Offshore wind power or offshore wind energy refers to the construction of wind farms offshore to generate electricity from marine wind. The advantage of this approach is that wind speeds are generally stronger offshore compared to on land, so offshore wind power can manage to provide a greater amount of electrical power. In addition, offshore breezes can be strong in the afternoon, matching the time when people are using the most electricity. Another point in favour of offshore turbines is that the rising of NIMBY opposition to their construction is usually much weaker than with on shore ones, due to the distance of the offshore wind farms to people activities.

While the offshore wind industry has grown dramatically over the last several decades, especially in Europe, offshore wind farms are still relatively expensive. According to the US Energy Information Agency, offshore wind power is the most expensive energy generating technology being considered for large scale deployment. Prices can be in the range of 2.5-3.0 million €/MW (EWEA, 2015), with the turbine representing just one third to one half of the cost and the rest coming from infrastructure and maintenance.

Environmental impact of offshore turbines and of the associated infrastructures is still not completely clear and discussion are rising on how the construction and operation of these wind farms affect the marine ecosystem. Common environmental concerns include:

- The risk of seabirds being struck by wind turbine blades
- The underwater noise associated with the turbine operation
- The physical presence of offshore wind farms altering the behaviour of marine animals with both possibilities of attraction and avoidance;
- The potential disruption of the local marine environment from large offshore wind projects.

4.1.7.3 **Vortex bladeless**

Vortex is a new technology currently under development, consisting of a wind generator without blades. Instead of capturing energy via the rotational motion of a turbine, the Vortex takes advantage of the so called 'vorticity', an aerodynamic effect that occurs when wind breaks against a solid structure. The Vortex structure starts to oscillate, and captures the mechanical energy that is produced to transform it into electricity. An advantage of Vortex technology is that it is designed to have no parts in contact at all (no gears, linkages, etc.) in order to make it cheap and easy to maintain. This technology should be able to produce energy at a 40% lower cost than a comparable wind installation and, thanks to the elimination of mechanical elements that can suffer wear and tear from friction, it is estimated to reduce maintenance cost by 80 %.

Finally, Vortex is silent, since it oscillates at a frequency that doesn't produce audible noise (it is below 20 Hz), has smaller dimensions than a normal wind turbine and it's also safer for birds, eliminating the possibility of collision with turbine blades.

The reduced cost and dimensions allow for a higher density of installation, which compensates for a lower efficiency of energy conversion (30% less). Computational modelling estimates operational lifetime of the installation to be between 32 and 96 years (Indiegogo, 2016).

4.1.8 *Solar*

Solar energy is the most abundant renewable energy source available on Earth. Just 18 days of sunshine contain the same amount of energy as all of the planet's reserves of coal, oil, and natural gas. Solar power has increased rapidly its market share in recent years and, in 2013, accounted for 10 % of all renewable electricity, 2.7% of the total European electricity production. Also, in 2013 the electricity generated from solar energy surpassed wood and other solid biomass, becoming the third most important contributor to the electricity production from renewable sources (Eurostat, 2016).

Like wind power, the sun provides a tremendous resource for generating clean and sustainable electricity. Solar power does not lead to any harmful emissions during operation, but some pollution is generated during the solar panels production phase, making it a less clean energy than wind.

Another advantage of solar systems is that they can be built both in small installations, to provide electricity for homes, buildings and remote power needs (this is particularly true for poor regions), and at utility-scale, to produce energy as a central power plant.

Different types of solar panels are present on the market, having average efficiency ranging from 15% to 25%, respectively (Honorio, 2003: 11). Efficiency is highly dependent from the amount of sunrays that hit the panels, and therefore varies a lot depending on the geographical region and the period of the year. This has consequences also on the payback time of the system. In southern Europe, this is approximately 1 to 2 years and increases at higher latitudes (IEA, 2013d, 31). This is a very fast payback period, considering an average system life expectancy of 30 years.

The environmental impacts associated with solar power can include land use and habitat loss (in particular for large solar plants), water use, and the use of hazardous materials in panels manufacturing, though the types of impacts vary greatly depending on the scale of the system and the technology used.

4.1.8.1 **Photovoltaic**

Photovoltaic is a technology that converts light into electrical energy thanks to a photovoltaic system called solar cell. Both a physical and chemical process take place, generating an electric current. Multiple solar cells are mutually connected in a photovoltaic module thus total capacity of PV system is increased. PV modules produce direct current, which then needs to be converted into alternating current by an inverter. Typical conversion efficiencies for PV modules can reach values up to 20% and over (IEA, 2013d, 29).

PV system can be used as grid connected systems, and as off-grid systems. These systems are mainly installed on roofs and have relatively small capacity. When available they are connected to the grid, especially in developed countries with large markets, in order to sell the electricity when production exceeds the needs. Building integrated PV systems are a green and cost effective solution, since they allow on-site electricity generation and deployment of unused roof area. In certain applications such as lighthouses, or in developing countries, exceeding produced electricity can be stored in batteries or additional power generators, in order to allow operations at night and at other times of limited sunlight. With introduction of incentive scheme for RES electricity production, grid connected system for electricity generation become main application of PV (IEA, 2012d).

4.1.8.2 **Concentrated solar power**

Concentrating solar power (CSP) systems use mirrors to concentrate the energy from the sun to drive traditional steam turbines or engines that create electricity. The main solar concentrating technologies used nowadays are:

- **Parabolic trough:** it consists of a linear parabolic reflector that concentrates light onto a receiver positioned along the reflector's focal line.
- **Compact Linear Fresnel Reflectors:** It's a system which uses many thin mirror strips instead of parabolic mirrors to concentrate sunlight onto two tubes with working fluid.
- **Stirling solar dish:** it combines a parabolic concentrating dish with a Stirling engine which normally drives an electric generator. The advantages of Stirling solar over photovoltaic cells are higher efficiency of converting sunlight into electricity and longer lifetime.
- **Solar power tower:** An array of tracking reflectors is used to concentrate light on a central receiver positioned at the top of a tower.

For all of these technologies it is possible to use various techniques to track the sun and focus light in a single point, improving the overall system efficiency. The concentrated sunlight is then used to heat a working fluid, which generates power through a turbine (Energy Gov., 2016a).

Environmental impact is low, but due to the high concentrated heat generated by this type of technology, there has been numerous reports of birds injured or killed.

4.1.8.3 **Concentrator photovoltaic**

Concentrator photovoltaics (CPV) systems employ sunlight concentrated onto photovoltaic surfaces for the purpose of electrical power production. They basically combine together photovoltaic and concentrating solar systems, using lenses and curved mirrors to focus sunlight onto small, but highly efficient solar cells. Solar concentrators are often mounted on a solar tracker in order to keep the focal point upon the cell as

the sun moves across the sky. This solution can drastically improve efficiency of PV-solar panels (IEA, 2013d).

Figure 8: Concentrator PV panel

4.1.8.4 **Floatovoltaics**

Floatovoltaics are an emerging form of PV systems that float on the surface of water. The advantage of these systems is similar to the ones of offshore wind: they reduce the need of valuable land area and, as the panels are kept at a cooler temperature than they would be on land, they allow a higher efficiency of solar energy conversion. Floatovoltaic panels also make it possible to save drinking water that would otherwise be lost through evaporation. This is a great advantage for poor countries with limited access to both centralised power and drinking water (Energynnovation.it, 2016).

4.1.8.5 **Fully transparent solar panels**

It consists of a solar cell that absorb infrared and UV light, letting visible light pass through and therefore looking transparent. Until now, solar cells of this kind have been only partially transparent and usually a bit tinted, but a Michigan State University research team have managed to create new ones that are so clear that they're practically indistinguishable from a normal panel of glass. This technology is currently at research stage, and it can achieve only 1% efficiency, but the hope is to reach 10% after industrialisation. The range of possible application is huge, such as for example windows and smartphone screens (ExtremeTech, 2015).

4.1.9 **Geothermal**

Geothermal power take advantage of the natural heat generated from radioactive decay inside Earth. It has been used for bathing since Palaeolithic times and for space heating since ancient Roman times. Nowadays

it is used for both electricity and heat production. In 2013, 0.2% of total electricity in Europe has been produced through geothermal power (Eurostat, 2016). Thanks to technological improvement, it is possible to build geothermal electric plants not only on areas where high temperature geothermal resources are available near the surface, but over a much greater geographical range.

The thermal efficiency of geothermal electric plants is low, around 10–23%, because geothermal fluids do not reach the high temperatures of steam from boilers. When possible, exhaust heat can be used locally to provide heating to near buildings. Since the heat from ground is constantly available, the main efforts in improvements are not on system efficiency but rather on operational costs, in order to reduce the payback period. Geothermal plants regularly operating at 90% or more of their rated capacity, being therefore most often used for providing baseload energy, increasing system reliability and lowering overall operating costs.

While not requiring any fuel to produce heat, geothermal heating systems contain pumps and compressors, which may consume energy from a polluting source. Fluids drawn from the deep earth carry a mixture of gases, notably carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), methane (CH₄) and ammonia (NH₃). Another important environmental impact of geothermal power is relative to the plant construction, when drilling operation can cause subsidence, tectonic uplift or trigger earthquakes as part of hydraulic fracturing (Kagel, Bates and Gawell, 2007).

4.1.9.1 **Dry steam power station**

Dry steam stations are the simplest and oldest design. They directly use geothermal steam of 150°C or greater to generate electricity from turbines. This solution is applicable when a natural underground resource of steam is available at the proper temperature. For this reason, there are not many power plants of this type in the world (IEA, 2012b: 15).

Figure 9: Dry steam power station scheme

4.1.9.2 **Flash steam power station**

In a flash steam process, water from underground wells is separated (flashed) into steam and water. The water is directly returned to the geothermal reservoir by injection wells, where it can be heated again,

while the steam is used to drive a turbine and generate electricity. After passing through the turbine, the steam is cooled again to liquid form and then also re-injected into the geothermal reservoir.

In order to operate correctly, any gases or pollutant in the steam are removed. For very high temperature resources, the water can be controlled to flash more than once to recover even more energy from the same resource (IEA, 2012b: 14).

4.1.9.3 **Binary cycle power station**

A binary cycle power plant is used for moderate-temperature resources. The hot water from a geothermal source is used to heat a secondary working fluid in a closed-loop system. The working fluid is vaporised in a heat exchanger and is then used to drive a turbine generator. A cooling system is used to condense the vaporised working fluid back into liquid form to begin the process again. The hot water from the geothermal resource is injected back into the reservoir where it can be re-heated. The hot water and the working fluid are kept separate, so that environmental issues are minimal (IEA, 2012b: 15).

4.1.10 **Bioenergies**

Bioenergy, the energy from plants and plant-derived materials, has been used in history since people began burning wood to cook food and keep warm. Wood is still the largest biomass energy resource today, but many others are commonly used such as food crops, residues from agriculture, oil-rich algae, and the organic component of municipal and industrial wastes.

The use of biomass energy has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Even though biomass generates about the same amount of carbon dioxide as fossil fuels, this amount of pollution is compensated by new plants, which are going to absorb the same amount of carbon dioxide. The final net emission of carbon dioxide will be zero as long as plants continue to be replenished for biomass energy purposes (Renewable Energy World.com, 2016).

It has to be considered, though, that the evaluation is not that easily computed as 1:1 between emitted CO_2 and newborn plant absorbed CO_2 . Clearing forests to grow biomass could result in a carbon penalty that takes decades to recover, so environmental agencies suggest to use biomass to help in the path towards a low-carbon economy, but not as a final solution. It is also possible to reduce the environmental impact growing biomass on previously cleared land, such as under-utilised farm land, instead of clearing forests.

4.1.10.1 **Direct biomass combustion**

Most electricity generated from biomass is produced by direct combustion using conventional boilers. These boilers primarily burn waste wood products from the agriculture and wood-processing industries. When burned, the wood produces steam, which spins a turbine. The spinning turbine then activates a generator that produces electricity.

4.1.10.2 **Biomass co-firing**

Co-firing involves replacing a portion of the petroleum-based fuel in high-efficiency coal-fired boilers with biomass. Co-firing biomass can significantly reduce the SO_2 emissions of coal-fired power plants and is a least-cost renewable energy option for many power producers (IEA, 2012a: 15).

4.1.10.3 Biomass gasification

Gasification is a thermochemical process in which biomass is transformed into a mixture of several combustible gases, called fuel gas. Gasification is a highly versatile process, due to the fact that almost any dry biomass feedstock can be converted to fuel gas. The advantage of gasification is that using the syngas is that it can be combusted at higher temperatures than the original fuel, resulting in a more efficient process. The produced gas can be used to generate electricity directly via engines or by using gas turbines, with the possibility to guarantee higher efficiency than via a steam cycle, particularly in small-scale plants (IEA, 2012a: 15).

4.1.10.4 Anaerobic digestion

Anaerobic digestion is a common technology used to convert organic waste to electricity or heat. In anaerobic digestion, some particular bacteria decompose organic matter, in the absence of oxygen, producing methane and other by-products that form a renewable natural gas (IEA, 2012a).

4.1.11 KPIs evaluation for renewable energies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the renewable energy production technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. It helps giving a clear and simple understanding of each technology strength and weakness towards a low carbon future. The main sources that inform Table 7, below, come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of Schlömer *et al.* (2014), Lazard (2014), Honorio (2003) and European Commission (2007).

Table 7: KPIs evaluation for renewable energies

Theme	Type of indicator	Hydro	Tide	Solar	Wind	Geothermal	Bioenergies
GHG Emissions	<i>Life-cycle CO₂ emissions (gCO₂eq/kWh)</i>	24	17	45	12	38	20
Environmental impact	<i>Main environmental impact</i>	Landscape	Landscape	Hazardous waste	Visual - Noise	GHG Emissions	GHG Emissions
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	High	High	Low-medium	Medium	Low-Medium	Low-Medium
Capital investment cost	<i>Levelised energy cost (€/MWh)</i>	86.4	450	210.7	97 (onshore) 243.2 (offshore)	101.7	112.5
Performance index	<i>Efficiency</i>	95%	85-90%	12-20%	30-45%	25-60%	35-40%
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan</i>	40	40-50	25-30	30	20-30	25
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Energy Roadmap 2050 2030 climate & energy framework (Each member state is free to take individual decisions on the measures to reach the set objectives)					
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium-High	Medium-High	High	High	Medium	Medium

Multiple different solutions exist for electricity production through renewable sources. The most relevant one is hydroelectric, which is a mature technology with low GHG emission and very good performances. Its efficiency is very high, it guarantees good performances and the use of such a source in big plants, while providing a very low rate of GHG emission. The main drawback of such a technology is that it has almost no more margin for new plants installations, since plants have already been built in all the suitable natural spots. After hydroelectric, the most used and promising types of renewables are solar and wind energies, with the latter providing the lowest GHG emission level among all the power generation solutions.

The fast growth occurred to wind and solar in the last decade is well represented in the percentage of people in favour to those technologies, which are the highest among all sources, being solar at the first and wind at the second place. Wind and solar generation technologies, though, still need to improve their performances and costs, in order to become really competitive with traditional plants without the need of financial support and dedicated policies from European Countries.

Geothermal and bioenergies allow for the use in bigger plants as heat sources, both alone or together with fossil fuels, in order to reduce the GHG emission maintaining high performances and power generation levels. They are less supported by the community since they emit higher level of greenhouse gases than wind and solar. The main drawback of bioenergies are the deforestation issue and the fact that, even though GHG emissions resulting from burning biomass can be equilibrated by growing new plants, it can take from decades to a century to do that.

4.2 District heating

Eurostat data show that almost 50% of the total energy consumed in Europe is used for the generation of heat. Renewable energy already contributes to heat generation with an important share, with biomass accounting for 55% of all RES. When talking in particular about District Heating (DH), over 80% of heat supplied by DH originates from renewable energy sources or waste heat recovery from combined heat and power plants of industrial processes.

DH network are present through all Europe and currently cover around 10% of the total annual heat demand. However, market penetration of DH is unevenly distributed. While DH has an average market share of 10% in Europe, it is particularly widespread in North, Central and Eastern Europe, where temperature can reach much lower value during winter, with a market shares often around 50% and more (CrossBorder Bioenergy, 2012).

In Southern and Western regions, where District Heating is not widespread, each single building provides its own heating. This is generally produced using boilers, which are dimensioned depending on the specific building needs. This system makes use of around 75-85% of the energy contained in fossil fuel when new technologies are installed, which in many case does not happen, since it is difficult to convince people to face a big initial investment required to upgrade the boiler. Moreover, boilers use high-value energy such as heat at 1.200-1.500°C to provide indoor heating at around 20°C.

District heating, on the other side, make use of a single central or a few big plants that provide heat to multiple buildings. This allow for the contemporary production of heat and power, resulting in a great total efficiency improvement, since CHP plants do not disperse process heat in the environment, but make direct

use of it for building heating. Moreover, central heat production ensures better control on the heat plant, reducing maintenance costs, and allows for the use of energy sources such as Municipal Waste, that would be otherwise useless.

For those reasons, to promote the use of District Heating, in particular with heat supplied by renewables or waste heat recovery, is one of the targets of the EU RES-Directive for 2020.

Today, heat-only technologies and plants are the most common, while district cooling is less common, but is slowly increasing its popularity during the last decades. Combined Heat and Power has already gained the largest share among district heating solutions, even though they are traditionally fossil fuelled and many plants run obsolete technology. New solutions are slowly being introduced into the market, which make prevalently use of biomasses, i.e. bioCHP, pellets, biofuels or fuel mixes (CrossBorder Bioenergy, 2012).

In general, a stronger use of renewables is foreseen for DH, in particular of biomasses and municipal wastes, which allows similar performances as fossil fuels and the use in CHP plants, but strongly reduce the environmental impact and GHG emissions. Other eco-friendly solutions, such as solar heating, are also gaining more and more importance and, even though the presence of a back-up heat generation system is still required, they can provide great advantages, further reducing GHG emissions and energy dependency from fossil fuels.

4.2.1 Natural gas

The use of fossil fuel is dominant in heating generation as it is in electricity generation, with 70% of the total European heat power generated in 2013 coming from non-renewable sources. Natural gas is the most commonly used, with more than 40% of the total share (Eurostat, 2016).

When used for the sole purpose of heating generation, natural gas is burned in a heat-only boiler station, which generates thermal energy in the form of hot water for use in district heating applications. District heating systems have a typical heat generating capacity between 0.5 to 20 MW, with supply and return temperatures of 80°C/40°C. It is possible to reach higher supply temperatures, up to 120 °C or even higher, in pressurised systems (European Commission, 2012a).

Boilers for district heating are a mature technology and have been used for more than three decades. Nowadays, due to the flexibility of natural gas, most boilers are used to meet the heating demand during peak-load periods or as a back-up system to supply energy when required. The efficiencies are typically in the range of 97 – 105 %, based on net calorific values (European Commission, 2012b).

The advantage of using gas fired boilers for district heating, as we have already discussed for the electricity production, is that it can produce heat easily, with complete control on the amount of energy provided. For this reason, it is commonly used for backup capacity in district heating systems in which the main part of the heat comes from other sources such as wastes or biomass. The main disadvantage of the technology is that it is based on burning a fossil-based energy source, with the consequent emission of high level of greenhouse gasses in the air. As a consequence, EU is promoting the implementation of different cleaner types of technologies for heat production, reducing the use of natural gas only for backup capacity.

4.2.2 Combined heat and power (CHP)

Combined heat and power consists in the simultaneous production of usable heat and power (electricity), in one single, highly efficient process. In conventional ways of generating electricity, a vast amount of heat remains at the end of the electricity production cycle and it is simply wasted. This lost heat, often well visible as a cloud of steam rising from cooling towers, usually represents up to two thirds of the overall energy consumed by coal and gas fired power plants.

CHP, therefore, is an interesting solution since it efficiently uses the otherwise waste heat generated by electrical power plants, with a consequent reduction of final CO₂ emissions. By using waste heat, CHP plants can highly improve the overall plant efficiency, reaching ratings even higher than 80%. The improvement is clear if we consider that electrical and thermal total efficiency of gas power station range between 49% and 52%, while for coal-fired plant it is even lower, with an efficiency of around 38% (Rezaie, & Rosen, 2012: 4).

Figure 10: CHP compared with separated power and heat generation (Northern Utilities, 2015)

CHP is first of all an energy efficiency technology and can be applied to both renewable and fossil fuels. The specific technologies employed, and the final efficiencies achievable will vary from case to case, but in all cases CHP offers the capability to make more efficient and effective use of valuable primary energy resources.

When providing also cooling, together with power and heating, a CHP process is called 'trigeneration'. An important example of trigeneration applications in a major city is the New York City steam system.

Direct benefits of CHP include up to 30% energy and carbon dioxide reduction, high overall efficiency and cost savings around 30% over electricity sourced from the grid and heat generated by on-site boilers. It is also a mature and reliable technology widely used worldwide (VV. AA., 2015b: 31).

An important drawback of the technology, which is common to all district heating technologies, that heat is difficult to transport for long distances without having big losses. This means that CHP plants are an economically valuable solution when there is a high concentrated demand for heat close to the plant.

4.2.3 Solid biomass

Since ancient times, human beings have used wood to produce fire for heating, cooking and many other purposes. Nowadays, burning wood is still the easiest and most immediate way to produce heating. Among renewable energy sources, solid biomass has the highest share on the market in derived heat production, with 74.7% in 2013 (Eurostat, 2015).

The wood used in this technology can derive directly from chipped trees, from wood industry in the form of pellets and from industrial wastes. Pellets are a processed form of wood, which make them more expensive, but their cost is compensated by the fact that they are much more condensed and uniform, and therefore more efficient. In addition, they provide several advantages related to handling, shipping and storage, a large calorific value, an improved possibility of transporting the material for long distances and an easier implementation in automated lines.

As already seen in the previous chapter, biomass is a renewable energy, although limited in the amount of biomass available, and can be considered a CO_2 neutral source. The energy produced from biomass has a costs similar to other traditional energy sources such as natural gas, sometimes even lower, which makes it not only environmentally friendly, but also economically competitive.

A technology with potential for growth in the future is biomass gasification, which produces a wide range of fuel alternatives like methanol, synthetic natural gas (SNG) and Fischer–Tropsch diesel.

The advantage of the technology is that it can use waste products, it helps reducing the amount of CO_2 emitted in the air, even though there can be a minor use of fossil fuel for related operations such as wood transportation. In well-designed systems, efficiencies above 110 % are achievable.

The disadvantages include the high investment cost and the availability of the energy source, which is limited due to the annual growth rate of biomass. Even though biomass is considered a CO_2 neutral source, it may require many decades to equilibrate the amount of CO_2 introduced in the air. Another important issue is the negative impact harvesting has on forests and the relative ecosystem.

4.2.4 Waste

Using waste for district heating is an efficient way to address government policies aimed at reducing fossil fuel use for space heating and corresponding CO_2 emissions, using wastes coming primarily from industry and households. Waste fired plants are usually designed for incineration of non-hazardous wastes, even though in certain cases it is possible that some types of hazardous wastes may also be incinerated.

Three categories are defined to classify the types of waste (European Commission, 2012b):

- Industrial wastes: Wastes of industrial non-renewable origin combusted directly for the production of heat or electricity.
- Municipal solid waste (renewable sources): Waste produced by households, industry, hospitals and the tertiary sector, which contains biodegradable materials that are incinerated at specific installations.
- Municipal solid waste (non-renewable sources): They are the same as municipal solid waste, but contains non-biodegradable materials.

This system has various advantages. Waste fired plant allow to reach high temperatures, making it possible to have combined heat and power generation. Produced hot water can be used for industrial applications, while district heating operations are performed with lower temperature water. It uses waste as an energy source instead of using fossil fuels or other energy sources and, since a large part of the municipal solid waste is considered as renewable energy, it results in a reduction of CO₂ emissions. Incineration of waste residues can also be used for construction works.

The disadvantage are the high investment costs for the plant construction and operation, the extensive treatment needed to control the polluted flue gases and the fact that the source of energy, even if renewable, is limited to the amount of collected waste. Moreover, in order for the plant to work efficiently, there has to be a systematic collection of waste, which need to be sorted in order to remove non-inflammable waste such as glass and metal.

4.2.5 Geothermal

Heat from underground water reservoirs can be utilised directly through a heat exchanger and used in a district heating system. However, this solution is highly dependable on the presence of a natural geothermal source in the area and on the temperature it provides water. Generally, then, it is preferable and more economically convenient to extract heat from reservoirs located at higher levels, which have lower temperatures, and use that heat in heat pump systems to provide heating. The typical system for district heating is a closed-loop system, which transfers the heat to the district heating network through heat exchangers and/or heat pumps, and then reinjection the cooled water to the reservoir to be re-heated (GEODH, 2016).

The advantage of the system is its good performance and that it uses a natural energy source with no need for combustion, with consequent reduced CO₂ emissions. The disadvantages are the investment costs, the possibility of pollutants presence in the geothermal water and the limits to the availability of the energy source. The technique is, in fact, only applicable at the specific geographic locations where geothermal sources are present, since heat transportation is much less efficient than electricity one (European Commission, 2012b: 20).

4.2.6 Solar district heating

This type of technology is related to large installations, which are used for producing heat for district heating systems. Solar heating systems use solar collectors and a liquid handling unit to transfer heat to the load generally by using storage. As we have already discussed for solar electricity, since solar power is an intermittent source, this system requires additional heat generation capacity in order to meet all the heating needs of the community during periods of insufficient sunshine or during wintertime. This additional heat can be obtained by other backup energy source, which can be based on biofuels, waste, or fossil fuels as natural gas, oil or coal. Other possibility is the cogeneration with heat and power (CHP) or the use of heat pumps (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2016).

The solar collectors typically used are highly efficient flat plate collectors. Other systems such as the concentrating systems can generate higher temperatures and are most used in areas with a high level of direct solar irradiance for power generation or high-temperature applications. The efficiency is higher if the

temperature level of the district heating system is relatively low. Due to the climatic variations during the year, it is less cost effective to have 100% coverage of the heating demand than to have part load coverage. These systems are applicable wherever there are district heating networks, in order for the solar heating system to connect to it. Usually such networks exist in cold climates, where there is a substantial demand for heat during autumn and winter. Although it may be considered that using solar thermal energy in such climates would be neither feasible nor competitive, the reality proves the opposite to be true. The main disadvantages are its high investment cost and the need for a large area for the panel installation, since high quantity of heat are needed for district purposes (European Commission, 2012b: 12).

4.2.7 Heat pump for district heating

Heat pumps usually draw heat from the ambient and convert the heat to a higher temperature through a closed-loop process. We are going to discuss heat pumps in more details when talking about building heating in the End User chapter. This because heat pumps are a technology better suited for smaller installations than district heating due to the fact that it is harder to regulate and control. Even so, this technology still finds some application in district heating and several types of installations are available:

- **Large electrical heat pumps for district heating systems:** they absorb heat at ambient temperature or, if available, from waste process heat. Supply temperature is around 80 °C, with a typical capacity of 1 to 10 MW of generation heat. Depending on the working fluid, the COP (Coefficient of Performances) may vary, reaching values up to 4.5.
- **Large absorption heat pumps – biomass heat source:** They usually work in connection with municipal solid waste and biomass plants, but natural gas might also be used. They provide district heating temperature around 80 °C, with a typical capacity of 2 to 15 MW of heat generation. The COP is usually 1.7.
- **Large absorption heat pumps – geothermal heat source:** Geothermal water is used to heat water for a district heating system around 80 °C, with a typical capacity of 2 to 15 MW of heat generation. The COP is around 1.7.

The advantage of a heat pump system is that it uses free ambient energy or waste heat and transforms it to a higher temperature suitable for heating purposes. The disadvantage is the energy needed for the transformation (electricity or high-temperature heat), which may come from polluting sources, and the cost of the necessary equipment. The advantage of the electrically driven heat pumps compared to absorption heat pumps is a higher efficiency. However, when the heat needed to run the absorption heat pumps is available a lower cost, e.g. industrial waste heat, absorption heat pumps may be a favourable option (European Commission, 2012b: 14-17).

4.2.8 KPIs evaluation for district heating technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between district heating production technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. As already done for the electricity production technologies, a high level comparison is performed here, dividing the depending on the source. The proposed table helps understanding each technology group pros and cons. The main sources that inform Table 8, below, come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of Pöyry Energy Consulting (2009), VV. AA. (2015b).

Table 8: KPIs evaluation for district heating technologies

Theme	Type of indicator	Natural gas	CHP	Solid biomass	Waste	Geothermal	Solar thermal	Heat pump
GHG Emissions	<i>Life-cycle CO2 emissions (gCO2eq/kWh)</i>	469	30% reduction compared to only electric plant	20	40 (MSW) 200 (Non biodegradable wastes)	45	22	Indirect from electricity consumption
Environmental impact	<i>Main env. impact</i>	GHG Emissions	No addition w.r.t. electric plant	GHG Emissions	GHG Emissions	Release of pollutant	-	-
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	Medium-High	-	Low-Medium	Medium	Low-Medium	-	-
Capital investment cost	<i>Investment cost (€/MWh)</i>	130-155	115	155-185 250 (Anaerobic digestion)	260	65-200	100-130	110-130
Performance index	<i>Thermal efficiency</i>	97-105%	70-90% (Total electrical + thermal)	10-30% (traditional) 90% (pellet)	90%	15-30%	25-30%	COP = 1.7 (Absorption) COP = 4.5 (Electrical)
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan(years)</i>	40	40	25	15	20-30	25	15
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	High	High	High	Medium-High	High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Energy Roadmap 2050 2030 climate & energy framework (Each member state is free to take individual decisions on the measures to reach the set objectives)						
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance (% citizens in favour)</i>	Medium	Medium-High	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Medium-High

Natural gas is the most used energy source for district heating. Even if, as already said for the electricity generation, natural gas provides lower pollutant emissions than coal and oil, there are still more clean solutions to apply. Combined heat and power plant is the most effective solution, when there is the need for district heating close to a power plant. CHP highly improves power plants total efficiency, reducing the GHG emissions by 30%. It is also a simple and mature technology, which does not affect the plant lifespan.

The most used renewable source for heating is biomass, which can achieve very high efficiency thank to modern solutions such as the conversion of wood into highly compressed and dry pellets. The main drawback remain the time needed to equilibrate the GHG emitted with a new-grown plant.

Solar thermal provides a good solution as a complement to an already existing district heating grid. It has even lower life-cycle GHG emissions than photovoltaic and a relative low cost. The technology is not mature yet to compete with fossil fuels and provide a total heat base for district heating.

When geothermal sources are naturally present, this type of solution proves to be a very efficient choice, characterised by particularly low cost. Moreover, geothermal is more suited to heat purposes than power generation ones, since lower temperatures are needed in district heating than in power plants to generate the steam that moves the turbines.

5 Energy transportation and distribution

The second step of the energy supply chain is constituted by transportation. It aims to take an energy source from its extraction or production site, and move it through the big national or transnational infrastructures to centralised distribution facilities.

The distribution step covers a more capillary network of the supply infrastructure, taking the energy source to the end users (residential buildings, industries, services, *etc.*).

It is very important to technically evaluate these two phases of the energy supply chain, because the transportation and distribution aspects can have huge impacts on several crucial points of this industrial field. They can affect the final energy cost to the end user and landscape impacts can be caused by the transportation and distribution infrastructures, with subsequent social changes that are not economically computable (residential value decreasing, life quality worsening, *etc.*). Moreover, environmental impacts such as carbon emissions and other pollutants are worth evaluating, together with the risk of serious environmental accidents associated with the transportation and distribution of energy sources, like in the case of oil tanker vessels damages.

Transportation and distribution technologies can act on two different segments of the energy chain:

- primary energy sources like coal, oil, gas (*i.e.*, those which have not been transformed into any other energy form yet) are carried from a place to another and then distributed to their transformation sites and plants (*i.e.*, thermal power plants, residential buildings heating plants, public services buildings, *etc.*)
- already transformed energy (*e.g.*, electric high voltage) is transported and distributed to end users (houses, industries, *etc.*).

In this section, an overview of the main energy transportation and distribution technologies is presented. Then, the Key Performance Indicators defined in Chapter 3 are used in order to quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate each listed technology, with a comparative analysis of the energy transportation and distribution scenario.

5.1 Electricity

Electricity power is widely used in every social, working and production aspect of human life. It is produced in the form of a potential differential between two or more conductors, and under the same form it is transported and distributed from the power plant to the grid nodes and the peripheral end users' sites.

The present paragraph differentiates some technology which is used in this field.

5.1.1 3-phase Overhead Transmission

The 3-phase overhead transmission is the most used technology to face the problem of long distances to be covered when a certain amount of electrical energy has to be transported to the distributions sites. This technology is adopted with high voltage to be passed through the conductors, due to the long distances which could cause too high leakages in case of low voltage transmission (in fact, long conductors mean high resistances and subsequently high voltage drops).

When 3-phase overhead transmission is adopted, high voltage is conducted through a material which often is an aluminium alloy, which allows low weight (important aspect for overhead infrastructure installation) and low costs if compared to other conductors like copper. The conducting line is composed by metal strands which are mechanically reinforced by introduction of steel strands. The resistance is kept low by using very high conductor sections, up to 750 mm².

The main issue of such a technology is the landscape impact, together with the environment pollution due to its installation phase (components transportation, industrial machinery utilisation for assembly and mounting). Electric field created by the high differential potential is another impacting aspect of this technology. Moreover, bad weather conditions can affect the conduction performance (Betz *et al.*, 2009).

This kind of infrastructure is adopted for both the electricity transportation and distribution phases.

5.1.2 Bundle Conductors

Due to the so-called *skin effect*, electric current flows more close to the conductor surface rather than internally in the material bulk. This phenomenon is exploited by bundled conductors infrastructure, which are used in order to optimise the performance of high voltage electricity transportation (Grainger *et al.*, 1994).

The bundled conductors are multiple parallel cables often used instead of single cables for overhead transmission. This technology aims to reduce at minimum the energy losses due to corona discharge effect, by which the high potential voltage cable causes the surrounding air ionisation, as well as maximising the surface and capacity of the conductors, thus creating an electric arc, discharging a part of electric energy to the ground (Freimark, 2007).

5.1.3 3-phase Underground Transmission

This solution is adopted to face with electricity transportation and distribution problems. It is technically the same as the already seen overhead transmission, but it is installed after excavations underground. Differently from the overhead transmission, this kind of high voltage transportation is more stable (*i.e.*, it is not affected by weather conditions), and it does not need pylons. As a consequence, it can be installed in particular situations such as to cross short sea areas, making it a more flexible solution for energy transportation and distribution. Moreover, the huge landscape impact due to overhead installations is avoided by underground lines.

On the other hand, installation activities such as excavations and cables create higher costs than 3-phase overhead transmissions lines.

5.1.4 Voltage Transformers

The transport and distribution grid is characterised by several technical parameters that need to be taken into account in order to have good performances. Then, voltage transformers stations are needed to load the grid with the right voltage range.

In fact, the electric power is produced at the power plants between 2.3 kV and 30 kV, and it needs to be increased because the long distances of the transportation grid cause losses and voltage drops. So, the transformer's technology is used to take the voltage up to 115 kV / 765 kV AC before loading the grid with it.

5.1.5 Subtransmission

After crossing the transportation level of the power grid, electricity feeds distribution ramifications in order to gradually reach the most peripheral areas and respective end users.

Subtransmission is the part of power transmission working at medium and low voltages (VV.AA., 2011b). Substations are connected to high voltage transmission line, and transformers decrease the voltage for a shorter distance distribution. Smaller substations at town level are then connected to this medium voltage lines, where the voltage is stepped down again (Fink *et al.*, 2007).

Then, by means of voltage transformer station's technology, a complete transportation and distribution grid is managed.

5.1.6 Transmission Grid Exit

Finally, when the electric power has to exit the distribution grid in order to feed the single end users (buildings, industries, transport services, *etc.*), the voltage is once more taken down to a level which is nationally regulated and varies country by country (*e.g.*, 220 V- 50 Hz in Italy).

5.1.7 KPIs evaluation for electricity transmission technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the different analysed technologies for electricity transportation and distribution is proposed. The proposed KPIs and their values can give some clarifications about each technology strength and weakness towards a low carbon future.

The main sources that inform Table 9, below, come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of European Commission (2015) and EASAC (2009).

Table 9: KPIs evaluation for electricity T&D

Theme	Type of indicator	3-phase Overhead Transmission	Bundle Conductors	3-phase Underground Transmission	Subtransmission
Environmental impact	<i>Major impact type generated</i>	High landscape (visual) impact, high electromagnetic induced field	High landscape (visual) impact, high electromagnetic induced field (for overhead application)	CO ₂ emissions, yard logistic impacts, noise impact.	CO ₂ emissions, yard logistic impacts, noise impact (underground transmission in urban areas)
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of transported energy</i>	1.5 M€/km for installation	More expensive to install than normal overhead line	40 M€/km for installation	50 k€ - 1 M€/km for installation
Performance index	<i>Efficiency Energy carried/(energy carried + energy consumed + losses)</i>	0.94	0,96	0,96	0.94-0.96
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure Lifespan (years)</i>	80	80/40	40	40
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	Medium	High	High
Technology flexibility	<i>Possibility to reach different locations</i>	Medium	Medium	High	High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>	Integrated European grid development supported by EU			
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium, stable	High, stable	High, stable	High, stable

The main differences between the performance of the electricity transport and distribution technologies regard the environmental impact and cost aspects.

In particular, the 3-phase overhead transmission takes the biggest landscape impact, but this is not the most polluting technology: during the installation phase of an underground transmission line, indeed, the high CO₂ emissions due to the excavation machineries represent the main environmental impact. Moreover, the yard set up during this phase can cause logistic issues such as the transportation and disposal of excavated material.

The yard logistics, furthermore, cause the much higher costs of an underground line installation if compared to any other electricity transmission solution, as shown in Table 8. The corrosion action of the underground environment makes it have a shorter lifespan than overhead lines.

On the other hand, the main advantage of 3-phase underground transmission is the technology flexibility, being able to reach zones where an overhead installation would be impossible or very difficult to realise (*e.g.*, transmission through a sea).

From a policy point of view, the EU has designated €70 million to finance 9 innovative projects to improve electricity transmission grid, in order to create an integrated network at community level, to meet the increasing energy exchange needs.

5.2 Oil

Oil is a primary energy source largely adopted for transformation into electric energy in oil power plants, refinement into fuel for vehicle movement and direct burning in heating systems.

This energy source is extracted from soil and underwater deposits in limited areas, and it has to be transported through long distances in order to be available for end users (*i.e.*, refineries, industries, heating systems).

In this section, the most exploited technologies for oil transportation and distribution are listed.

5.2.1 Pipelines

Usually, the first segment of crude oil transportation starting from the extraction site is performed by mean of pipelines, which are constituted by tubes with a pressure differential that makes the fluid flow in a determined direction.

This solution is widely adopted in the oil transportation and, on a ton-mile basis, it has been estimated that 71% of crude oil is transported by this method.

The main advantages of pipelines are both economic and environmental: in fact, this technology requires significantly less energy to move a certain oil amount along a determined distance, if compared to other tools like trucks or vessels (Trench, 2001). Furthermore, it has a much lower carbon footprint on the environment. From a reliability point of view, pipelines have good performances too, due to the low risk of environmental damages and accidents.

The main disadvantage of this technology is its low flexibility, being a fix infrastructure able to move crude oil for long distances but only to determined areas reached by the line. Another drawback is represented by

the high installation costs (Karangwa, 2008), with the needing of big starting investments to build such a facility.

5.2.2 Pump Stations

The oil flow through the pipelines is assured by pump systems operating both before entering the pipeline, after having collected crude oil from field gathering systems, and along the pipeline itself. Here, booster pumps are located in order to maintain the right pressure (*i.e.*, up to 150 atm) and keep the oil flowing.

5.2.3 Tanker Ships

The problem of transporting crude oil through the oceans, from a continent to another, can only be faced by tanker vessels. This method allows to simultaneously carry many barrels of oil, making the transportation price per barrel very low if compared to land transport vehicles.

An alternative to the big, propelled tanker ships are barges, which are smaller and do not have any propulsion system; they are used to move crude oil in calm waters and for short distances, and are pushed or towed by tugs (PetroStrategies, 2015).

Obviously, the main drawback of this technology is represented by the flexibility, being able to carry oil only through the sea and rivers. It has to be used in combination with another technology when the oil is downloaded at the harbour.

Marine oil transportation with vessels has also the highest impact and damage potential in case of accident, with many barrels of oil which can pollute oceans if a tanker has leakages or sinks.

5.2.4 Tank Trucks

After long-distance transport phases, primary energy sources such as crude oil and its derivative fuels are distributed to the end users by tank trucks, which represent the most flexible technology to move them. In fact, tank trucks can potentially reach every place where there is a road, thus making it particularly suitable for retail distribution purposes.

The main disadvantages of using this kind of vehicle are the low storage capacity (only 80 or 100 barrels of oil for each truck) and the high costs and carbon footprint due to the trucks fuel consumption (PPIAF website, 2016).

5.2.5 Rails

Similar to the tank trucks distribution method, crude oil and its derivatives can be moved by using trains: this technology is generally has less of an impact compared to the previous one, and takes the advantage of the railway, an already existing infrastructure built for more general purposes. This makes rail technology more flexible than the pipelines, even if tank trucks system is the most flexible distribution method at all.

A single train (about 8,000 barrels) can carry quite a large amount of crude oil, which keeps distribution costs low (PPIAF, website, 2016).

5.2.6 KPIs evaluation for oil transmission technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the different analysed technologies for crude oil transportation and distribution is proposed. These KPIs can help in the characterisation of each technology under technical, economical and environmental aspects.

The main sources used to fill in Table 10 come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of Directorate general for Internal Policies (2009) and Kiefner & Rosenfeld (2012).

Table 10: KPIs evaluation for oil T&D

Theme	Type	Pipelines + pump stations	Tanker Ships	Tank Trucks	Rails
Environmental impact	<i>Major impact type generated</i>	Yard logistic and noise impact during installation, landscape impact	CO2 emissions, environmental disaster risks	CO2 emissions	Logistic issues
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of transported energy €/(barrel*km)</i>	0,002	0,00005 considering 2 Mbarrel ship	0,00325	0,008
Efficiency in transport and consumption	<i>Energy carried/(energy carried + energy consumed + losses)</i>	-	0,98 (considering 2 Mbarrel ship and 10000 km shipping)	0,96 (considering 2000 km driving)	0,99 (considering 2000 km transportation)
Infrastructure Lifespan	<i>years / infrastructure</i>	80	30	15	20
Maturity of technology	<i>years since emergence</i>	150	150	110	150
Technology flexibility	<i>Possibility to reach different locations</i>	Low	Low	High	Medium
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>		-	-	-
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium - decreasing	Low	Medium	Medium

As shown in the table above, all the presented oil transport and distribution technologies have a strong historical maturity, since all of them had to be studied and developed in the period of oil extraction and consumption increasing (1860s).

Oil pipelines, if compared to other solutions, have a higher impact in terms of landscape damages and yard logistics, and it has a very low, practically null, flexibility: it can take oil only where dedicated infrastructure

has been built. On the other hand, once built, this transport method has a much higher lifespan than other ones (if the pipeline is well maintained, otherwise the risk of accident greatly increases).

Every conveyance-based method is characterised by a high efficiency (railway distribution being the highest), due to the large number of barrels that can be carried.

Referring to the transportation and distribution costs, vessel shipping is the cheapest way to move the oil mass unit along a certain distance (because the shipping cost is distributed over a huge amount of oil, e.g., 2 million barrels). Pipelines also have quite a low cost too in terms of $\text{€}/(\text{barrel} \cdot \text{km})$; tank truck and rail have higher costs due to the limited capacity of these conveyances.

5.3 Gas

Another primary energy source is natural gas, which is extracted from the soil and has to be delivered to distribution facilities and end users.

It is mainly used in the heating systems for residential buildings and industrial sites, further than in electric power plants to produce electricity.

In the present section, different adopted technologies are shown in order to evaluate their peculiarities and their impacts.

5.3.1 Pipelines - Gathering System

Once the natural gas has been extracted from the wellhead, in order to transport it to processing facilities, small diameter (from 6 to 48 inches) carbon steel pipelines are used. This represents the safest method of gas transportation, and in order to reduce the risk of leakages when the pipe is put into the ground, it is covered with a specialised coating, whose purpose is to protect the pipe from the ground moisture, which could cause corrosion and rusting.

As mentioned for oil pipelines, this kind of infrastructure has the disadvantages of a low flexibility and high investment cost for its installation (Karangwa, 2008).

5.3.2 Pipelines - Interstate System

Interstate pipelines are conceptually the same technology as gathering pipelines, but in this case the infrastructure grids are larger and they are aimed at transporting natural gas through countries and their boundaries, in order to allow raw gas commerce.

Interstate pipelines include a great number of valves along their length, working like gateways; they are usually open and allow natural gas to flow freely, or they can be used to stop gas flow along a certain section of pipe.

5.3.3 Compressor Stations

Natural gas in the pipelines needs the right pressure level in order to correctly flow towards the gathering systems, processing units, distribution points and end users. In order to achieve this pressure, compressor stations are set up along the lines. These facilities are equipped with gas treatment units, air coolers, shut-off control valves, lubrication systems, fuel and impulse gas make-up units, and power supply.

Compressors technology is adopted for both gas transportation and distribution phases.

5.3.4 LNG Tankers

Further than what already mentioned for crude oil, ships can be used to transport natural gas. To exploit this technology, the gas is shrunk to 1/600 of its original volume, in order to transport a reasonable mass of gas on one ship. During the shrinking operation, the gas is liquefied and becomes Liquefied Natural Gas

(LNG), which can be stored in pressurised and refrigerated (the temperature of the gas is taken down to -162°C to liquefy it) tanks, and then transported on vessels (US Dept. of Energy, 2005).

As previously mentioned, the main drawback of ship transportation is the low flexibility and the need of other land transportation/distribution technologies in combination with it.

At the delivery point, the LNG is re-gasified into natural gas and added into a gas pipeline system.

5.3.5 Gas Hydrate Transportation

A possible future alternative to the previously mentioned natural gas transportation methods is being studied in this period: natural gas hydrates are indeed considered as a possibility for the storage and subsequently for the transportation of natural gas.

Several technologies are under research in order to find the best way to produce, ship and regasify such materials containing natural gas molecules.

At the moment, natural gas hydrates is less cost-effective than the LNG transportation method, due to the lower density of natural gas which can be stored in them. However, this solution could be economically viable for small capacity peak-shaving plants and natural gas storage due to the costs associated with natural gas hydrate synthesis, which are lower than the LNG production costs (HydraTech, 2016).

5.3.6 KPIs evaluation for gas transmission technologies

In Table 11 the main KPIs for a technical, economic and environmental comparison between the different analysed technologies for natural gas transportation and distribution is proposed. These figures can help assessing the various transportation modes.

The main sources used to fill in the table come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, with the addition of Kiefner & Rosenfeld (2012), INSEE (n.d.), Directorate-General for Internal Policies (2009), NaturalGas, (2016).

Table 11: KPIs evaluation for natural gas T&D

Themes	Type	Pipelines	LNG on ships	Gas Hydrate on ships
Environmental impact	<i>Major impact type generated</i>	Yard logistic and noise impact during installation, landscape impact	CO2 emissions	CO2 emissions
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of transported energy €/ (m³*km)</i>	0,00003 €/ (m ³ *km)	115*10 ⁻⁹ €/ (m3/km)	Worse than LNG, because 1 m ³ of gas hydrate contains 150 m ³ natural gas
Performance index	<i>Efficiency (Energy carried/(energy carried + energy consumed + losses))</i>	0,95	0,998 (considering 10000 km shipping)	
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure Lifespan (years)</i>	80	30	30

Themes	Type	Pipelines	LNG on ships	Gas Hydrate on ships
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	Low
Technology flexibility	<i>Possibility to reach different locations</i>	Low	Low	Low
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>		Baltic Energy Market Interconnection Plan, with construction of a LNG terminal serving Baltic countries and Finland	HYDRATECH EU project
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium, stable	Medium, stable	-

In Table 11 the traditional pipeline transport technology is compared to techniques of carrying natural gas after a physical status change. These techniques (LNG and hydrates) are considered with marine vessel transportation, in order to have a comparison between their general costs and efficiencies. The same considerations are still valid for the land distribution methods (trucks and trains), since costs and energy consumption are strictly related to the adopted technology.

Liquefied Natural Gas is the cheapest long distance transport technique of all, because of the very high volume ratio between natural gas and LNG transported (600/1). This extreme shrinkage allows a single vessel to carry a huge amount of natural gas that can be regasified (up to 3 x 10⁹ m³), with a subsequent low price and low energy consumption for each cubic metre of natural gas. This energy density is better in the case of natural gas hydrates on a vessel, as each cubic meter of material contains up to 150 m³ of natural gas.

Pipelines infrastructures are characterised by higher transportation costs, but they have a more stable technological maturity and a longer lifespan. Moreover, they have a lower CO₂ footprint as compared to the other two presented technologies (their main impacts, indeed, are represented by landscape and logistic issues). The EU Commission is pushing R&D activities on innovative gas transport and distribution methods with programs like BEMIP and HYDRATECH project.

5.4 Coal

This section is dedicated to coal, another primary energy source widely used in electricity production.

Since the distance between the supply point and the demand point is often long, coal transportation technologies face costs which are often higher than mining costs themselves, and environmental impacts including air pollution, solid wastes, noise levels, safety and traffic hazards. Direct environmental impacts can occur at the mine, where the coal is being transferred, transported or loaded. Indirect impacts from coal transportation largely result from the combustion of fuel for the transportation itself.

Several technologies are used for its transportation from the mining sites to the distribution facilities and power plants, where it is burned to convert the combustion heat into electric power.

5.4.1 Railroad Trains

Both for transportation and distribution purposes, railway infrastructures are used within the coal supply chain. Coal can be moved from the extraction site to a distribution place, or to the end user (*i.e.*, power plant) by a general freight train or a dedicated train. The main differences between these two solutions lie in the flexibility and in the transportation costs: a dedicated coal train only handles coal from a single origin to a single destination so that it is much faster and cheaper than the general train, which is a more flexible way to use this kind of technology.

General purpose freight trains typically handle from 1,500 to 6,000 net tons, with an average of about 3,000 net tons. In contrast, dedicated trains can carry 7,500 to 12,500 net tons per trip (McKetta, n.d.).

5.4.2 Coal Pipelines

As well as for transporting oil and gas, pipeline technology can be used to transport and distribute coal too. In particular, two different methods are suitable for moving coal from where it is mined to where it is consumed: coal slurry and coal log.

In the case of coal slurry pipeline transportation, a slurry of mixed water and pulverised coal is pumped into the line, having a mixing ratio of 1 to 1 by weight (OTA 1978). After the transportation through long distances, the slurry needs to be well dried, otherwise its electricity generation potential will be lower.

Coal log pipelines use coal that has been compressed into logs with a diameter 5 to 10% smaller than the pipeline diameter, and a length about twice the pipeline diameter. Also in this case water is used in order to move the coal, and the coal/water ratio is 3 or 4 to 1 (Marrero). Due to the tight coal compression into logs, it does not absorb much water, so this technology does not need the same drying procedure as coal slurry.

Coal pipelines can be used where infrastructure such as railways or marine transportation are not present, without having a great flexibility from a point of view of reachable places.

5.4.3 Barges Transport

Marine coal transportation is a solution to move coal worldwide, from a continent to another one. In this case, coal is usually moved in open barges having capacity ranging from 1,000 to 3,000 net tons, with an average of 1,500 net tons (McKetta, n.d.). 10–14 barges are normally located in series, so the main advantage of this kind of transportation is the large amount of coal that can be moved with a single shipping since a typical shipment can contain up to 30,000 net tons of coal (McKetta, n.d.).

Terminal facilities for coal transport are involved with either the loading or unloading of barges, with loading capacities for coal ranging from 1,000 to 4,000 tons per hour. Unloading of coal can take place by bucket, or revolving scoop, with subsequent conveyor movement to storage silos, loading facilities, or end-use points.

5.4.4 Highway Truck Movement

The most versatile method of coal transportation and distribution is represented by roads, on which vehicles like truck, having capacities between 15 and 30 tons, can carry this primary energy source almost all over the world. On the other hand, the logistic solution is affected by the relatively low capacity of a single truck, when compared to other technologies like barge transportation or coal pipelines (McKetta, n.d).

Other issues like the high carbon footprint, fuel consumption and consequent high transportation costs have to be taken into consideration, together with the damages and accident risk during carrying.

5.4.5 Conveyor Belt Transport

Some coal power plants are directly located close to the mining sites, which facilitates the logistical problem of raw material transportation from the mining area to the storage and end-user facilities. In such cases, if hilly terrain makes roads unsuitable for this purpose, conveyor belts are installed.

The main advantage of adopting this technology is the reliability (conveyor belts are almost maintenance free). However, installing such a machinery does not represent a flexible solution, carrying coal only from one location to another one (Vogel & Roberts, 1979).

5.4.6 KPIs evaluation for coal distribution technologies

In, the table below, the main KPIs for a comparative assessment between the analysed technologies for coal transportation and distribution is proposed. These KPIs can help characterising the various transportation modes.

The main sources used to complete Table 12 come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section.

Table 12: KPIs evaluation for coal T&D

<i>KPI</i>	<i>Type</i>	Coal Slurry Pipelines	Coal Log Pipelines	Railroad Trains	Barges	Trucks	Conveyor Belts
Environmental impact	<i>Major impact type generated</i>	Yard impact during installation, landscape impact, high water demand	Yard impact during installation, landscape impact, water demand	Logistic issues, electricity demand	GHG emissions	GHG emissions	-
Capital investment cost	<i>Cost of transported energy €/ (ton*km)</i>	0,4	0,2	0,007	0,005	0,09	0,015
Performance index	<i>Efficiency (Energy carried/(carried + consumed + losses))</i>	0,98 (considering 2000 km transportation)	0,99 (considering 2000 km)	0.99 (considering 2000 km)	0,84 (considering 10000 km)	0,83 (considering 2000 km)	0,97 (considering 1 km)
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure Lifespan (years)</i>	30		20	30	15	5
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	Medium-High	Medium	High	High	High	High
Technology flexibility	<i>Possibility to reach different locations</i>	Low		Medium	Low	High	Low
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy Support</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
National public support & Public support monitoring	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Low- Medium / decreasing					

As shown in Table 12, coal pipelines have higher costs compared to other more traditional coal transportation methods. These high costs are due to the complex crushing and dewatering operations that are performed before and after the transportation respectively, which have to be added infrastructure (pumping stations and pipelines) installation costs. Their main advantage is the possibility to be used where other infrastructures are not possible or too expensive to be built.

On the other hand, transportation costs are lower when they are distributed over a large amount of coal. As a barge can carry up to 30,000 tons in a single shipping, this makes it the cheapest way to transport this primary energy source. However, these low costs come with the very low flexibility of this technology, needing infrastructure like harbours, loading and downloading facilities, *etc.* Land transportation methods like trucks or railways are certainly more flexible.

Fuel-based technologies (*i.e.*, barges and trucks) are characterised by the lowest efficiencies because of the high consumption for the amount of coal carried in a single journey. Moreover, from an environmental point of view, they have the highest carbon footprint.

Slurry and log pipeline methods are quite innovative from a technology maturity point of view.

6 Energy storage

Energy storage involves the capture of the energy produced at one time to be used at a later moment. To make this possible, the energy captured needs to be converted from forms that might be difficult to store to more storable forms.

The conversion is done with various types of technology, which can provide a different range of storages, from long to short term. Storage is used at times when consumption, that cannot be deferred or delayed, exceeds production. In this way, electricity production does not need to be drastically scaled up and down to meet momentary consumption but instead, transmission from a combination of generators and storage facilities is maintained at a more constant level.

To meet the needs of the population, which is being progressively sensitised to the issues around energy consumption, a large number of manufacturers launched rechargeable battery systems for storing energy, generally to hold surplus energy from home solar/wind generation plants, that could be integrated into the traditional system in order to allow home users to store, monitor and manage electricity.

Grid energy storage (also called large-scale energy storage) can be defined as a group of methods and systems used to store electrical energy within an electrical power grid. A smart grid communication infrastructure that enables Demand Response (DR), can be used, alternatively and complementary, to achieve the same effect: in fact, both these technologies shift energy usage and transmission of power on the grid from one time (in which it is not useful and it would be wasted) to another (in which it's required).

The purpose of any electrical power grid is to balance energy production to energy consumption, by following and being flexible to their variation over time. Any combination of energy storage and demand response has its advantages. Some examples can be found below:

- electricity generated by intermittent sources can be stored and used later, otherwise it would have to be transmitted for sale elsewhere, or simply wasted

- fuel-based power plants, such as coal, gas, oil, can be more efficiently and easily operated at constant production levels
- transmission capacity or peak generating can be reduced by the total potential of all storage plus deferrable loads saving expense of this capacity
- Reducing the variance in the energy production needs reduces the production costs, resulting in a more stable pricing for the costumers and a higher income for the utilities
- In case of emergency, vital needs (such as electricity in an hospital) can be met reliably even with no transmission or generation going on

Energy storage is particularly important in an energy system dominated by renewable sources, such as the one EU is aiming at. Energy produced from photovoltaic and wind sources inherently varies: the amount of electrical energy produced varies according with time, season, day of the week, and weather. Therefore, renewables present special challenges to electric utilities. While hooking up many wind sources can reduce the variability, actually solar is considered a reliable source but is not available at night and tidal power shifts with the moon therefore is never reliably available on peak demand.

In an electrical power grid without energy storage, energy sources that rely on energy stored within fuels (coal, gas, oil, nuclear) must be scaled up and down to match the rise and fall of energy production from intermittent energy sources. While coal and nuclear plants take considerable time to respond to load, oil and gas plants can be scaled up when wind intensity dies down quickly. Utilities with less gas or oil power generation are, for this reason, more reliant on demand management and grid storage.

Energy storage systems may bring benefits on a small or large scale:

- Commercial consumers connect storage with renewables or demand response.
- Residential consumers match storage with PV installations in order to collect maximum benefit from solar systems.
- Utilities usually use storage as reserve capacity not only to hold peak loads but also to improve grid resilience.

Despite the fact that basic technologies have been around for years, energy storage is still a difficult problem to solve. In recent years, though, there have been many improvements in terms of cost, effectiveness and safety that makes it possible to hope for a speed up in future implementation towards a DG system.

6.1 Electricity

Energy storage solutions can be deployed in different applications. In terms of the technologies themselves, some of them can be used across a range of applications, while others are uniquely appropriate to specific applications. A key factor to success is to increase the market presence of energy storage technologies, which will result in capacity matching the application of the technology in the best way possible, especially in terms of effectiveness and economy.

6.1.1 Pumped-storage hydroelectricity

The electric power systems for load balancing use a type of storage named Pumped-Storage Hydroelectricity (PSH, or PHES). The method accumulates energy using the gravitational potential energy of

water, pumped from a lower elevation reservoir to a higher elevation. In order to run the pumps a low-cost off-peak electric power source is used. The stored water is released through turbines to produce electric power during periods of high electrical demand. Despite the losses the pumping process makes in terms of net consumption of energy overall, the system is able to increase revenue by selling more electricity during periods of peak demand, when electricity prices are more expensive.

Electricity must be used as it is being generated, or converted instantly into another form of energy such as kinetic, potential or chemical. The use of pumped-storage hydroelectricity represents a traditional way of storing energy on a large scale. Some areas of the world such as Norway, Wales in the United Kingdom, as well as Washington and Oregon in the United States, have used the topography there to store large quantities of water in elevated reservoirs, using excess electricity during periods of low demand to pump water up into their reservoirs. The facilities then release the water which passes across turbine generators and converts the stored potential energy back to electricity during electrical demand peaks.

The world's largest pumped hydro plant has a capacity of 2,862 MW (VV. AA., 2012b: 31), which is a proof that pumped hydro plants have a huge potential in terms of energy and power capacity; they can accommodate energy spikes associated with generation from intermittent renewable energy sources. Pumped hydro presents several advantages: a cycle efficiency of approximately 75%, a long lifespan, and no life cycle limitations, given a continuous supply of water. Another significant advantage to consider is the fact that enhancing an existing project can result in large savings on capital expenditures and at the same time reduce environmental and planning issues (VV. AA., 2012b).

6.1.2 Compressed air energy storage (CAES)

(CAES) is a process to store energy generated at one time in order to be used in another moment using compressed air. CAES plants are largely equivalent to pumped-hydro power plants in terms of their applications, output and storage capacity.

The technology stores low-cost off-peak energy, in the form of compressed air in an underground reservoir. The air is then released during peak load hours and heated with the exhaust heat of a standard combustion turbine.

This heated air is converted to energy through expansion turbines in order to produce electricity.

One of most important characteristics of CAES is the fact that has a high-energy storage potential; nearly all CAES facilities are at least 100 MW in size (VV. AA., 2012b: 37); the use of existing geological structures for storage reduces environmental impacts and footprints of CAES facilities.

On the other side, CAES requires a suitable site that must fulfil specific underground geological characteristics (very large subterranean caverns of suitable geologic strata, ancient salt mines, or underground natural gas storage, *etc.*) and, taking in consideration economies of scale and the costs of facilities, underground caverns have to be quite large in order to make CAES cost effective (EEG, 2012).

6.1.3 Flywheel energy storage

A flywheel energy storage (FES) is a chemical-free mechanical battery that harnesses the energy of a rapidly spinning wheel and stores it as rotational energy. The energy is converted back by decelerating the

flywheel. The flywheel system itself is a kinetic, or mechanical battery, spinning at very high speeds to store energy that is immediately available when needed.

Being a completely mechanical system, flywheels are not affected by temperature changes, nor do they suffer from memory effect. They cause potentially less damages to the environment, because they are made of largely inert or benign materials. Another advantage of flywheels is that it is possible to know the exact amount of energy stored by a simple measurement of the rotation speed.

Flywheels are considered a green technology, having practically no environmental impacts due to the benign materials that they are constructed of and also due to their rather compact design.

Other advantages are represented by the fact that Flywheels does not require a temperature controlled environment and need little maintenance (Devitt, D., 2010; VV. AA., 2012b; Calnetix Technologies Llc., 2016).

6.1.4 Gravitational potential energy storage with solid masses

This technology uses the movement of solid masses from lower to high elevations. Solid masses to be considered are: hopper rail cars filled with plain earth driven by electric locomotives.

Energy is used to raise a mass through a height thus storing energy as gravitational potential energy. The amount of energy stored is mass times gravitational acceleration times height raised.

Pumped hydro storage is the more frequently large scale use of gravity storage in current use. The idea is that we can pump a mass of water up from a low reservoir to a high reservoir, and later retrieve this energy through a process where water flows down and leads a water turbine that drives a generator producing electricity. The round-trip storage requests modest costs.

The main problem with gravitational storage is that it is incredibly weak compared to chemical, compressed air, or flywheel techniques. Gravitational storage lacks in energy density but in terms of volume presents advantages since lakes of water behind dams represent substantial storage (StratoSolar, 2016).

6.1.5 Battery energy storage

Power grids at present are characterised by a high share of renewable energy sources and this will be the same in the future. This process drives to a massive fluctuant power injection, that has the necessity to be balanced by battery energy storage.

Battery energy storage solutions are designed specifically for facilitating the transition to new ways of generating and distributing electricity. A BES system consists of electrochemical cells connected in series or parallel, that from an electrochemical reaction are able to produce electricity with the desired voltage. Each cell contains two electrodes with an electrolyte that can be at liquid, solid or ropy/viscous states. A cell can convert energy bi-directionally between electrical and chemical energy (AEG Power solutions, 2016).

6.1.6 Flow Battery Energy Storage

A flow battery stores energy in two soluble redox couples contained in external liquid electrolyte tanks. This electrolyte can be pumped from the tanks to the cell stack, which consists of two electrolyte flow

compartments separated by a membrane. The operation consists basically of reduction-oxidation reactions of the electrolyte solutions. During the charging phase, one electrolyte is oxidised at the anode while another electrolyte is reduced at the cathode, and at the same time the electrical energy is converted to the electrolyte chemical energy. During the discharging phase the process is reversed.

This technology is similar to both a fuel cell and a battery – where liquid energy sources are able to be recharged within the same system, as well as to create electricity.

Flow batteries can be almost immediately recharged when the electrolyte liquid is replaced, while at the same time recovering the material consumed for re-energisation.

Redox, hybrid and membraneless represent different classes of flow cells that have been developed. The main difference between conventional batteries and flow cells is that energy is stored as the electrode material in conventional batteries but as the electrolyte in flow cells (Energy Storage Association, 2016).

6.1.7 Capacitor and supercapacitor

A capacitor is composed of at least two electrical conductors (normally made of metal foils) separated by a thin layer of insulator that can be made of glass, ceramics or a plastic film. In ordinary capacitors, electrons are moved from one electrode and deposited on the other and the charge is separated by a solid.

Compared to conventional batteries, capacitors have shorter charging times and a higher power density. In terms of storing small quantities of electrical energy, capacitors are the most appropriate as well as for conducting varying voltage outputs.

Supercapacitors (also called an Electric double-layer capacitor) or Ultracapacitors are a type of high power high energy density capacitor. In Supercapacitors instead of a solid dielectric, the two electrodes are separated by a liquid electrolyte rich in ions. Electrical energy is stored in supercapacitors through two storage principles: the distribution of the two types of capacitance depends on the structure and material of the electrodes; as well as the static double-layer capacitance and electrochemical pseudocapacitance (Quora, 2016). Supercapacitors can have both the characteristics of electrochemical batteries and traditional capacitors thank to their structures.

There are three types of supercapacitors based on storage principle:

- Double-layer capacitors (EDLCs) – with activated carbon electrodes or derivatives with much higher electrostatic double-layer capacitance than electrochemical pseudocapacitance (Jayalakshmi, M. and Balasubramanian, K., 2008)
- Pseudocapacitors – with transition metal oxide or conducting polymer electrodes with a high electrochemical pseudocapacitance
- Hybrid capacitors – with asymmetric electrodes, one of which exhibits mostly electrostatic and the other mostly electrochemical capacitance, such as lithium-ion capacitors

Supercapacitors demonstrate a much longer lifetime than batteries. In fact the energy density of supercapacitors is generally on an order of magnitude less than that of conventional batteries, but the power density is generally 1-2 orders of magnitude greater. Since supercapacitors do not rely on chemical

changes in the electrodes (except for those with polymer electrodes) lifetimes depend predominantly on the rate of evaporation of the liquid electrolyte (Quora, 2016).

6.1.8 Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage

Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES) is a method of energy storage based on the fact that a current will continue to flow in a superconductor even after the voltage across it has been removed.

The SMES system stores electrical energy in the magnetic field generated by the direct current (DC) in the superconducting coil, cryogenically cooled to a temperature below its superconducting critical temperature, in order to have negligible resistance. In general, when current passes through a coil, the electrical energy will be dissipated as heat due to the resistance of the wire; however, zero resistance may occur if the coil is made from a superconducting material, under its superconducting state (usually at very low temperature) consequently the electrical energy can be stored with practically no losses.

Due to its very high cycling capacity and high efficiency over short time periods SMES is very well suited to high power short duration applications.

The biggest problem with SMES at present is the fact that the cooling units require very high capital costs (SuperPower, 2016).

6.1.9 Solar fuels

Solar energy is the world's most plentiful energy source, and researchers around the world are pursuing ways to convert sunlight into a useful form.

Turning sunlight into liquid fuels represents another element of solar research, because most people are basically aware of solar panels that produce hot water and solar photovoltaics that generate electricity.

A number of fuels can be produced from solar energy, such as solar hydrogen, carbon-based fuels and solar chemical heat pipe. These fuels can be stored and afterwards provide the basis for later electricity generation. Solar energy is captured and then stored in chemical bonds, in natural and artificial photosynthesis. The thermochemical approach uses thermal processes for solar fuels production. The solar fuel technology at the moment is still at the development stage (IFL Science, 2015).

6.1.10 Hydrogen storage and fuel cell

Hydrogen energy storage systems use two different processes for storing energy and producing electricity.

A common way to produce hydrogen is by using a water electrolysis unit which can then be stored in high pressure containers and/or transmitted by pipelines for later use.

Hydrogen storage is a key enabling technology in the advancement of hydrogen and fuel cell technologies in applications such as portable power, stationary power and transportation. Hydrogen has the highest energy per mass of any fuel; however, require the development of advanced storage methods that have potential for higher energy density because its low ambient temperature density results in a low energy per unit volume.

High density hydrogen storage is a significant challenge not only for transportation applications but also for stationary and portable applications. Currently available storage options typically require large-volume system that store hydrogen in gaseous form. Nowadays hydrogen EES with cell technology in the development and demonstration phase (Energy.Gov, 2016).

6.1.11 Cryogenic energy storage (CES)

CES is a process that comprehends the use of low temperatures (cryogenic) liquids such as liquid nitrogen or liquid air as energy storage. Usually at night when the costs are lower, electricity is used to cool air from the atmosphere to -195°C, which is the point where it liquefies. The liquid air can be kept for a long time at atmospheric pressure in a large vacuum flask. The liquid air is pumped at high pressure into a heat exchanger, that acts as a boiler, during periods when the request of electricity is higher (Highview Power, 2016).

In the process to heat the liquid and turn it back into a gas hot water is used from an industrial heat source, or from atmospheric air at an ambient temperature. This results in a significant increase in volume and pressure that is used to drive a turbine to generate electricity.

Cryogenic energy storage offers the following benefits:

- it uses proven technology that’s been around for years
- the regulations already exist
- tanks are less costly due to the fact that Storage is at low pressure; and
- the air it’s non-toxic and doesn’t explode and liquid air has four times the energy density of compressed air.

6.1.12 KPIs evaluation for electricity storage

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the electricity storage technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. Due to the various nature and level of maturity of the technologies considered, some indicators are evaluated through qualitative measurements, in order to provide a clear and simple view of parameters otherwise quite different through the technologies.

Information in the table below come in the main from the following sources; AEG Power Solutions (2016), Energy.Gov (2016), Energy Storage Association (2016), Highview Power (2016) and VV. AA. (2012b).

Table 13: KPIs evaluation for electricity storage

Theme	Type of indicator	Pumped-storage hydroelectricity	Compressed air energy storage	Flywheel energy storage	Hydrogen storage and fuel cell
GHG Emissions	<i>Life-cycle GHG emissions (gCO2eq/MWh)</i>	15.7	17.2	-	-
Environmental impact	<i>Main environmental impact</i>	Special site required. Land destruction to	Special site required. Some NOx	None	Impacts of mining and manufacturing catalyst

Theme	Type of indicator	Pumped-storage hydroelectricity	Compressed air energy storage	Flywheel energy storage	Hydrogen storage and fuel cell
		create reservoir.	emissions can occur.		
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	Medium-High	Medium	-	Medium
Capital investment cost	<i>Energy-related cost (€/kWh)</i>	75	5	1600	15
Performance index	<i>Efficiency</i>	55-85%	40-70%	90-95%	20-40%
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan (years)</i>	30	30	20	6
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	Medium	High	Low
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Electricity Directive 2009/72/EC does not mention storage issue, several Member States give their Transmission System Operators the management of electricity storage.			
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance and success of the technology</i>	High	Medium	Low	-

As the above table suggests, heat storage technologies appear to have a relatively low impact on the environment. The main difference between the proposed technology groups are in terms of the capital costs involved: sensible heat storage methods are largely the cheapest, whilst PCM and thermo-chemical storage require higher expenses for tools purchasing and installation.

Technical performances are generally high for these technologies, with the highest values demonstrated in the thermo-chemical storage methods, with efficiency rating recorded up to 100%.

Anyway, despite the good performances and “green” aspect of these processes, they are not at full technological maturity and therefore do not allow them to reach large market shares. Also, public opinion is not completely accepting, or even aware of these technologies yet.

6.2 Oil

Since oil is a liquid, its storage does not present as much difficulties as the other three categories considered in this chapter, such as electricity, gas and heat. Nevertheless, oil storage needs to be performed with care in order to avoid environmental contamination and oil loss. For this reason, only a brief overview on storage tanks is given in the following section.

6.2.1 Storage tanks

Storage tanks are important for many industries and may assume different sizes and shapes. The vertical, cylindrical storage tank shape is the most common used. In fact, large tanks tend to be vertical cylindrical. Some special applications may require tanks to be rectangular, in the form of horizontal cylinders, or even spherical in shape. Horizontal tanks can be used above and below ground, and are generally small storage tanks. In most cases Horizontal cylinders and spheres are used for full pressure storage of chemical products or hydrocarbon.

The type of products produced in refineries all over the world have changed significantly. The storage tank industry had to face new challenges in order to adapt to these changes, especially in terms of the physical and chemical properties of products themselves. The petroleum industry continues to give great importance to environmental and safety requirements in the process of design and selection of storage tanks.

An atmospheric storage tank (AST) is a container for holding a liquid at atmospheric pressure. There are different types of AST in use: top tanks (OTT), fixed-roof tanks (FRT), external floating-roof tanks (EFRT), or internal floating-roof tanks (IFRT). Depending on the characteristics of the product, a closed floating-roof tank (CFRT) may also be put into use (PetroWiki, 2013).

6.3 Gas

Natural gas has always been considered a seasonal fuel since its demand changes according to the changing weather patterns throughout the year. The need for heat in both residential and commercial settings during winter months necessitates a higher demand of natural gas compared to summer months.

The storage of natural gas is crucial since excess gas supply built up during the summer period may be available to satisfy the consumer needs during winter time. Basically in order to respond this load variations, the Gas is injected into storage tanks during periods where the demand is lower and then withdrawn to meet periods of peak request. This method is very important for maintaining a contractual balance.

In order to maintain the volume delivered and withdrawn from the pipeline system, shippers use stored gas. Otherwise, they would risk substantial penalties in cases of imbalance situations.

Natural gas storage plays a crucial role in maintaining the reliability of supply and smoothing out industry responses to changing consumer demand. Nowadays natural gas storage is also used for commercial reasons by industry participants since they are storing gas when prices are low, and withdrawing and selling it when prices are high.

6.3.1 Depleted gas reservoir

This is the form of underground storage that is most frequently used. It is also the cheapest, easiest to develop, operate and maintain of the three types of underground storage. Depleted reservoirs are the formations that have produced all their recoverable natural gas and have an underground formation with certain geological characteristics already known that allow the process of holding natural gas. The possibility to use a reservoir for storage allows for the industry to take advantage of the extraction and distribution equipment that are left on the gas field during the phase of production. This will be important to reduce start-up costs in the conversion process of a depleted reservoir into a storage facility (NaturalGas, 2016).

6.3.2 Aquifer reservoir

Aquifers are rock formations that act as natural water reservoirs characterised porous and permeable topographies of the landscapes in which they occur. In some specific cases they may be used for natural gas storage. Aquifers are the most expensive type of underground storage due to the fact that the geological features are not known in advance, which implies a significant investment of time and resources. Other costs

need to be expended to determine the aquifer's suitability for natural gas storage. In the case where the aquifer proves to be suitable all the associated infrastructure must be implemented, including the installation of wells, extraction equipment, pipelines, dehydration facilities, and possibly compression equipment.

In some cases, Aquifers development may require twice the amount of time needed in comparison to depleted reservoirs for suitable storage facilities. Environmental rules and restrictions should also be taking into consideration increasing time and costs. Environmental rules and restrictions should also be taking in consideration increasing time and costs (EIA, 2016b; NaturalGas, 2016).

6.3.3 Salt formation

Underground salt formations are basically applicable to natural gas storage since salt caverns, once formed, allow only a small quantity of injected natural gas to escape from the formation, unless it is specifically extracted. This option for natural gas storage is very resilient to reservoir degradation due to the fact that the properties of the walls are consistent with steel and consequently impervious to gas. Usually salt caverns are formed out of salt deposits that already exist. A cavern is developed within the formation as soon as it is considered appropriate for development as a gas storage facility. This consists of using water to dissolve and pull out a certain quantity of salt from the deposit leaving a large empty space in the formation. This process also involves drilling a well into the formation and cycling large quantities of water through the completed well. The water, now saline, is then pumped back to the surface. This process, called "salt caver leaching", can be quite expensive but offers the following advantages: salt caverns provides a natural gas storage vessel with high deliverability and when compared with other storage types cushion gas requirements are quite low, approximately 33% of total gas capacity (NaturalGas, 2016).

6.3.4 LNG storage tanks

With regards to the storage of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) the type of storage used is LNG storage tanks, which can store LNG at the significantly low temperatures of -162°C (-260°F). They may be placed underground, above ground or in LNG carriers. LNG is basically natural gas cooled to a liquid state. Natural gas condenses to a liquid when it is cooled to a temperature of -256°F at atmospheric pressure (UH IELE, 2016). A very clean product results with oxygen, carbon dioxide, sulfur compounds and water being removed as the natural gas is cooled to a liquid state during the liquefaction process. Liquefied natural gas has several advantages: it allows for the reduction of its volume by about 600 to 1, making it possible to transport natural gas by tanker. Also, re-gasification and delivery to markets became possible after the ability to store imported LNG and domestic production became possible (US Dept. of Energy, 2005). The amount of costs involved are usually high since it's necessary to construct facilities for the process of liquefaction, to purchase specific LNG ships and to build re-gasification facilities.

6.3.5 Pipe line capacity

A process called line packing allows gas to be temporarily stored in the pipeline system. The concept involves a process whereby there is an increase in the pressure to pack more gas into the pipeline. In periods when the demand is more intensive, higher quantities of gas can be withdrawn from the pipeline in the market area to conform with the quantity injected at the production area. The line packing process is important to respond to the time period after demand peaks and during off-peak periods. We are talking about a short-term substitute for a limited period of time for traditional underground storage (EIA, 2016b).

6.3.6 Gas holders

A gas holder is a container of large dimensions, sometimes known as gasometer, that stores large volumes of gas usually from nearby gasworks. The volume of the container is closely related the quantity of stored gas. The gas holders may store up to two million cubic feet of gas, just to conceptualise this that is enough to supply 2,400 homes for a full day. Due to developments in gas pipe technology gas holders are no longer

needed and now tend to be used mostly for balancing purposes rather than for storing gas for later use (The Telegraph, 2016).

6.3.7 Lined Rock Cavern

Lined Rock Cavern (LRC) gas-storage is an innovative technology that has been under development in Sweden since 1987. The evolution path passed through several phases such as technical studies, laboratory testing and field tests. It presents some differences when compared to current storage technologies since it provides major flexibility as far as the management of supplies at local and regional level are concerned. The concept is to use a rock mass to serve as a pressurised vessel in the process of containing stored natural gas, with maximum pressures from about 15 MPa to 25 MPa. This idea requires the excavation of large and vertically cylindrical caverns with diameters ranging from 20m to 50m, with heights ranging from 50m to 115m. 12-30 million Nm³ (400-1,100 million cubic feet (MMcf)) of capacity for natural gas storage. We are talking about caverns from 100m to 200m below ground (Brandshaug, Christianson, and Damjanac, 2001).

In cases where the storage pressure is lower than that in the pipeline itself, the injection into the cavern takes place from the pipeline through a process of flow control. Otherwise compression is used to boost gas pressure. An air or water cooler is usually in the process of cooling the gas, after compression, and the moment before the injection of the gas inside the cavern. The gas can be injected back into the cavern during the gas injection if the pressure levels in the cavern demonstrate to be superior than those in the pipeline. This process will take place with the help of a separate compressor after being circulated through a cooler. It can also contribute to rise in the working gas volume in the cavern. A refrigeration unit can be used in order to cool the recirculated gas to a lower temperature for the purpose of increasing even further the working gas capacity (Sofregaz US Inc., & LRC., 1999)

6.3.8 Hydrates

The discovery of large gas hydrate accumulations represented an important result in the search for possible energy sources in the earth. Gas hydrates are crystalline substances of water and natural gas where a solid water-lattice holds gas molecules in clathrate, or in a structure similar to a cage. Basically the storage of natural gas would require nothing less than the synthesis of the hydrate and its regasification. This process can be very useful due to the fact that the density of natural gas has a significant influence as far as the reduction of space requests for gas storage are concerned.

Only a limited number of gas hydrate accumulations have been analysed in detail, and it must be taken into consideration that only in 50 areas around the world does this energy source appear to occur. Further research into gas hydrates is necessary for a significant breakthrough to occur (Altenergymag.com, 2007). The availability of producible gas hydrate resources and the cost to extract them are two crucial elements to take into consideration to determine the real importance of this energy resource and how it may be used in response to the world's energy demands. Actually considerable doubts still exist about the real potential of gas hydrates as an energy resource. The limitations include accessibility, reliable use and compatible costs (Oellrich, 2004).

6.3.1 KPIs evaluation for gas storage

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the gas storage solutions introduced in the previous section are proposed. As it happened for electricity storage systems, qualitative measurements are used in multiple KPIs, in order to create a uniform view of these technologies given their very different characteristics and readiness levels.

The main sources that inform the table below, come from EIA (2016a), EIA (2016b) and NaturalGas (2016).

Table 14: KPIs evaluation for gas storage

Theme	Type of indicator	Depleted gas reservoir	Aquifer reservoir	Salt formation	LNG storage tanks
Environmental impact	<i>Main environmental impact</i>	Landscape impact due to extraction equipment installation	Landscape impact due to extraction equipment installation	Disposal of saturated salt water during mining	8-10% of gas losses in LNG production, 2-2.5% losses in regasification
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	Medium	Medium	Medium-High	Medium
Capital investment cost	<i>Energy-related cost (\$/kWh)</i>	Medium	High	Low	0.01
Performance index	<i>Capacity</i>	10 ⁹ m ³	Comparable to depleted gas reservoirs	1.5-3 * 10 ⁸ m ³	450 * 10 ⁶ m ³
Performance index	<i>Charge/Discharge time</i>	120-200 days / 60-120 days	120-200 days / 60-120 days	20 days / 5-20 days	2.6 * 10 ⁶ m ³ /h
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan (years)</i>	30	30	30	30
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	High	High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Gas Directive 2009/73/EC mention gas storage as one of core elements of the gas distribution system. Enhancing energy security by sustaining gas storage technologies. 27 projects to be finished within 2020, € 17 billion granted.			
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Low	Low	Low	Medium

The table above shows a KPI-based comparison between different proposed gas storage technologies. As can be seen, the main environmental issue related to these operations is in terms of landscape impact resulting from the presence of significant charge/discharge installations required. Moreover, LNG production releases a certain amount of natural gas emissions in the atmosphere.

Huge amounts of natural gas can be stored in reservoirs (including depleted, aquifer and salt formation types), whilst LNG technology has lower capacities and is suitable for smaller gas volume storage options.

When compared to salt formation storage facilities, depleted gas and aquifer reservoirs require longer charge and extraction times, and the lower investment costs make it a more accessible technology.

Referring to the public opinion more generally people appear to see the environmental and landscape drawbacks associated to gas reservoirs, though LNG technology seems to be more acceptable.

6.4 Coal

The same approach applied for oil storage can be proposed for coal storage. Coal supplies are much easier to store than gas, electricity or heat, and the main focus in coal stacking is due to productivity calculations and the need to avoid air and ground pollution from rain. In the following section an overview of coal stacking techniques is presented.

6.4.1 Coal stacking

Figure 11 Coal stacking position (RSTPS, 2012)

Coal is a material that offers the possibility to be stored in large quantities in preparation for some specific future needs. Trucks or wagons are the main means of transport used to take the produced coal to these storage areas.

Climate conditions, the dimension and design of the storage required represent the main factors that influence the choice for the most suitable techniques to use in different countries. Stacking can be done in open areas but also on covered stack areas or in closed coal silos. The first case is more frequently used. The long period storing in open areas can cause some problems due to the spontaneous combustion of coal as a consequence of the gas created in the stack pile. This may arise due to a number different factors: the first category represents those that are possible to be controlled (for example the management of the coal storage in stockpiles, silos/bunkers and mills in the power plant) as well as the all the procedures related to the coal transport. On the other hand, there are those factors that cannot be controlled such the ambient air conditions and the coal itself.

Coal is stored for a limited period of time, given the chance of self-heating is directly connected to its storage conditions. The problem with long-term silo/bunker storage may be solved with ventilation placed at the top of the silo or bunker to remove all gases released from the coal or by sealing the silo/bunker. Stacking process demands consciously and respect of the rules otherwise unpleasant situations can come out (Okten *et al.*, 2013; Radhakrishnane, 2012).

6.5 Heat storage

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is a proven technology with over three decades of successful installations and stable thermal energy capacity. This process is done by heating or cooling a storage medium in order to use the energy for later use in power generation and also to for heating and cooling applications.

TES systems can be divided along three different technologies, each one with its own characteristics and different associated costs: sensible heat storage (e.g. water, sand), latent heat storage using phase change materials (e.g. from a solid state into a liquid state) and thermo-chemical storage using chemical reactions to store and release thermal energy.

The first system offers storage efficiencies between 50-90% and capacity ranging from 10-50kwh/t, according to the heat level of the storage and thermal insulation technologies (VV. AA., 2013c).

The second system (PCMs) is able to offer storage efficiencies from 75-90% and a superior storage capacity. As far as regards thermo-chemical storage (TCS) systems can reach storage efficiencies from 75%-100%, storage capacities of up to 250kwh/m³ with operation temperatures superior to 300°C (VV. AA., 2013c).

The sensible heat storage system is the most economical, while the other two options have higher associated costs and are considered economically viable only for applications with high numbers of cycles.

TES technologies face significant obstacles around market entry: TCS and PCM both need to improve in terms of stable storage performance, linked to associated material properties, though the main barrier is in relation to the costs required.

On the other hand, the storage of thermal energy presents the following advantages: including its important role in contributing to the reduction of CO₂ emissions; the process of replacing heat and cold generation from fossil fuels; in reducing the need for power during peak periods when costs are higher; and in contributing to heat production capacity.

6.5.1 Sensible Heat Storage

Sensible Heat Storage (SHS) concerns the process of storing heat in a liquid or solid for the purpose of using it again at a later time, when needed. SHS occurs by avoiding the phase change of the liquid or solid, adding heat to the storage medium and increasing its temperature. Water can be used in co-generation plants and to store energy from heating systems based on solar energy and represents the most common type of storage medium for SHS. Water tank storage is a cost-effective storage solution that can be carried out in small building systems and big plants (GENI, 2012).

6.5.1.1 Seasonal thermal energy storage

Seasonal thermal energy storage refers to storage of heat or cold for periods of time that may last several months. Thermal energy offers the possibility to be collected in every possible moment and to be used even in other seasons of the year when the need of energy is higher and its advantages can be understood as follows:

- Underground thermal energy storage: it can be used for both heat and cold storage.
- Surface and above ground technologies, typically insulated water tank storage solutions.

The types of seasonal thermal energy stores are: tank thermal energy store (HW), pit thermal energy storage (PTES), borehole thermal energy store (BTES) and aquifer-thermal energy store (ATES). As far as construction costs are concerned, HW usually has higher costs while ATES is the cheaper option.

Future characteristics for large scale seasonal thermal energy storage need to account for the following factors: prices should be cheaper given expected prices are less than 50 €/m³, sealing by polymeric foil and free flowing evacuated insulation material (Kerskes, 2011).

6.5.1.2 Steam accumulator

A steam accumulator is an insulated steel pressure tank containing hot water and steam under pressure. The concept of a steam accumulator is to release steam when demand is higher than the boiler's capacity in order to ensure supply in the period when the demand is low to accept steam.

Even though steam accumulators do not have a significant application in modern industry more generally, they have been installed in some industries, for example in bio-technology, medical and industrial sterilisation processes and in the printing and food manufacturing sectors. Steam accumulators have also been installed in more traditional industries such as breweries and dyehouses.

Modern boilers have become smaller and there has also been an increase in the use of small water-tube boilers, coil boilers and annular boilers, all of which are efficient though they do reduce the thermal capacity of the system and make it vulnerable to peak load problems.

The possibilities of possible applications for steam accumulators are endless. For example, they can be used with immersion heater boilers or electrodes in order to generate steam during an off peak period, storing it and then using it during peak times.

In terms of efficiency it is possible to note that steam accumulators are tools that gives guarantees in this field since they may provide the most cost effective way of supplying steam to a batch process (Spirax Sarco Limited, 2016).

6.5.1.3 Molten salt

Figure 12: Molten salt system (eSolar website, 2013)

Looking at its efficiency values, the flexibility and cost-effectiveness in using molten salt represents the best option for large scale energy storage systems. This storage feature, unlike other technologies, allows for stable power delivery without the need for any backup fossil fuel support. Molten salt is used to store thermal energy from solar power and then convert it and dispatch it as electrical power when needed.

During the day the system pumps molten salt through special conduits or a tower that is heated, thanks to the long-time sun exposure and held in storage tanks during the night. The tanks store the salt at atmospheric pressure. Molten salt is stored until electricity is needed independently, whether it is during the day or night. When this is the case, molten salt is dispatched from the hot tank with the help of a heat exchanger in order to create extreme heated steam that is fed to turbines in order to generate electricity.

The molten salt never demands replacing or topping up during the entire plant life duration (SolarReserve, 2016).

6.5.2 *Phase Change Materials*

Sensible Heat Storage (SHS) is a solution used quite frequently because it involves low running costs, but it does present some problems in terms of charging and discharging temperature. In order to solve these issues, Phase Change Materials (PCMs) can be used in storage systems. Actually, they store and release thermal energy during the process of melting and freezing (as they change from one phase to another). PCMs are ideal products for thermal management solutions. The mass and latent heat of fusion of the material used will influence the quantity of energy stored.

PHC have two main advantages: the first one is related to the fact that they have higher storage capacities and the other one is that storage operates isothermally at the melting point of the material.

The PHC can be either solid to liquid, or liquid to gas. Water/ice represents the most effective phase change material. From a cost perspective it is quite interesting since is known to be the cheap and also the simplest PCH. Unfortunately, the freezing temperature of water is fixed at 0° (32°F) which makes it inappropriate for most of energy storage applications (PCM Products Ltd, 2016).

6.5.2.1 *Ice storage air conditioning*

Thermal energy storage is like a battery for a building's air-conditioning system. Ice is made and stored inside IceBank energy storage tanks during night time hours, which represent the off-peak period. After this process, the stored ice is used to cool the building users during the following day.

This process avoids the high energy costs, along with peak demand charges during the day. The ice storage system process comprehends the ice charging mode and ice melt/burn mode. Additional savings are delivered from extended free cooling periods.

The main purpose of ice storage is to shift on-peak electric load to off-peak times, this brings significant benefits in terms of reduction of air polluting emissions and therefore to environment and people's health (CALMAC, 2016).

6.5.3 *Heat Storage via Chemical Reactions*

The use of heat to cause a specific physicochemical reaction is another possibility when storing thermal energy and should be taken into consideration. The products that result from this process can also be stored. When the reverse reaction takes place the heat is then released. Heat exchange is connected to a constant level of temperature during the time reaction occurrences. The temperature of heat release and heat storage at most times are different. Thermo-chemical reactions can be used in different ways, for example to control humidity, to store heat and cold, and also for thermal energy transportation due to the high storage capacity (IEA, 2013b).

6.5.1 KPIs evaluation for heat storage

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the heat storage technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. It helps giving a clear and simple understanding of each technology strength and weakness towards a low carbon future.

The main sources that inform the table below, come from CALMAC (2016), GENI (2012) and VV. AA. (2013c).

Table 15: KPIs evaluation for heat storage

Theme	Type of indicator	Sensible Heat Storage	Phase Change Materials	Thermo-Chemical Storage
Environmental impact	<i>Main environmental impact</i>	Negligible		
Capital investment cost	<i>Energy-related cost (€/kWh)</i>	0.1-10	8-50	10-100
Performance index	<i>Efficiency</i>	50-90%	75-90%	75-100%
Performance index	<i>Storage Capacity (kWh/t)</i>	10-50	50-150	120-250
Technological regime	<i>Infrastructure lifespan</i>	10-30 (depends on the number of storage cycle and temperature)		
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	Medium-High	Medium-High	Medium-High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	Energy Roadmap 2050 2030 climate & energy framework (Each member state is free to take individual decisions on the measures to reach the set objectives)		
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium	Low-Medium	Low

As can be seen from the above table, heat storage technologies have a generally low impact on the environment. The main difference between the proposed technology groups lies in the capital costs involved: sensible heat storage methods are largely the cheapest, whilst PCM and thermo-chemical storage requires higher expenses for equipment purchasing and installation.

Technical performances are generally high for these technologies with the highest values, which characterise the thermo-chemical storage methods (efficiency up to 100%). Also, despite the good performances and “green” aspect of these processes, they are not at full technological maturity limiting their ability to build large market shares, and public opinion is not completely accepting in exploiting these technologies yet. There is no specific policy dedicated to heat storage measures.

7 Energy end users

The end user stage of the supply chain is a very wide field, which comprehends multiple aspects of the energy system. As shown in Figure 13, the three main sectors responsible for the European Union's final energy consumption are Households, Transport and Industry. In this section, we are going to focus mainly on Households and Transport. The main types of technological solutions for building comfort (lighting, heating, cooling and ventilation), building control (Building Automation and Control Systems), individual power and heat generation (micro CHP), along with private transport will be investigated.

Figure 13: European final energy consumption by sector (Eurostat, 2015)

With the European Energy Roadmap 2050, energy efficiency has become key to the EU's strategic development. More efficient buildings will provide better comfort for the inhabitants, while reducing energy demand and result in cost savings and GHG emission reductions from power plants.

In 2015, buildings were responsible for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of CO₂ emissions in the EU. This is mainly due to the fact that most of these buildings are old and inefficient. The European Commission has estimated that, currently, about 35% of the EU's buildings are over 50 years old. It is clear, then, that a lot of improvements still need to be done in such a critical sector (European Commission, 2016d).

Even though building technologies present several differences depending on the region of Europe considered, it is possible to give a general overview of the current state of the sector based on when the building has been last retrofitted.

Current situation for building without retrofitting in the last 10-15 years:

- **Lighting:** Mainly Fluorescent and Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFL) are installed and, in residential buildings, it is often possible to find older incandescent lamps. Automation systems are very rare and only implemented in commercial buildings.
- **Micro CHP:** Micro CHP solutions are implemented very rarely.
- **Heating:** Buildings are generally heated with individual gas or oil fired boilers. As we have already alluded to in Chapter 4, district heating would be a more efficient solution, but has been mainly implemented in the North-East regions of Europe.
- **Ventilating:** Building air quality is guaranteed almost solely by natural ventilation.

- **Air conditioning:** Cooling systems are present mainly in commercial buildings and rarely in residential ones. The technology installed is in the majority of cases a central chiller unit.
- **Building monitoring, automation and control systems:** Indoor comfort sensors are rarely installed and temperature sensors can be found a few times in commercial buildings. Building Automation and Control Systems (BACS) are not used.

In the last 10 years Europe has started to push towards an improvement in building efficiency, with policies and incentives that support building retrofitting operations. The latest directive that regulates building efficiency, in order to reach the Roadmap2050 targets, is the 2012/27/EU, which defines a series of common measures for energy efficiency promotion across the EU. Following the directive guidelines, more advanced technologies are implemented in modern or recently retrofitted buildings, especially concerning monitoring and control.

The current situation for new or recently retrofitted building includes:

- **Lighting:** LED lamps are rapidly becoming the standard, as their cost reduces due to their low electricity consumption and high quality illumination. Light controls are often implemented, in particular in commercial buildings, with a predominance of Vacancy/Occupancy sensors. Residential buildings start to see the installation of control sensors as well, in particular dimmers for indoor lighting and timers or daylighting for gardens.
- **Micro CHP:** Micro CHP systems are becoming more frequent, allowing users to save money on both electricity and heat, reduce GHG emissions and sell excess electricity back to the grid.
- **Heating:** The installation of heat pumps is more often preferred over traditional boilers, due to the higher efficiency and lower environmental impact provided.
- **Ventilating:** Mechanical ventilation is often present, since it can guarantee higher levels of indoor air quality.
- **Air conditioning:** VRV are often implemented. Their choice over chillers is highly project dependent, but due to more compact dimensions and modularity they are better suited for retrofitting operations where space is an issue.
- **Building monitoring, automation and control systems:** Temperature and Humidity sensors are often present to regulate mechanical ventilation. CO₂ sensors are a possibility but they are less frequently installed. BACS are often used in commercial buildings.

Transport is more resilient than the building sector to changes and it is still dominated by gasoline and diesel cars in the private sector. In recent years, however, we have seen a strong increase in the number of electric cars sold in Europe. According to the European Automobile Manufacturers Association, during the period 2014–2015, electrical cars saw an increase of between 50% and 70% in units sold while hybrid cars have increased their unit sales by around 20%, forecasting an increasing impact from those emerging technologies in the transport sector in the near future.

Electric transport is not limited only to private cars, but plays an important role in public transport as well (bus, tram, metro). With increased urbanisation taking place across Europe cities are evolving to provide a more efficient public transport, which can guarantee high energy savings and a better quality of life compared to private transport options.

7.1 Lighting

Lighting is an essential part of everyday life, as lighting technologies can be found in every sector, from industry to building or transportation and with different aims, such as indoor illumination, traffic lights, cars lights, *etc.*

In the following sections, we focus on end user applications including the main type of lamps present in the market and the main control system used to regulate their functioning. The savings therefore on energy consumption will also be presented.

7.1.1 Incandescent lamps

Incandescent lighting works by heat-driven light emissions (incandescence). Light is produced when a filament of tungsten is heated by an electric current until it glows.

With conventional incandescent bulbs, the filament is protected from coming in contact with oxygen in the air thanks to the lamp bulb, preventing the filament from burning up. In 2014, 79% of lamp sales were incandescent lamps. Even though they are characterised by a low efficacy (around 8 to 14 lm/W), most of these lamps can manage to convert into visible light no more than the 8% of the energy they use, wasting the remaining 92% as heat lost in the environment. Incandescent lamps are cheap, simple in operation, are dimmable and emit a good natural colour light, but their working life is short (typically between 400 - 2,000 hours) when compared to other, more recent, technologies. Overall, they are the least efficient light sources with energy ratings of E, F or G.

Under the Ecodesign Directive, between 2009 and 2016, traditional incandescent bulbs will cease to be sold (with the exception of some specific applications) and will gradually be replaced by other types of electric light. Incandescent bulbs main application is for domestic and display lighting, but can also be used for commercial lighting. One of their drawbacks, poor energy efficiency and heat wasting, can become an advantage in applications such as incubators, egg hatching, heat lamps for reptiles and for some industrial heating and drying processes (Tahir *et al.*, 2014: 9).

7.1.2 Halogen

In halogen lamps, the filament of tungsten is sealed into a compact transparent envelope filled with an inert halogen gas. Thanks to this process, the lifetime span of the bulb is highly increased. It operates its filament at a higher temperature and has slightly higher efficacy of 10 – 25 lm/W when compared to incandescent lamps, leading to saving possibilities of up to 50%. Another advantage of halogens is that they have the possibility to be dimmed. Halogen lamps are usually energy rated at B or C and have a longer life than a standard incandescent bulb. However, considering the increasing demand for high levels of efficiency, coming from both legislations and customers, halogen lamps are still considered a poor solution in terms of efficacy and have a relatively short life times when compared to other solutions such as Compact Fluorescent Light bulbs and Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs).

Halogen lamps offer a good quality light and can produce a colour in the range of 2,700 to 3,200 K which is a relatively comfortable, warm white light. This make them ideal for home installations and studios, or in general all those places where a bright warm instant light is required. Halogen lamps are often used in cars, floodlights, desktop lamps, projector lamps to be used in theatres or studios (Tahir *et al.*, 2014:9).

7.1.3 Compact Fluorescent Lamps (CFL)

CFLs use less power to supply the same amount of light as an incandescent lamp, with typically efficacy of between 50 to 70 lm/W, and they can achieve 75% savings when compared to conventional light bulbs. It has to be noted, though, that CFLs contain mercury, a highly toxic and polluting material. For this reason, CFLs at the end of their lifecycle have to be disposed of safely, in accordance to the strict EU regulations. In

recent years, with the increasing demand of highly efficient lamps, the use of CFLs have been encouraged by multiple organisations throughout the world, undertaking several measures to encourage their adoption, given their ability to reduce electricity consumption.

CFLs represent a simple and quick solution for households and businesses to increase their energy efficiency. Moreover, CFLs have the important advantage of a very fast reach of their full brightness, unlike incandescent lamps that need some time to 'warm up'. On the other side, not all CFLs are suitable for dimming, so they should be selected with care, depending on the specific needs. Given the simplicity and flexibility of CFLs, some electric utilities and local governments have either subsidised CFLs or provided them free to customers as a fast and effective means of reducing electricity demand. The majority of CFL applications are internal in places such as offices or corridors (Tahir *et al.*, 2014: 11).

7.1.4 LED

LED lamps are based on diodes, a technology that is present in many electrical devices such as computers. They emit light when electricity is passed through a chemical compound (crystal), exciting it to generate light. LED lamps are usually made of a cluster of LEDs packed in a suitable bulb and can offer a white light of up to 250 lm/W. Lifespans are greatly increased with respect to older lamp technologies, with around 50,000 hours (some LEDs even promise 100,000 hours) of working life. LED technology offers high efficacy, ultra-long life, and limited environmental impact, using only 10% of the power required to generate the same amount of light with standard incandescent bulbs. As a comparison, it is worth noticing how CFL lamps use 20% of incandescent lamp energy and halogen lamp use 70%.

LEDs are a type of Solid State Lighting (SSL), which means they use different types of semiconductor LEDs as sources of illumination. Being based on SSL, LEDs can be easily and smartly controlled and programmed, making them the best light system choice when a high degree of control is required. This high versatility allows LEDs to be used in a very wide range of applications, from internal lighting to traffic and street lighting, from very small portable lamps to big scale ADs screens.

Some of the drawbacks with LEDs include the initial cost, the uniformity of light output and lack of extensive data from manufacturers, due to the relatively novelty of the technology. As the development in this area continues, it is expected that these issues will be overcome (Tahir *et al.*, 2014: 14).

Two competing technologies which could radically change the nature of lighting in the future are Organic Light Emitting and Polymer Light Emitting Diodes.

- **Organic light emitting diode (OLED):** OLEDs are made by placing a series of organic thin films between two conductors. They make use of flat display technology and when electrical current pass through it, a bright light is emitted. Due to the nature of this technology, OLEDs are intrinsically well suited for indoor illumination and could open the way to new solutions that abandon the use of luminaries, such as glowing wall papers or illuminated ceiling tiles. OLEDs are already on the market for displays applications, such as TVs or portable devices (smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc.).
- **Polymer light emitting diode (PLED):** PLEDs consist of thin, flexible film made of polymers and capable of emitting the full colour spectrum of light. PLEDs are a good example of 'nanotechnology'. The ability to dissolve the active materials in a solvent to form an "ink", and deposit by a range of printing techniques on a wide variety of substrates at low temperatures provides a number of manufacturing advantages over small molecule OLED technology. The total thickness of all layers in a PLED display device can be less than 500 nm compared to a human hair which is 0.1 mm thick.

7.1.5 KPIs evaluation for lighting technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the lighting technologies introduced in the previous section are presented. Taking into account the fast pace at which this specific market is changing in recent years, with a rapid growth of LED lamps in the market, the proposed table helps giving a clear and simple understanding of each technology’s strength and weakness.

The main sources that inform Table 16, below, come from Tahir *et al.* (2014), Navigant Consulting Inc. (2012a) and Navigant Consulting Inc. (2012b).

Table 16: KPIs evaluation for lighting technologies

Theme	Type of indicator	Incandescent	Halogen	CFL	LED
Environmental impact	<i>Presence of toxic material requiring disposal</i>	No	No	Yes	Yes
Performance index	<i>Energy Use (MJ/20 million lumen-hrs)</i>	15,100	13,000	3,780	3,540-1,630
Capital investment cost	<i>Average purchase price*</i>	€0.40	€1.50	€1	€5-30
Technological regime	<i>Lifetime (hours)</i>	750 - 2,000	3,000-4,000	8,000-10,000	25,000-50,000
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	High	Medium-High
Political commitment	<i>Policy support</i>	Banned	Planned ban	Accepted	Accepted
Public opinion	<i>Market share (2011)</i>	69.3%	4.9%	25.4%	0.4%**

*Cost Comparison for 60-watt incandescent equivalent lightbulb.

** Official data for all technologies has been found for 2011, but LED market share is rapidly growing (Yu, 2015).

The most mature lighting technology is represented by incandescent lamps. As shown in the previous table, they have the highest energy absorption index when compared to the other proposed lighting tools. For this reason, although they still represent the most diffused lighting method they are now generally no longer sold in the EU market.

Referring to the most efficient and innovative solutions, CFLs have a more mature technological background than LEDs, and this is clearly reflected in the higher market share covered by this technology.

On the other hand, LEDs have even higher efficiencies when compared to CFLs, but since they are an emerging technology their market prices are still too high to increase their market share. Moreover, from a technical point of view, it’s not easy regulating LEDs’ intensity, because not all types of LED can be interfaced to light control systems, which are described in detail in the following section. Generally, LEDs technology is developing strongly and their costs are becoming more acceptable for the general public. It can be easily foreseen that they will establish greater and greater market share in the near future.

7.1.6 Lighting control systems

Lighting control systems are technologies that permit to control the functioning of lamps in different ways, such as regulating the light intensity or simply controlling the ON/OFF functionality in manual or smart ways. In the next sections, the main lighting control technologies used nowadays are presented (Eaton, 2014).

7.1.6.1 Switches

Switches are the most common type of lighting control used in buildings. They are simple to install and operate, are relatively cost effective and can work with all type of lighting lamps without any problem. They make also possible to control multiple luminaries with one single switch.

If operated correctly, switches allow users to have an efficient energy consumption, but most of the times this is not the case. Users tend often to forget lights on when leaving a room, especially in communal areas, causing important energy waste.

Overall, the system is simple and reliable, but provide no automation nor advanced control on the lighting.

7.1.6.2 Dimmers

Dimmers are the most commonly used type of lighting control system in residential buildings, after switches. They allow the user to control the light intensity manually, making it possible to reduce energy consumption, easily cutting back any unwanted over-lighting. Even though they can provide some energy savings, the main reason homeowners usually choose this solution is comfort, thanks to the possibility to dim lighting following the user personal needs.

Dimmers are not compatible with some types of CFL and LED lamps, and some lamps may cause more energy to be consumed and the lamp life may be shortened compared to a simple on/off switch.

7.1.6.3 Photosensors

Photosensors are based on a light-sensitive photocell that produces an electrical current proportional to the amount of external lighting measured. In this way, photosensors are able to dim light intensity based on how much natural light is already present in the room, in order to maintain the required total amount of illumination. These can solve the problem of over-lighting because they can reduce artificial light when there is adequate and suitable natural light present.

They are mainly used in commercial buildings, where working activity is performed during daily hours and this type of control can have a high impact on energy savings; while in residential buildings their main application is to simply turn on and off external lighting when needed.

Photosensor are an efficient and reliable way to reduce energy consumption, but they require the installation of lamps that can be dimmed. The possibility of wireless technology increases the flexibility and possibility for retrofitting of this solution.

7.1.6.4 Occupancy/Vacancy sensors

Occupancy/vacancy sensors automatically turn on or off lighting when somebody enters or leaves a room, thereby increasing energy efficiency. Different technologies are used to detect the presence of a person inside the room, such as passive infrared, ultrasonic and acoustic. Most of the commercially available solutions implement more than one technology at the same time.

The difference between occupancy and vacancy sensors is simply that the first one automatically turns the lights on when someone enters the room, while the second one only turns off the light if the room is left empty for a certain amount of time. In residential buildings vacancy sensors are usually preferred, since

they can save more energy, due to the fact that homeowners do not always need to turn on the lights when they enter a room.

While providing an automatic solution for lighting, with high possibilities of energy savings, this control technology does not solve the problem of over-lighting. Another important issue with occupancy sensors is their need to be well tuned in order to avoid generating frustration in the users. The experience of an automatic light turning off when using a toilet is a common a typical example of a frustrating occupancy sensor failure.

The possibility of wireless technology increases the flexibility and possibility for retrofitting of this solution.

7.1.6.5 Timers

Timers are an efficient way of reducing energy consumption as they allow users to regulate the lighting depending on the particular time of the day they need it. They come in two varieties, countdown and astronomical. Countdown timers allow the user to turn on the lights at a particular time and for a certain period during the day. Astronomical timers are based on sunset and sunrise time, automatically calculated every day depending on the user’s geographical position.

They can be regulated to work in a way similar to photosensors, varying the level of light to suit daily tasks at different times of the day. They may also be used to change the lighting control regime passing, for example, from manual switching during the day to automatic movement sensors at night.

Timers present an automatic solution, but need to be correctly programmed, following the user’s needs and habits, in order to achieve high energy savings. The drawback with this control technology is that it doesn’t take into account the possible daily variability and cannot automatically tune the different light intensity needed between a sunny and a cloudy day.

7.1.7 KPIs evaluation for Lighting control systems

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the lighting control systems introduced in the previous section are explored. Due to the very specific nature of the discussed technologies, the KPIs considered for the final analysis in the following table are very case specific, putting more focus on a technological comparison. The main sources that inform Table 17, below, come from Eaton (2016).

Table 17: KPIs evaluation for lighting control systems

Theme	Type of indicator	Simple switch	Dimmers	Day lighting	Occupancy sensors	Timers
Capital investment cost	Average market price	1-3€	20€	25-30€	25-30€	25-30€
Capital investment cost	Average annual energy savings*	-	38%	26%	50%	54%
Technological regime	Operation	Manual	Manual	Automatic	Automatic	Semi-automatic

Theme	Type of indicator	Simple switch	Dimmers	Day lighting	Occupancy sensors	Timers
Technological regime	<i>Control</i>	ON/OFF	Intensity regulation	Intensity regulation	ON/OFF	Intensity regulation
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	High	High	High
Technology flexibility	<i>Field of application</i>	Residential building	Residential building	Commercial building	Commercial building	Commercial building
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	European Directive 2012/27EU on Energy efficiency				
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance and success of the technology</i>	-	Medium-High	Low-Medium	Medium	Medium

*value considered for incandescent lamps. Using more advanced lamps those values decrease.

As we can see from the above table, it must be firstly pointed out that not all the building typologies are equipped with the same light control systems. Indeed, the most of the residential buildings have no control systems, or manual dimmers for single lamps installed in the apartments. Very often, commercial and industrial buildings have more complex and efficient controls, in order to minimise energy consumption and costs. Generally, lighting control systems are not largely used, because people are still mainly focused on the final lighting tool (i.e., the lamp) absorption, rather than investing money into an efficiency intervention at system level.

Not only public opinion, but also political commitment plays an important role in this “misrecognition” of lighting control systems importance: in fact, if energy efficient lamps (LEDs) utilisation is encouraged with economic incentives and discounts, no actions are actually taken in order to boost the diffusion of lighting control systems other than policies in favour of the overall building efficiency.

As shown in table 15, investment costs for the presented technologies are almost the same (except for the simplest switch tool). Then, the choice of the best technology is not money driven, but each method is often selected on the basis of a specific application. Manual dimmers are mainly chosen for residential house lighting systems; daylighting control is the most suitable for residential outdoor areas or working buildings; systems based on occupancy or vacancy sensors can be used in commercial buildings, in order to light the rooms up only if needed (i.e., if people are present in the room); timers can be used in commercial or industrial buildings too, especially in transit zones.

7.2 Micro CHP

Using the same principle described for cogeneration district heating, micro heat and power systems allow for the production of both heating and electricity on a smaller scale (0,3 - 50 kW), ideal for single/multi

family home or small office building. An important advantage of local generation is that it lacks the energy losses of energy transportation over long distances, in particular for heat. Most micro CHP units operate in grid-parallel mode, so that the building continues to receive some of its electrical needs from the electrical network, but it may also export some electricity to the electrical network.

Although the total "efficiency" of a micro CHP system is similar to a boiler system, the electricity produced has a much higher value than heat. It is the value of this electricity which covers the investment cost of the micro CHP unit and provides a net saving.

In the following sections, the main solutions for micro CHP are introduced and discussed (VV.AA., 2006).

7.2.1 Reciprocating engines

Reciprocating engines generate mechanical power by using the energy produced expanding a gas burned within a chamber integrated to the engine. For this reason, reciprocating engines are also called internal combustion engines or endothermic engines and they are the type of engine commonly used in cars.

When used for CHP generation, the engine drives an electric generator while the heat from the engine exhaust gases is used for building heating purposes. Engines have the advantage of providing high efficiencies even in small sizes, with the addition of modularity. For this reason, they are widely used in small plants and, depending on the application and amount of energy needed, several small modules can be assembled in one system. Modularity allows for easier and more efficient control, in order to better follow the load curves, and it also eases maintenance.

Reciprocating engines can be split into two main categories:

- **Diesel engines:** They are also called compression-ignition engines, since combustion of the fuel is induced from the high temperature of compressed air. This kind of engine presents a higher power to heat ratio compared to spark ignition engines, and operates through a large scale of very small sizes from $5 kW_{el}$ for small units to a power equivalent of some $10 MW_{el}$ for large systems. Biodiesel and rape oil are potentially discredited alternatives as fuel for diesel engines, in order to reduce CO_2 emissions and maintain relatively high efficiency.
- **Spark ignition engines:** This type of engine works similar to the Diesel engine, but ignition is provoked through an electrical spark. This type of engine ranges from between $3 kW_{el}$ and $6 MW_{el}$ capacities. The heat to power ratio is lower than the one achievable with compression engine, yet the overall efficiency of this technology is higher.

7.2.2 Microturbines

Microturbines are a type of Internal Combustion Engine designed to work on a relatively small scale that produces both heat and electricity. Presently, microturbines can generate between 25kW to 1000kW for small scale usage (residential, small buildings), with almost the same efficiency than reciprocating engines at lower emission levels of NO_x and CO_2 . Micro turbines high outlet temperature ($> 500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), make them suitable for numerous high value applications, such as direct drying or heating processes as well as cooling applications in absorption systems.

They offer several advantages compared to other small-scale power generation technologies. The small number of moving parts make it easy to repair, while compact size and lightweight simplify the installation of new devices. Microturbines also have high efficiency, fewer emissions and lower electricity costs than internal combustion engines and they can use different types of fuels, from natural gas to biogas or waste fuels.

The drawbacks are a high initial investment cost, the loss of power and efficiency with high ambient temperature or altitude and the production of constant noise, which can be problematic in residential buildings. Moreover, other solutions that use renewable sources, such as PV, may prove more attractive.

7.2.3 Stirling engines

A Stirling engine is a closed-cycle regenerative heat engine with a permanently gaseous working fluid. They operate by cyclically compressing and expanding the working fluid (generally helium or hydrogen), thanks to the temperature difference across the engine. The working fluid moves a system of pistons, resulting in a conversion of heat energy to mechanical work. The external combustion facilitates the control of the process and supports a cleaner and more efficient process.

Figure 14: Stirling engine schematic view in Alpha, Beta and Gamma configurations (diystirlingengine.com, n.d.)

The main advantage of Stirling engines is that, thanks to the external combustion, they can make use of almost any heat source and thus work optimally in conjunction with renewable sources. They also guarantee high thermodynamic efficiency and present a low level of noise and vibration (Energy International, 2002). Another point to consider is that they have a low power-to-weight ratio, making it suitable for installations where weight and space is not an issue.

7.2.4 Fuel cells

A fuel cell produces electricity converting the chemical energy from a fuel (usually natural gas) into electricity through a chemical reaction of positively charged hydrogen ions and oxygen or another oxidising agent. Even though they may look similar, they differ from batteries as they require a continuous source of fuel and oxygen, or air, to sustain the chemical reaction.

As fuel cells create electricity chemically, rather than by combustion, they are not subject to the thermodynamic laws that limit a conventional power plant, resulting in a more efficient extraction of energy from a fuel. Consequently, they can provide an electrical efficiency of around 40-50% (Jothilingam & Suresh, 2015) being around 10 percentage points higher than corresponding engines. Waste heat from the process is then used for heating purposes.

The downside is significantly higher investment costs, which are much higher than reciprocating engines. These costs need to be consistently reduced in order to improve fuel cells market acceptance and make them a viable solution for micro CHP system.

7.2.5 KPIs evaluation for micro CHP technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the micro CHP technologies introduced in the previous section is outlined. It gives a clear and simple presentation of each technology's strengths and weaknesses when framed within a low carbon future context.

The main sources that inform Table 18, below, come from IEA (2015), VV.AA. (2010) and Thimsen (2002).

Table 18: KPIs evaluation for micro CHP technologies

Theme	Type of indicator	Reciprocating engines	Stirling engines	Micro turbines	Fuel cells
Environmental impact	<i>GHG emissions (gCO₂/kWh)</i>	600-690	Depends on the heat source	630	480
Performance index	<i>Total efficiency</i>	65-90%	65-95%	65-90%	85-95%
Performance index	<i>Electrical efficiency</i>	25-45%	25%	15-30%	35-50%
Capital investment cost	<i>Initial investment (€/kW_{el})</i>	340-2000	2500-4500	900-2500	8.000-18.000
Technological regime	<i>Lifetime (hours)</i>	35.000	50.000	40.000	60.000
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	Medium	High	Low-Medium
Political commitment	<i>Policy support</i>	European Directive 2012/27EU on Energy efficiency			
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance and success of the technology</i>	Medium	Low-Medium	Low-Medium	Low-medium

The most diffused CHP method is represented by reciprocating engines, because of their low capital investment costs, when compared to the others shown. The main advantage of micro turbines is their lower environmental impact, since their polluting emissions are reduced, and their good energy efficiency. Moreover, their lifetime is much higher than reciprocating engines.

Stirling engines are becoming increasingly successful in the last period, thanks to their quite high flexibility and the possibility to adapt them to the growing output from renewable energy sources, indicating their somewhat “green” credentials in micro CHP technology.

The most innovative micro CHP solutions are the fuel cells. However, prices are still too high for them to occupy a large market share. They still are the most promising CHP method, having the best electrical performances and the longest lifetime.

No specific policy is dedicated to micro CHP solutions at European level, their implementation falls under the Roadmap 2050 improvement measures and each member state is free to direct its evolution and policies on its own.

7.3 Building heating

Building heating is a fundamental comfort in residential building and workplaces, which makes up for a big percentage of the final users utility bills. For this reason, moving towards energy efficient and economic solutions for building heating is a primary concern not only for environmental issues, but also for economical aspects. Several technologies are presented nowadays but, especially for residential building, an effective technological upgrade is still far to take place.

In the following sections, main traditional and innovative building heating technologies are presented.

7.3.1 Boilers

Boilers are used in building heating and industrial processes to generate steam or hot water and can be fired by natural gas, fuel oil, or coal. A central heating unit provides heat to the whole facility and it is sized to match the size of the facility. An oversized boiler will result in excessive fuel consumption, with relatively high costs and pollution, while, an undersized boiler may not be able to generate the correct comfort temperature in every part of the building.

The ideal size for a boiler is one that can provide just the needed amount of heat on the coldest day of the year. Since in the past there was the tendency to over-calculate boilers dimensions, in order to leave some safety margin in case of a particularly cold period, most boilers are oversized by at least 30% (Odesie, n.a.).

This idea has changed today and the emphasis is now put on energy conservation. This fact, together with important improvements in heat loss calculations accuracy, means there is no need to oversize. This allows smaller radiators and less water in the system, which results in a smaller boiler, reduced fuel and installation costs and reduced polluting emissions.

On average, boilers have combustion efficiencies between 78% and 86%.

7.3.1.1 Fire-tube steel boilers

The name “fire-tube” is very descriptive of the technology. The fire, which means hot flue gases from the burner, passes through tubes that are surrounded by the fluid to be heated, which, in most cases, is water. Heated water will then be circulated through all the building for heating purposes or converted to steam for industrial use. The body of the boiler which contains the fluid is called pressure vessel (Odesie, n.a.).

Typically, fire-tube boilers do not exceed 25 million Btu/hr (MMBtu/hr), but capacities up to 70 MMBtu/hr are available (EnergyStar, 2015).

The advantages of a fire-tube boiler are its simple construction, which makes it relatively inexpensive, available in compact size and easy to repair, and less rigid water treatment requirements.

The disadvantages are the excessive weight in proportion with the steam generation capacity and the presence of a large volume of water stored in the pressure vessel. In practice, large volume of water means

excessive time required to raise steam pressure and an inability to respond quickly to load changes (P.C. McKenzie Company, n.a.).

7.3.1.2 **Water-tube steel boilers**

Water-tube steel boilers function with a working principle that is the exact opposite of fire-tube boilers. Here the water to be heated is inside the tubes and combustion gases pass around the outside of the tubes. These tubes are connected to a steam drum and a mud drum. The water is heated and steam is produced in the upper drum (Odesie, n.a.). The available size for water-tube boilers have a wide range: from small, low pressure units (around 10 MMBtu/hr) to large, high-pressure units with steam outputs of about 300 MMBtu/hr (EnergyStar, 2015).

The advantages of a water-tube boiler are a lower unit weight in proportion with the steam generation capacity and the absence of a large stored volume of water. This allows for less time required to raise steam pressure, a greater flexibility for responding to load changes, and the ability to handle higher pressures and temperatures, and high rates of steam generation. They also are available in sizes far greater than a fire-tube design.

Disadvantages include a high initial capital cost and a more complex design, which translates into more difficult repair and cleaning operations. Moreover, in certain cases, physical size may be an issue (P.C. McKenzie Company, n.a.).

7.3.1.3 **Cast iron boilers**

Cast iron boilers are used in small installations (0.35 to 10 MMBtu/hr) (Energy Star, 2016) where the most important requirement is long service life. A particular feature of these boilers is that they are composed of precast sections, meaning they can be more readily field-assembled than watertube or firetube boilers.

The most common problem associated with cast-iron boilers is cracking due to overheating or thermal shock. Since they are designed for small installations, at similar capacities, cast-iron boilers are more expensive than firetube or watertube boilers.

7.3.1.4 **Condensing boilers**

Condensing boilers are the most efficient type of boilers developed to date. They are modern and highly efficient boilers that use less fuel to produce the same amount of heat, therefore resulting in lower running costs than conventional fire-tube and water-tube boilers. Conventional boilers expel a lot of waste energy as hot vapour out of their flu, while condensing boilers make use of such heat, which is driven through the boiler and used to provide additional heat energy. This is made possible using two heat exchangers or a larger one, which allows the recovery of useful heat from the waste gases that would be otherwise lost through the flue. Figure 15 shows a schematic view of this process.

Figure 15: Condensing boiler scheme (microgreening.com, n.a.)

Since water is condensed inside the boiler, flue gas is emitted in the air at a considerably lower temperature than non-condensing boilers.

In common facility heating applications, the condensate water is at atmospheric pressure and is drained to a central condensate receiver, or into local smaller receivers that pump the condensate back to the central receiver unit.

They are typically fired with natural gas and operate between 95% and 96% combustion efficiencies. They also operate more efficiently than non-condensing boilers at part-load. Condensing boilers are available in capacities between 0.3 and 2 MMBtu/hr (EnergyStar, 2015), and can be connected in modular installations.

The advantages of condensing boilers are a greater efficiency (up to 12% more efficient than a non-condensing boiler), which results in reduced running costs and CO_2 emissions, and easy installation and repair operations (Microgreening, n.a.).

Although condenser boilers are more efficient than traditional boilers and will therefore reduce fuel bills and carbon emissions, they do still require expensive non-renewable fuels and produce greenhouse gases.

7.3.2 Furnaces

Furnaces are very similar to boilers. The main difference is that a furnace uses air, while a boiler uses water to distribute heat throughout your home. In particular, furnaces heat air that is distributed throughout the house via a blower motor and the home's duct system. They can be used for residential and small commercial heating systems. Furnaces use natural gas, fuel oil, and electricity for the heat source. Natural gas furnaces are available in condensing and non-condensing models and they can provide cooling as well.

Since they work moving air, furnaces are more suited for cooling purposes, while a drafty environment is less comfortable for heating. They are less expensive than boilers, but require more maintenance, requiring to change the air filter every 1 to 4 months, in order to have good air quality (Fehr, 2009).

7.3.3 Heat pumps

Heat pumps are devices able to transfer heat from a source at lower temperature to another one at higher temperature, inverting the natural flow of heat. This principle is similar to a water pump that pumps water from a reservoir to another one positioned higher (Robur, n.a.). The heat pump cycle is constituted of four main phases:

- 1) The refrigerant fluid goes from gaseous state to liquid state in the **condenser**, transferring heat to the environment.
- 2) In the **expansion valve** the fluid cool down, partially transforming into vapour.
- 3) In the **evaporator** the refrigerant absorb heat from an external source and completely evaporates.
- 4) The refrigerant fluid at low pressure is forced into high pressure in **compressor** and is heated as a consequence.

Those four phases are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Heat pump cycle scheme

A heat pump is able to reverse the normal heating flow thanks to electric consumption to give power to the compressor. The advantage is that, absorbing heat from external environment (air, water or ground), it is able to generate more energy (heat) than it consumes (electricity). On average, a heat pump can produce 2.5 kWh of energy for any 1 kWh consumed.

The external medium from which heat is drawn is called a cold source. In the heat pump the refrigerant absorbs heat from the cold source by means of the evaporator.

The main cold sources are (heat pump centre, n.a.):

- Air: typically air from the external environment, can be heated thanks to a solar collector

- **Water:** when available, water from rivers and lakes nearby the facility to be heated. Other reservoirs may consist of water which has been specifically accumulated and is usually heated by solar radiation.
- **Ground:** dedicated specific pipes are sunk into the ground at varying depths, usually from 1 to 1.5 meters. Ground has the advantage to maintain a more constant temperature without being influenced by external weather conditions. These pipes constitute a geothermal system.

While the latest gas condensing boilers are ultra-efficient, they depend upon finite fossil fuels. The heat provided by a heat pump is taken directly from the environment, and is therefore 'green'. If the electricity needed for the compressor to work is generated from renewable sources, then a building can be heated entirely renewably and cost effectively.

The main disadvantage with heat pump is that they work best when the difference between the cold source and the building temperature is low. In particular, they are not well suited to be used in particularly cold environment. Heat pumps are also difficult to regulate (Robur, n.a.).

7.3.4 Solar heating

Solar heating and cooling comprises a wide range of technologies, from mature domestic hot water heaters to new technologies, such as solar thermally driven cooling. Nowadays, the majority of applications for solar thermal systems use rooftop glazed and unglazed collectors. The choice of solar thermal collector generally depends on the application and the required temperature. In the building sector, non-concentrating flat-plate and evacuated-tube collectors are most commonly used for space and water heating. The use of solar energy for heat supply is mostly limited to low temperatures processes, such as hot water for sanitarian use. It should be noted that solar thermal combination systems, in which solar technology is combined with an auxiliary heating or cooling source, can be used to increase heating and cooling efficiency in buildings and to supply the demand that is not achieved by the solar thermal system (IEA, 2012d.).

7.3.5 Electric heaters

Electric heating or resistance heating converts electricity directly to heat. Electric heat is often more expensive than heat produced by combustion appliances like natural gas, propane, and oil. Electric resistance heat can be provided by baseboard heaters, space heaters, radiant heaters, furnaces, wall heaters, or thermal storage systems.

Electric heaters are usually part of a fan coil which is part of a central air conditioner. They circulate heat by blowing air across the heating element which is supplied to the furnace through return air ducts. Blowers in electric furnaces move air over one to five resistance coils or elements which are usually rated at five kilowatts. The heating elements activate one at a time to avoid overloading the electrical system. Overheating is prevented by a safety switch called a limit controller or limit switch. This limit controller may shut the furnace off if the blower fails or if something is blocking the air flow. The heated air is then sent back through the home through supply ducts.

7.3.6 KPIs evaluation for building heating

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the building heating technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. Technologies are compared at higher level, leaving a deeper inspection to the analysis performed in the previous sections. The table provides a simple and clear comparison between the technologies, helping the reader to obtain a clear overview of the heating solution proposed in this deliverable.

The main sources that inform Table 19, below, come from the sources cited in the relative sections above.

Table 19: KPIs evaluation for building heating technologies

Theme	Type of indicator	Boilers	Furnaces	Heat pumps	Solar heating	Electric heaters
GHG Emissions	<i>Fuel used</i>	Gas – Oil	Gas – Oil	Electricity	Sunlight	Electricity
Capital investment cost	<i>Installation cost (€)</i>	5.000 - 60.000	1.500 – 5.000	1.500 – 45.000	300 – 1.200 (€/m ²)	200 – 1.000
Performance index	<i>COP</i>	-	-	3 – 4,5	-	-
Technological regime	<i>Combustion efficiency</i>	80-96%	80-96%	-	30%	90%
Technological regime	<i>Lifetime (years)</i>	20-25	20-25	15	25	5-10
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	High	Medium-High	High
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	YES Condens. Boilers $\eta > 93\%$	YES Condens. Furnaces $\eta > 93\%$	YES COP > 4	YES	NO
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	High	High	High	Medium – High	Low - Medium

Boilers and furnaces, the most traditional building heating technologies, generally have the largest market shares.

From a technical point of view, heat pumps can work with high energy efficiency performances, especially in relatively temperate climates. In very cold environment their efficiency decreases, and they need a back-up boiler in order to well work.

The latest technological improvements have made boilers and furnaces more efficient, and their environmental impacts have been mitigated too, thanks to lower emissions from the combustion process.

Solar heating is the least diffused technology, despite it not producing GHG emissions and it being the least harmful to the environment. There are two main reasons for the slow uptake of solar heating technologies.

First, it is the most recent technology and so is the least well known. Second, solar technologies in general have intrinsic limits connected to the working intermittence, as they can only work during the day.

7.4 Ventilating

In order to guarantee adequate comfort to the inhabitants, removing stale interior air and providing oxygen recycle, the role of building ventilation systems is central. There has been considerable concern recently about how much ventilation is required to maintain the quality of air in homes. Too much ventilation will generate energy efficiency problems, making heat escape the building during cold seasons and enter during hot seasons. On the other side, a lack of ventilation will result in lack of oxygen recycling, with a decrease of inhabitants comfort (Fehr, 2009).

While opening and closing windows offers one way to control outside air for ventilation, this strategy is rarely useful on a regular, year-round basis. It becomes necessary to take into account ventilation needs during building design process. The following section presents the main type of integrated building ventilation solutions, each one with their pros and cons.

7.4.1 Natural ventilation

Natural ventilation is to the process of circulating air in an indoor space as a result of pressure differences arising between the inside and the outside of the building, without making use of mechanical systems. Two main types of natural ventilation can be defined: wind driven ventilation and buoyancy-driven ventilation (National Institute of Building Science, n.a.). In wind driven ventilation the difference in inside and outside air pressure is created by wind around the building, while in buoyancy-driven ventilation it's the results of temperature differences between the interior and exterior. The way air is enabled to circulate through the building is simply thanks to purpose-built openings, which can include windows, doors, solar chimneys, wind towers and trickle ventilators (Aereco, n.a.).

In order for natural ventilation to be effective, care must be taken on climate, building design and human behaviour. If well installed and maintained, several advantages can be obtained when compared with mechanical ventilation systems.

In general, the advantage of natural ventilation is its ability to provide a high ventilation rate at low cost, thanks to a very simple and energy efficient system. It is an environmental friendly solution, since it requires no electricity usage and add no polluting gases into the environment. Although the air-change rate can vary significantly depending on the external weather conditions, buildings carefully designed to maximise natural ventilation benefits and properly operated can achieve very high air-change rates by natural forces. Many times natural ventilation alone can guarantee or even exceed the minimum ventilation requirements.

There are, though, some important drawbacks to a natural ventilation system.

First of all, natural ventilation is dependent on outside climatic conditions relative to the indoor environment, making the air flow rate variable and therefore difficult to control. As a consequence, airflow may be uncomfortably high in some locations and stagnant in others during certain unfavourable climate conditions. In some areas it may be important to control the airflow direction, in order to avoid contamination of adjacent corridors and rooms, and natural ventilation cannot provide the required consistent control (VV. AA., 2009b).

Although the maintenance cost of simple natural ventilation systems can be very low, if a natural ventilation system is not designed or installed properly or maintenance level is low, its performance can be compromised. Other possible drawbacks that need to be considered are the possibility of polluted air

entering the building, presence of noise due to the wind, insect vectors and security issues, due to the fact that open access area into the building must be present to let air flow.

These difficulties can be overcome, for example, by using a better design or hybrid ventilation.

7.4.2 Mechanical ventilation

Mechanical ventilation is used for applications where natural ventilation is not appropriate. Air flow is driven by fans, which can either be installed directly in windows or walls, or installed in air ducts for supplying fresh air into, or exhausting air from, a room. Before entering in the building, air is filtered in order to remove particulates and dust from the air (Aereco, n.a.).

Mechanical ventilation can be divided in positive or negative pressure ventilation. In a positive pressure system, the room is in positive pressure and the polluted air is leaked out through an opening. In a negative pressure system, the room is in negative pressure, and fresh air is sucked from the outside. A balanced mechanical ventilation system refers to the system where air supplies and exhausts have been adjusted to maintain either a slightly positive or negative pressure in the room. This is achieved by setting the supply and exhaust ventilation at slightly different rates. A mechanical ventilation system can be combined with all sorts of heating and cooling systems. A common procedure implemented in order to reduce electrical consumption is the extraction of heat from the exhaust air, which is used to preheat the fresh air supply (heat recovery). The scheme is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery scheme (thegreenage.co.uk, 2015)

Mechanical ventilation presents some advantages with respect to natural ventilation. It provides a good control of the ventilation capacity, independent from the outside weather conditions and, as mechanical ventilation can be integrated easily into air-conditioning, the indoor air temperature and humidity can also be controlled (UOL-VENTILATION, n.a.). Control is possible also on air flow direction, which can be very critical in environment such as hospitals, and filtration systems can be installed so that harmful microorganisms, particulates, gases, odours and vapours can be removed (VV. AA., 2009b). Finally, mechanical ventilation can work everywhere when electricity is available.

However, mechanical ventilation also presents some critical problems. Equipment may not always work as expected, and when a failure occurs, normal operation may need to be interrupted for the time needed for reparations. If the system services a critical facility, and there is a need for continuous operation, all the equipment may have to be backed up, which can be expensive and unsustainable.

Installation and maintenance costs for the operation of a mechanical ventilation system are higher than those needed for natural ventilation, and may constitute a problem, especially in private houses (The Green Age,n.a.).

7.4.3 Hybrid ventilation

Hybrid ventilation is the ideal solution when the environmental and energy saving benefits of natural ventilation are required, but where for some reasons is not possible to adopt a fully passive system. The reasons for this impossibility may be various, such as a building surrounded by taller structures or sited where there is unlikely to be sufficient wind. In a hybrid system an intermittent fan, which is controlled by a temperature sensor, pressure controller or wind gauge, is activated when the air flow rate provided by natural ventilation alone is not sufficient.

Hybrid ventilation has the advantages of natural ventilation, such as easy maintenance, low-energy use and CO₂ emissions, combined with the ones of mechanical ventilation, such as reliability, flexibility and increased control possibilities. Hybrid ventilation can bring an important reduction of annual energy use, with an important part of this reduction due to reduced night cooling of the building, which is excessive with natural solutions only. Night ventilation is enhanced by mechanical systems, while natural systems are preferred during the day.

However, this system presents some drawbacks as well and needs to be used and implemented with care. The fans should be installed either on a wall or the roof, so that air can be exhausted directly to the outdoor environment. The size and number of exhaust fans depends on the targeted ventilation rate, and must be measured and tested before use (Aereco, n.a.).

Problems associated with the use of exhaust fans include installation difficulties (especially for large fans), noise (particularly from high-power fans), increased or decreased temperature in the room and the requirement for non-stop electricity supply.

7.4.4 KPIs evaluation for ventilating solutions

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the building ventilating solutions introduced in the previous section is proposed. The high level comparison performed in the previous section between natural, Mechanical and hybrid ventilation is proposed again here in the table. It follows that the KPIs are described mainly by qualitative parameters. The main sources that inform Table 20, below, come from Aereco (n.a.).

Table 20: KPIs evaluation for ventilating solutions

Theme	Type of indicator	Natural ventilation	Hybrid ventilation	Mechanical ventilation
Environmental impact	Type	None	Electricity consumption	Electricity consumption
Environmental impact	Level	-	Medium	High
Capital investment cost	Installation cost	Low	Medium	High
Capital investment cost	Savings on heat losses	Low	Low-Medium	High
Technological regime	Ventilation flow Control	Low	Medium	High
Technological regime	Maturity of technology	High	High	High

Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	European Directive 2012/27EU on Energy efficiency		
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	High	Medium – High	Medium

Natural ventilation is the most commonly implemented, especially in older buildings. It does not have any impact on the environment since it does not need any fuel or electricity, but it provides a very low control on the ventilation flow. For this reason, mechanical ventilation is growing in popularity and not only in commercial buildings, since it allows a greater comfort to the users than natural ventilation.

Hybrid ventilation comprehends both natural and mechanical ventilation. It provides more control on the ventilation flow, but the openings in the building necessary for natural ventilation still make not possible to have the level of control of mechanical ventilation. Having a constant air exchange with the outside, natural and hybrid ventilation lose again when taking into account heat losses.

7.5 Air conditioning

Air conditioning systems have an important role in comfort control of building inhabitants, undertaking the same function of heating technologies, but opposite in heat exchange direction. It is worth noting, though, how building heating is considered essential and is present in basically all buildings, while air conditioning is still viewed as a luxury in many areas of Europe, especially for residential buildings. The situation improves when considering public buildings (e.g. hospitals) or industrial workplaces and buildings with heavy computer equipment presence (European Commission, 2012a). With the raising of temperature during summer in Europe and the increased concern for environmental issues, energy efficient air conditioning system may see a higher implementation in building design or during retrofitting solutions in next years.

The following section presents the main air conditioning technologies present on the market today.

7.5.1 Chillers

In large commercial and institutional buildings, devices used to produce cool water are called chillers. A chiller is a vapour compression mechanical refrigeration system that cool down the building or process water extracting its heat in a device called evaporator. As the heat transfer between the warm water and the cold refrigerator takes place, the refrigerator evaporates, changing its state into vapour, while the water is cooled and inserted into the process. From the evaporator, the refrigerant moves into the compressor, where it is compressed in order to raise its temperature. When the now high-pressure and high-temperature refrigerant reaches the condenser, it releases its heat, returning to liquid state. Liquid refrigerant passes through an expansion valve and returns to low-pressure before entering again in the evaporator (Miller, 2010). Figure 18 give a schematic view of this process.

Figure 18: Chiller process schematic view (achrnews.com, 2007)

The heat exchange in the condenser can be performed through water or air. This defines the two main different types of chillers (Miller, 2010):

- **Air-cooled chillers:** Air is forced through the condenser with a motorised blower. Heat exchange is increased using a grid of refrigerant lines. Unless when specially designed for high-ambient conditions, air-cooled chillers need outdoor temperatures below 35°C to work efficiently. They are offered on smaller, packaged systems (typically from less than one ton to 120 tons). They are initially less costly than water-cooled condensers, because they require fewer components to operate, but do not allow the chiller to operate as efficiently. Air-cooled chillers Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) can usually range from 2.5 to 4.5.
- **Water-cooled chillers:** The principle is the same as air-cooled chillers, but they require one more step to complete heat transfer. First, the condenser water absorbs the refrigerant vapor heat, condensing it. Then the now warm condenser water is pumped to a cooling tower where the

process heat is finally discharged into the environment. The lower temperature achieved by evaporating water allows chillers served by water-cooled condensers to operate more efficiently. The condenser operation costs of a cooling tower are lower than the ones needed to operate the electrically driven fan used on an air-cooled system. Moreover, when the outdoor air temperature is sufficiently low and/or the air is very dry, the temperature of the cooling tower water may be low enough to directly cool the chilled water loop without use of the chiller, resulting in significant energy savings (waterside economiser). Water-cooled chillers EER can usually range between 4 and 6.3.

Chillers use either mechanical refrigeration processes or absorption processes (Chen, Chi et Yan, 2009).

7.5.1.1 **Mechanical refrigeration chillers**

Mechanical refrigeration chillers may have one or more compressors. These compressors can be powered by electric motors, fossil fuel engines, or turbines. Refrigeration systems achieve variable capacity by bringing compressors on or off line, by unloading stages within the compressors, or by varying the speed of the compressor.

7.5.1.2 **Absorption chillers**

Absorption chillers are heat-operated devices that produce chilled water via an absorption cycle. Absorption chillers can be direct-fired, using natural gas or fuel oil, or indirect-fired. Indirect-fired units may use different sources for heat: hot water or steam from a boiler, steam from district heating, or waste heat in the form of water, air, or other gas. Absorption chillers can be single-effect or double-effect, where one or two vapor generators are used. Double-effect chillers use two generators sequentially to increase efficiency. Several manufacturers offer absorption chiller/heater units, which use the heat produced by firing to provide space heating and service hot water.

7.5.1.3 **Evaporative coolers**

Evaporative coolers, also called swamp coolers, are packaged units that cool the air by humidifying it and then evaporating the moisture. The equipment is most effective in dry climates. It can significantly reduce the peak electric demand when compared to electric chillers.

7.5.2 **Variable refrigerant flow (VRF)**

The term “variable refrigerant flow” refers to the ability of the system to control the amount of refrigerant flowing to each of the evaporators, enabling the use of many evaporators of differing capacities and configurations, individualised comfort control, simultaneous heating and cooling in different zones, and heat recovery from one zone to another. This refrigerant flow control lies at the heart of VRF systems and is the major technical challenge as well as the source of many of the system’s advantages.

For buildings requiring simultaneous heating and cooling, heat recovery VRF systems can be used. These systems circulate refrigerant between zones, transferring heat from the indoor units of zones being cooled to those of zones being heated (VV. AA., 2010).

VRF systems have several key benefits, including (Goetzler, 2007):

- Installation advantages: chillers often require cranes for installation, but VRF systems are lightweight and modular. Each module can be transported easily and fits into a standard elevator. Multiples of these modules can be used to achieve cooling capacities of hundreds of tons. Each module (or set of two) is an independent refrigerant loop, they are usually controlled by a common control system, but independent control is possible as well.
- Maintenance and commissioning: VRF systems with their standardised configurations and sophisticated electronic controls are aiming toward near plug-and-play commissioning. Because

they are DX systems, maintenance costs for a VRF should be lower than for water-cooled chillers. However, chillers, which often operate for 20 to 30 years, normally would be anticipated to have a longer life expectancy than a DX system such as a VRF. The large number of compressors in a VRF may create a higher probability of compressor failure, although the redundancy also leads to a greater ability to continue to occupy the space while repairs are in progress.

Total installed costs for VRF systems are estimated by some sources to be 5% to 20% higher than for chilled water systems providing equivalent capacity, but actual costs are highly project dependent.

On the other hand, VRF systems have higher efficiencies, with energy savings of 30% to 40% compared to the chillers (Goetzler, 2007).

VRF systems are generally best suited to buildings with diverse, multiple zones requiring individual control, such as office buildings, hospitals, or hotels.

The main disadvantages of VRF systems include (Goetzler, 2007):

- The efficiency drops off considerably at low temperatures, so they are less cost effective compared to gas heating in very cold climates.
- Lack of awareness of energy efficiency advantages: most industry professionals refer only to EER or kW/ton ratings when considering efficiency. The more subtle energy efficiency advantages of VRF systems, such as the reduction in duct losses, the ease of electrical sub-metering, and even the higher part load efficiency, frequently are overlooked.
- Initial cost: In many cases, the initial cost of a VRF system is higher if compared to a chilled water system. While a VRF may be cost competitive for new construction, in a chiller replacement situation with existing water piping, replacing the chiller would normally be less expensive than installing a VRF.

7.5.3 KPIs evaluation for air conditioning technologies

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the building air conditioning technologies introduced in the previous section is proposed. The two main technologies presented in this section, chillers and VRF, are compared in the table, in order to provide a simple and clear understanding of each one pros and cons.

The main sources that inform Table 21, below, come from the sources cited in the relative sections above.

Table 21: KPIs evaluation for air conditioning technologies

Theme	Type of indicator	Chillers	VRF
GHG Emissions	<i>Type of fuel</i>	Electricity	Electricity
Environmental impact	<i>Type</i>	Refrigerant emission in the environment	Refrigerant emission in the environment
Environmental impact	<i>Level</i>	Medium-High	Medium-High
Capital investment cost	<i>Installation cost</i>	8.000 – 20.000	600 – 9.000

Theme	Type of indicator	Chillers	VRF
Performance index	EER	3.2 – 5	3 – 4.8
Technological regime	Lifetime (years)	30	10-15
Technological regime	Maturity of technology	High	High
Political commitment	Available Grants & Policy support	Yes EER > 3.4	Yes EER > 3.4
Public opinion	Degree of acceptance of the technology	Medium – High	Medium

Chillers are the more popular solution for building air conditioning, as they are the older technology. Except for that, the two technologies are quite comparable and the user choice between the two is highly dependent on the building characteristics. Chillers are usually better suited for bigger installation and where available space is not an issue. VRVs, on the other side, have high modularity and they can be used for small installations such as an individual apartment or for a whole building, connecting multiple unities. Possibilities and performances are similar, with VRVs having usually a little higher investment cost than chillers when considering the same power capacity.

Given the lower weight and simpler installation process, VRVs have higher possibilities when retrofitting old buildings, and are thus increasing their market share.

7.6 Building monitoring, automation and control

As technology is developing, building monitoring, automation and control is assuming a increasingly important role in the energy efficiency of industrial, public and residential buildings. The use of sensors to control the building energy performances and the possibility to automatically manage the building energy usage and correct detected faults, can produce a much higher comfort for building inhabitants, reducing at the same time the energy consumption.

The following sections will first detail the main parameters that need to be considered to guarantee people comfort inside the building and which sensors are used to control those parameters. Secondly, the main solution in the field of building automation and control system are discussed.

7.6.1 Comfort indoor and air quality

The term ‘comfort’ might be used to describe a feeling of contentment, a sense of easiness and a state of physical and mental well-being. Indoor environmental quality (IEQ) refers to the quality of a building’s environment in relation to the comfort of those who occupy space within it. IEQ is determined by several factors, including lighting, air quality, and damp conditions (Chappells & Shove, 2004). As proposed in the ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55-2004, building managers and operators can increase the satisfaction of building occupants by considering all of the aspects of IEQ rather than narrowly focusing on temperature or air quality alone.

Below a list of factors that contribute to define comfort levels, and how to control them.

7.6.1.1 **Temperature**

Thermal comfort is the condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment and is assessed by subjective evaluation ASHRAE Standard 55.

The main factors that influence thermal comfort are those that determine heat gain and loss, namely metabolic rate, clothing insulation, air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air speed and relative humidity. Psychological parameters such as individual expectations also affect thermal comfort.

Sensors which detect temperature or heat are currently the most commonly used ones in building. These types of temperature sensor vary from simple ON/OFF thermostatic devices, which control a domestic hot water heating system, to highly sensitive semiconductor types that can control more complex furnace plants.

Two main types of temperature sensors can be defined:

- **Contact Temperature Sensor:** These types of temperature sensor are required to be in physical contact with the heat source and use conduction to monitor changes in temperature. They can be used to detect solids, liquids or gases over a wide range of temperatures.
- **Non-contact Temperature Sensor:** These types of temperature sensor use convection and radiation to monitor changes in temperature. They can be used to detect liquids and gases that emit radiant energy as heat rises and cold settles to the bottom in convection currents or detect the radiant energy being transmitted from an object in the form of infra-red radiation.

7.6.1.2 **Humidity**

Human comfort depends on a complex interaction of multiple variables with humidity being only one of them. However, optimising both temperature and relative humidity satisfies the comfort requirements for a wider variety of occupants as opposed to regulating temperature only.

The ASHRAE standard 55 specifies that to decrease the possibility of discomfort due to low or high humidity, its level has to be maintained between 30% and 70% relative humidity at 21°C. The Health and Safety Executive in the United Kingdom recommends relative humidity in the range of 40% to 70% in the workplace environment.

Humidity sensors are employed to provide an indication of the moisture levels in the environment. A humidity sensor, also called a hygrometer, measures and regularly reports the relative humidity in the air. Relative humidity, expressed as a percent, is the ratio of actual moisture in the air to the highest amount of moisture air at that temperature can hold. The warmer the air is, the more moisture it can hold, so relative humidity changes with fluctuations in temperature.

The most common type of humidity sensor uses what is called “capacitive measurement.” This system relies on electrical capacitance, or the ability of two nearby electrical conductors to create an electrical field between them, and measure the changes in the voltage due to variations in moisture level.

Humidity sensors can be connected to the mechanical ventilation system, in order to regulate and control the characteristics and parameters of the fresh air introduced into the room. Commercial and office buildings often have humidity sensors in their HVAC systems, which help to ensure safe air quality, while they are less commonly used in residential buildings. Many times, humidity and temperature sensors are sold together.

7.6.1.3 **Air quality**

Indoor air quality is not easily defined. It is a constantly changing interaction of complex factors related to the types, levels and importance of pollutants in indoor environments. The sources of pollutants need to be

managed, either by removing them from the building or isolating them from people through physical barriers, air pressure differences, or by controlling the timing of their use. In this process, filtering of the polluted air is an essential step. Mechanical ventilation is a more suitable option than natural ventilation, since provide a better control of air flow direction and intensity, providing a higher air quality level.

In order to provide adequate ventilation for occupied spaces, monitoring systems can be installed to generate alarms when unhealthy levels of carbon dioxide are detected and fresh air needs to be brought in to restore healthy indoor air quality.

A CO₂ sensor is an instrument for the measurement of carbon dioxide level in indoor air. The most common principles for CO₂ sensors are infrared gas sensors and chemical gas sensors. New developments include using microelectromechanical system to bring down the costs of this sensor and to create smaller devices (for example for use in air conditioning applications).

Nowadays, mechanical ventilation is present almost solely in commercial buildings and, even there, CO₂ sensors are rarely found.

7.6.2 Building Automation and Control Systems

The goal of building operation is to achieve optimal occupant comfort with the least amount of energy consumption. Buildings that achieve this balance do so by addressing the two main elements of building performance:

- 1) *System Tracking* for HVAC and lighting systems. In a typical large commercial building, this information will be accessible via the BAS.
- 2) *Energy Tracking* for the whole building, accessed through monthly utility bills and given valuable context through benchmarking.

Building owners should address both sides of the coin to reap the full rewards of tracking building performance, since each side can answer different questions about building operation.

The two approaches can be divided in three different levels of complexity, detail and automation as shown in Figure 19. Higher levels tools can overcome the limits of the lower level ones, but cannot work optimally, if not work at all, without their presence (Portland Energy Conservation, 2011).

Figure 19: HVAC control systems typologies (Portland Energy Conservation, 2011)

7.6.2.1 **Energy Tracking**

7.6.2.1.1 Energy Benchmarking

Energy benchmarking is a strategy for checking a whole building energy consumption and comparing its energy performance either to peer groups or to historical performance. It has increasingly become the norm for commercial building owners, who appreciate the value of the data and ease-of-use of the tools. These tools not only benchmark performance at a point in time, but also indicate when performance improves or degrades over a longer period. They automatically generate clear performance tables and give the possibility to the user to set targets and check progresses. Several online resources are available to help with building benchmarking.

7.6.2.1.2 Energy Information System (EIS)

Energy information systems (EIS) are used to store, analyse and display current and historical energy use, typically displaying hour-by-hour data for each meter. EIS provide the capability for the user to analyse energy consumption patterns using a variety of graphical formats. This hourly tracking enables system improvements to be viewed at the meter level and problems to be more easily and quickly identified. Data collected by sensors are collected, analysed and archived into the EIS server and the user can access them in a variety of formats on a web interface.

EIS help find and fix problems faster and are a useful tool to check the results of efficiency investment. The limits of this level of tools is that they provide a view on how the building behaved, but any on how it should behave. This issue is fixed with the introduction of Advanced EIS.

7.6.2.1.3 Advanced EIS

Advanced EIS include the same features of EIS, adding a new level of features and possibilities. They can track and graphical display hourly energy use, taking into account many variables that affect the energy use: outside air temperature, day type (weekend/weekday or day of the week), and hour-of-day are typical, but other variables such as building occupancy levels may also be used.

In addition, these systems incorporate sophisticated energy modelling functionality that can, over a period of many months to one year, develop a model to predict expected energy use based on a number of variables, and alert the user if energy use exceeds that prediction. A comparison of 'typical vs. actual' energy use can then be used to automatically generate alerts when differences occur.

7.6.2.2 **System Tracking**

7.6.2.2.1 Building Automation System (BAS)

Most large buildings use a BAS to control a building's Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning (HVAC) and lighting systems. BAS can vary widely in capabilities and configuration, but on the basic level, they contain an instantaneous display of the building's current operation, including data readings from hundreds or thousands of data points from HVAC and lighting systems, along with the programming necessary to control system operation.

The BAS plays a key role in all building performance-tracking strategies, because it can be used for troubleshooting system performance problems. Using the BAS as a performance tracking tool begins with trend logging to record the performance of systems under various modes and operating conditions over time. Archiving the trended data is a key step in making sure the data is preserved. In addition to trends, BAS alarms can be configured to expose a system fault, a problem relating to occupant comfort, or an occupant-driven change with a damaging impact on energy. Typical BAS alarms will signal when a data

point is outside of a predetermined threshold. All BAS have inherent alarm capabilities that do not require custom programming by a controls contractor.

After discovering performance problems, either through trend logs and BAS alarms or any other performance tracking tool, the next step is to find the specific problem, including its root cause. All performance tracking tools require operators to use the BAS to diagnose problems, even if those tools can automatically detect faults.

After fixing performance issues, the BAS can be used to verify that performance has improved by observing data at the operator workstation and reviewing trends. This step assures operators that the problem has been fixed and often involves tweaking operating parameters to optimise the improvements rather than overriding them entirely. Also, BAS alarm thresholds may need to be revised based on the new operating conditions of the equipment.

7.6.2.2.2 BAS Metrics

Using the BAS to track key performance metrics can be an effective and inexpensive way to boil down the thousands of data points that may be tracked into more user friendly information. The BAS can track thousands of points within a building; the distinction with a metric is that the second one combines data from multiple points to provide deeper meaning. This minimises daily labour resources required and provides a way to track long term building performance improvements.

For example, tracking zone temperatures is important for ensuring comfort, but reviewing temperatures in every zone is difficult to manage long-term. Tracking a metric such as the percent of time when zones are within set values can be useful for assessing performance at a glance and for tracking improvement or degradation over time.

Most BAS have the capability to track energy-related metrics, as long as meter data can be input to the BAS, sometimes requiring the addition of new sensors.

Some of the most recommended BAS metric are, for example, Occupant Comfort Index, Cooling/Heating Plant Efficiency, Fan System Efficiency, Outside Air Ventilation.

Metric tracking minimises daily labour resources required and provides an easy way to track long term improvements on a monthly or annual basis. Adding this functionality to an already-familiar BAS tool should minimise the additional effort required for operators to track metrics.

Tracking a comfort-related metric is particularly useful, and make possible to identify problems before any occupant complaints are reported.

The limits of this approach are that in most of the cases metrics are building specific. A good knowledge of the building is required in order to understand what the normal behaviour of the measured metrics is. Moreover, these tools still lack a diagnosis ability, which is introduced only in FDD.

7.6.2.2.3 Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD)

FDD tools utilise system-level performance data to automatically detect problems. Some tools additionally provide diagnostics to help determine the root cause of the problem.

FDD tools rely on BAS data with a few tools requiring the installation of dedicated sensors external to the BAS. They may include a single system, such as an air handler or multiple systems throughout the facility such as air-handlers, pumps, chillers, boilers, etc.

Problems are typically detected using the following techniques:

- Expert rules mimic the thinking of a systems expert to compare multiple data points. In many cases, the expert use “if-then” rules, to check the system operation relative to known or expected operation.
- Performance data comparisons evaluate monitored BAS data against certain parameters, such as design intent, manufacturers’ equipment ratings, and historical trend data. A model of expected performance is created and is then compared to the actual performance values.

In addition to indicating problems, expert rules can account for the duration or cumulative cost impact of a particular problem, assigning a priority level consequently.

Some tools only pinpoint the location of the fault without providing specific causes, while others may issue a report with diagnostic possibilities for corrective action. In either case, additional manual inspection or further analysis may be required.

7.6.3 KPIs evaluation for building automation and control systems

In the following table, the main parameters for a brief multi-level comparison between the building automation and control systems introduced in the previous section is proposed. It helps giving a clear and simple understanding of each technology strength and weakness towards a low carbon future.

The main sources that inform Table 22, below, come from Portland Energy Conservation (2011) and VV.AA. (2010).

Table 22: KPIs evaluation for building automation and control systems

Theme	Type of indicator	Energy Benchmarking	EIS	Advanced EIS	BAS	BAS Metrics	FDD
Capital investment cost	<i>Average market price</i>	Low	Medium	Medium – High	Medium	Low - Medium	High
Capital investment cost	<i>Average annual energy savings*</i>	n.a.	n.a.	10-30%	n.a.	n.a.	10-30%
Technological regime	<i>Operation</i>	Tracks energy consumption	Tracks and save energy consumption	Data-based building model (Typical vs Actual)	Error detection	Provide a tool for fault diagnosis	Automatic Error detection and diagnosis
Technological regime	<i>Control</i>	Semi-Automatic	Semi-Automatic	Automatic	Semi-Automatic	Semi-Automatic	Automatic
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	Medium-High	Medium-High	Medium	Medium-High	Medium-High	Medium
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	European Directive 2012/27EU on Energy efficiency					
Public opinion	<i>Degree of acceptance of the technology</i>	Medium – High	Medium	Low – Medium	Medium – High	Medium –High	Low - Medium

* Compared to building without any building automation and control solution

Multiple different solutions exist on the market when referring to Building Automation and Control Systems. The more advanced is the tool the more functionalities it provides, increasing the level of automation and the possibilities of control on the building energetic performances. The price follows this evolution, with higher cost for more advanced and complete tools, with FDD usually having higher cost than Advanced EIS.

Overall, those tools are mainly implemented in commercial buildings and are seeing an increase in their market share. No specific policy is defined for implementing BACS systems at European level, but they are considered as measures to improve building efficiency and available grants and support depends on the efficiency level they allow the building to reach.

Comparing the different solution proposed, there is no real preference between Advanced EIS and FDD, as they serve different purpose. To obtain the best possible level of building control and automation, it is highly advisable to implement both solution together.

7.7 Transport

Transport is a very indicating sector in an energy and environmental impact analysis, since its energy demand is near one quarter of the total energy consumption worldwide, with huge effects on our society carbon footprint, CO₂ and other GHG emissions. In particular, private transport sector (i.e., the methods to move people by using their own relatively little sized vehicles like cars or motorcycles).

In this section, several different private transport methods are analysed and compared in an end-user perspective, with the main focus on the different propulsion methods like the traditional carbon-based ones (i.e., gasoline and diesel cars) and the innovative solutions based on less CO₂ emitting electric propulsion (hybrid and full hybrid cars).

In particular, their technical features are investigated with main reference to a general performance evaluation of their energy demand, environmental impact and social acceptance by mean of the KPIs set defined in Chapter 3.

In order to perform this assessment, the mainly used private transport technologies are taken into account: gasoline, diesel, hybrid and electric cars.

7.7.1 Private transport vehicles

7.7.1.1 Gasoline

With its 130 years history, gasoline vehicles represent the most mature private people transport technology in the current scenario. At the time being, this is one of the most adopted methods and the gasoline cars market is still large (in 2013, about 45% of new registered cars was represented by gasoline cars), even if the new diffused environmental concerns are pushing towards most innovative and energy effective vehicles.

Indeed, the main disadvantage is the high CO₂ emissions of this propulsion method, if compared to other engines like diesel or electric ones. With an average gasoline consumption of 6.3 l/100 km for gasoline cars, these vehicles emit in the atmosphere about 150 g_{CO2}/km.

In order to reduce the carbon footprint due to the private transport sector, some European Member States have created tax incentives to promote switching to less CO₂ intensive technologies, like hybrid vehicles.

Due to the lower price of a gasoline car compared to the diesel-propelled version of the same model, often people still purchase a gasoline one in spite of the higher carbon footprint. This is especially true in the segment of small vehicles and city cars, which are not aimed at being driven for many kilometres per year.

7.7.1.2 **Diesel**

Diesel propulsion vehicles appeared in 1930s, which makes it a very mature technology with a long worldwide history. This is the most used car technology currently in Europe: according to year 2013 market data, 53% of the purchased private cars had diesel engine (ICCT, 2014). This is due to the lower mean fuel consumption of this kind of vehicles if compared to the same class gasoline-propelled cars, this making it cheaper driving such a vehicle.

In fact, the mean fuel consumption for diesel cars is around 3.8 l/ 100 km: further the obvious economic advantages, diesel engines are less emitting than gasoline ones, with a CO₂ production close to 100 gCO₂/km.

So, both for economy and environment reasons, diesel cars tend to be preferred in the big vehicles segment, even if their purchasing prices are higher.

7.7.1.3 **Hybrid**

In contrast to previously described internal combustion cars, hybrid vehicles use two or more combined propulsion method in order to achieve an optimised energy efficiency. In this section, hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) are taken into consideration, using an internal combustion engine (gasoline or diesel engine) and an electric motor fed by a battery set. The electric motor shares the load with the internal combustion engine, which can be optimally sized for fuel efficiency and clean burning (i.e., a low cylinder capacity can be adopted for these engines).

Different typologies of hybrid vehicle working can be defined: full hybrids, mild hybrids and plug-in hybrids (Cobb 2014).

Full hybrid vehicles represent the most fuel efficient variety of hybrids. Their peculiarity is the ability to automatically choose the propulsion mode between series, parallel and all-electric mode, which are following explained.

The series mode uses the internal combustion engine as an on-board generator to feed the electric motor, driving the wheels. In parallel mode, both the engines (fuel-based and electric) cooperate to move the wheels. In particular regimes, such as low speeds, when low energy amount is required, the battery set and electric motor can drive the vehicle without the help of the combustion engine, in a pure electric mode.

Mild hybrids are limited to parallel mode: the vehicle never can be driven without the internal combustion engine propulsion. In this case, the electric motor works as a helper motor.

Plug-in hybrid cars can be directly plugged into the electricity grid, and they have larger batteries when compared to other hybrid typologies, giving these kind of vehicle autonomies up to 60 km in the full electric mode. When driven by fuel and electric motors together, they can work both in series and parallel mode.

Today, hybrid private vehicles diffusion is not so wide, but is growing thanks to public environmental concerns and their lower GHG emissions when compared to traditional fuel-based cars. Referring to the European market share, only 1.4% of purchased vehicles was hybrid during 2013 (ICCT, 2014).

On the other hand, some EU Member States like Netherlands are proposing tax incentives for people purchasing a hybrid vehicle, this putting these countries much above the European average referring to the new hybrid cars registrations (10% of the total car market share in 2013).

7.7.1.4 **Electric**

Electric vehicles (EV) are vehicles propelled only by one or more electric motors, which are fed by a battery set. In the case of plug-in electric vehicles (PEV), any external electricity source can be used to recharge the batteries.

The main advantages of this kind of private vehicles are the low carbon footprint (the electric motor is more efficient than internal combustion one, and it does not produce GHG where it is used) and the low energy costs if compared to the traditional cars.

One of the drawbacks which are still restraining people from switching to full electric private transport is the performance (maximum speeds of these vehicles are generally lower than traditional cars, thus meaning electric cars are not as suitable for long distances).

Another problem which electric cars drivers have to face with is range, which is short (batteries can give power to the electric motor for maximum routes of 240 km) and unstable (external temperatures, with subsequent use of heating or air conditioning, can strongly affect real range values).

With a European market share of 0.4% in 2013 electric vehicles are the least popular vehicle type, they also represent the newest private transport technology (ICCT, 2014).

From an environmental point of view, these vehicles are theoretically zero-emitting if we consider the place and the moment in which they are used. Nevertheless, electricity production is not a zero-emitting process, nor is the manufacturing processes required to make the vehicles themselves. Therefore, we must consider these factors along with impact of associated pollution levels taken on a worldwide scale.

In particular, if we consider an electricity absorption of 13kWh/100km for this type of car, and an average European CO₂ emission of 500 gCO₂/kWh, the real emissions for these vehicles are 65gCO₂/km. This estimation still makes electric cars the cleanest option in the private transport scenario.

7.7.2 KPIs evaluation for private transport vehicles

In Table 23, below, the main KPIs for a technical, economic and environmental comparison between the different analysed technologies for private transport are shown. These parameters help a categorisation of the different vehicles typologies, which are described in the sections above.

The main sources used in this table come from the same references quoted in each specific technology section, in addition to a number of car manufacturers technical data such as Ford Focus 1.5 and 1.6, Lexus (2016), Renault (2016). Moreover, data was also taken from the ACEA (2015).

Table 23: KPIs evaluation for private transport vehicles

Theme	Type of indicator	Gasoline	Diesel	Hybrid	Electric
Polluting gas emissions	<i>gCO₂/distance</i>	150 g/km	100 g/km	82 g/km	0 g/km (65 g/km considering electricity production)
Capital investment cost	<i>Technology price</i>	20,000 € Error! Bookmark not defined.	21,000 € Error! Bookmark not defined.	28,000 € Error! Bookmark not defined.	22,000 €
Capital investment cost	<i>Fuel cost</i>	1.26 €/l	1.08 €/l	1.26 €/l	0.22 €/kWh

Theme	Type of indicator	Gasoline	Diesel	Hybrid	Electric
Performance index	<i>Consumption</i>	6.3 l/100 km Error! Bookmark not defined.	3.8 l/100 km Error! Bookmark not defined.	3.6 l/100 km Error! Bookmark not defined.	13 kWh/100 km Error! Bookmark not defined.
Technological regime	<i>Lifespan</i>	300.000 km	300.000 km	240.000 km	200.000 km
Technological regime	<i>Maturity of technology</i>	High	High	Medium-High	Low-Medium
Political commitment	<i>Available Grants & Policy support</i>	-	-	Tax exemptions in some EU Member States	Research supported in FP7 Tax exemptions in some EU Member States
Public opinion	<i>Market share - market increase</i>	45% (-5% since 2009 to 2012)	53% (+8% since 2009 to 2012)	1.4% increasing	0.4% increasing

Analysing the data in the above table, we can see the increasing energy efficiency of each of the proposed transport technologies, starting from the most traditional fuel-based propulsion engines and moving towards the innovative hybrid and electric vehicles. These are framed both in terms of an economical point of view and the relative cost-effectiveness of driving a vehicle increases as we move towards electric models.

Moreover, as shown in Table 23, hybrid and electric vehicles have lower carbon footprint if compared to traditional internal combustion-propelled cars. On the other hand, they still have a little market share due to their short technological maturity, and the lifespan of a single electric motor-driven vehicle is shorter than other ones. The main reason for this shorter lifespan is the battery wear, which cannot be longer than 200.000 km at the state of the art.

Hybrid cars, thanks to the load sharing between electric motor and combustion engine, have the advantage of a longer lifespan if compared to pure electrics.

8 Conclusion and synthesis

The goal of T2.2 has been to provide a technological characterisation of the European energy system, following the energy supply chain, and augmenting the information captured during earlier tasks involving the various the stakeholders and the actor-network approaches. In doing so, the four main stages of the supply chain have been analysed and the main technological driving forces for each one of them has been presented. An extensive data gathering exercise was conducted to develop a clear view of each technology considered and to provide a simple but complete description. Moreover, the reviewed technologies have been grouped into similarly based categories, and a set of specific Key Performance Indicators have been defined for each category in order to compare them and provide a clearer view of the strengths and weaknesses of each technological option as we move towards a low-carbon energy system.

Merging together the information gathered during both Task 2.1 and Task 2.2, it is clear how complex and variegated the energy system is and how many factors have to be taken into account when describing it. In this particular document it is possible to gain an understanding of how the energy system has changed over the course of the past few decades, changes that have been informed by growing concerns over environmental issues and the awareness that the current situation is no longer sustainable. The traditional system, characterised by highly-centralised energy production models and by the extensive use of fossil fuels, remains dominant but important steps are being done towards a growing exploitation of clean and renewable energies. Many different solutions are already available in the market and are being successfully implemented. This is the case for wind and solar, which have seen the most important growth in the last ten years, due to their contributions in reducing GHG emissions, technology readiness and modularity. They may also prove to be a good solution for both small and plant-sized installations for highly-developed, urbanised areas and in more rural areas with limited access to the national grid.

The improvements that have been made to the energy system, though, have not been solely restricted to the implementation of new green technologies as a replacement for traditional fossil fuelled ones. What is shaping its future is around Distributed Generation, with stronger interconnections between big power and heat plants and building individual solutions, with the potential for a two-way flow of energy based on the energy demand variations during the day and on the peak-load periods associated with renewable energies. The electrical grid needs to be amplified and upgraded to sustain frequent changes in electricity direction and power levels. Natural gas pipelines will also see a similar processes of development to allow for changes in gas flow direction during particularly cold winters. Storage is becoming increasingly important due to the variable nature of the renewable energies such as wind and solar, in order to store energy during peak-load periods and use it back when most needed.

It has also shown the importance of solutions that provide electricity and heat at the same time. Combined heat and power plants can greatly improve efficiency with respect to traditional power-only plants, where a lot of process heat is wasted. The use of district heating, in combination with CHP plants, is an extremely efficient solution especially when the CHP plant is fired from renewable energies such as biomass or municipal waste, and is a solution that has been much encouraged by the EU. This despite this emphasis at the supranational level, district heating remains largely confined to Northern and Eastern regions of Europe.

Another relevant point to note is the need of greater efficiency, not only in terms of energy generation, but also in energy final use. This one of the three key targets of the Europe 2020 strategy, with a proposed 20% improvement in energy efficiency. This document also reviewed different solutions for automation and control of lighting and HVAC, with a discussion on their importance in both energy saving opportunities and provided comfort to people.

Overall, this document has provided an extensive overview of the technologies contributing to energy supply system, constituting a further step in the framework set out for the ENTRUST project. The information collected in both Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 shows us how the shift towards a carbon-free energy system is wholly necessary, but still remains far from a complete in terms of implementation. Renewable energy technologies and efficiency measures are being continually being introduced and existing technologies are undergoing rapid evolution. However, at least for the near future, traditional fossil fuel technologies will continue to be needed if we are to provide a secure and stable energy system throughout the European Union.

9 Bibliography

- ACEA. (2015). Overview of purchase and tax incentives for electric vehicles in the EU in 2015. [Online] Available at: https://www.acea.be/uploads/publications/Electric_vehicles_overview_2015.pdf [Accessed: 15/11/2015].
- AEG Power solutions. (2016). Battery Energy Storage for Grid Stabilization. [Online] Available at: <https://www.aegps.com/en/applications/storage-distribution/battery-energy-storage/> [Accessed 14/11/15].
- Aereco. (2016). Ventilation techniques. [Online] Available at: <http://www.aereco.co.uk/ventilation-techniques> [Accessed: 15/11/2015].
- Altenergymag. (2007). Natural Gas hydrates and their Potentiality for Future energy supply. [Online] Available at: <http://www.altenergymag.com/article/2007/06/natural-gas-hydrates-and-their-potentialityfor-future-energy-supply/331/> [Accessed: 10/11/2015].
- ANSI/ASHRAE. (2004). Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy. Atlanta, USA: ASHRAE Standard.
- Association for Decentralised Energy. (2016). Policies and incentives. [Online] Available at: http://www.theade.co.uk/policies-and-incentives_2969.html [Accessed: 10/01/2016].
- Atkinson J., Chartier Y., and Pessoa-Silva C.L. (2009). Natural ventilation. [Online] Available at: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK143277/> [Accessed: 11/11/2015].
- Beamon, B. M. (1999a) Measuring supply chain performance, *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 19: 275-292
- Beamon, B. M. (1999b) Designing the green supply chain, *Logistics Information Management*, 12: 332-342
- Beamon, B. M. (2008) Sustainability and the future of supply chain management, *Operations and Supply Chain Management*, 1: 4-18.
- Berman B. (2011). History of Hybrid Vehicles. [Online] Available at: <http://www.hybridcars.com/history-of-hybrid-vehicles/> [Accessed: 11/10/2015].
- Betz H.D., Schumann U., and Laroche P. (2009). *Lightning: Principles, Instruments and Applications*. New York: Springer, pp. 202–203. ISBN 978-1-4020-9078-3.
- Bloomberg New Energy Finance. (2013). World Energy Perspective. Cost of Energy. Technologies. London: World Energy Council.
- Bowen, B. H., & Irwin, M. W. (2007). Coal Transportation Economics. CCTR Basic Facts File # 7. [Online] Available at: <https://www.purdue.edu/discoverypark/energy/assets/pdfs/cctr/outreach/Basics7-Transportation-Apr07.pdf> [Accessed: 12/11/2015]. Energy Center at Discovery Park Purdue University.
- Brandshaug, T., Christianson, M., and Damjanac, B. (2001). Technical Review of the Lined Rock Cavern (LRC) Concept and Design Methodology: Mechanical Response of Rock Mass. Minnesota, U.S.A: U.S. Department of Energy.
- Cabeza, L. F., Galindo, E., Prieto, C., Barrenche, C. and Fernandez, A. I. (2015) Key Performance Indicators in thermal energy storage: Survey and assessment, *Renewable Energy*, 83: 820-827
- CALMAC. (2016). How thermal energy storage works. [Online] Available at: <http://www.calmac.com/how-energy-storage-works> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Calnetix Technologies Llc. (2016). Advantages of Flywheels. [Online] Available at: <http://www.calnetix.com/resource/flywheels/advantages-flywheels> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- Carlucci, D. (2010). Evaluating and selecting key performance indicators: an ANP-based model. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 14(2), 66–76. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1108/13683041011047876> [Accessed: 21/11/2015].

- Cen, K., Chi, Y., and Yan, J. (2009). Challenge of Power Engineering and Environment, Proceedings of International Conference on Power Engineering 2007. Hangzhou, China.
- Chappells, H., and Shove, E. (2004). *COMFORT: A review of philosophies and paradigms*. Lancaster, UK: Economic and Social Research Council.
- Chae, B. K. (2009). Developing key performance indicators for supply chain: an industry perspective. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 14(6), 422–428. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1108/13598540910995192> [Accessed: 11/12/2015].
- Chen, J. (2011). *Renewable Energy Supply Chains*. Washington D.C.
- CLEAR. (2016). Mechanical ventilation. [Online] Available at: http://new-learn.info/packages/clear/thermal/buildings/active_systems/mv/index.html [Accessed: 12/01/2016].
- Cobb, J. (2014). The Three Main Types Of Hybrids Explained. [Online] Available at: <http://www.hybridcars.com/the-three-main-types-of-hybrids-explained/> [Accessed: 11/10/2016].
- Coenen, L., Benneworth, P., & Truffer, B. (2012). Toward a spatial perspective on sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 41(6), 968–979. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2012.02.014
- Compressionjobs.com (2010). Storage tanks and vessels. [Online] Available at: <http://articles.compressionjobs.com/articles/oilfield-101/5130-storage-tanks-vessels-gas-liquids> [Accessed: 11/10/2015].
- CrossBorder Bioenergy. (2012). *EU Handbook - District Heating Markets*. Brussels, Belgium: AEBIOM.
- Culham Centre for Fusion Energy. (2012). Introduction to fusion. [Online] Available at: <http://www.ccf.ac.uk/introduction.aspx> [Accessed: 25/11/2015].
- Crabbé, A., Jacobs, R., Van Hoof, V., Bergmans, A., & Van Acker, K. (2013). Transition towards sustainable material innovation: evidence and evaluation of the Flemish case. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 56, 63–72. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.01.023
- Cucchiella, F., & Adamo, I. D. (2013). Issue on supply chain of renewable energy Energy Return on Investment. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 76, 774–780. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.07.081> [Accessed: 20/11/2015].
- DEFRA (2006) *Environmental Key Performance Indicators: Reporting Guidelines for UK Business*, DEFRA: London
- DEFRA (2013). *Incineration of Municipal Solid Waste*. London, London, UK: Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs publications.
- Devitt, D. (2010). Making a Case for Flywheel Energy Storage. [Online] Available at: <http://www.renewableenergyworld.com/articles/print/rewna/volume-2/issue-1/storage/making-a-case-for-flywheel-energy-storage.html> [Accessed: 11/11/2015].
- Directorate-General for Internal Policies. (2009). *Gas and Oil Pipelines in Europe*. Policy Department, Economic and Scientific Policy A. PE 416.239 (IPA/A/ITRE/NT/2009-13). [Online] Available at: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/document/activities/cont/201106/20110628ATT22856/20110628ATT22856EN.pdf> [Accessed: 11/10/2015].
- Dizdaroglu, D. (2015) Developing micro-level urban ecosystem indicators for sustainability assessment, *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 54: 119-224
- EASAC. (2009). *Transforming Europe's Electricity Supply*. European Academies Science Advisor Council. [Online] Available at: <http://www.easac.eu/home/reports-and-statements/detail-view/article/transforming.html> [Accessed: 16/11/2015].
- Eaton, E. (2014). *Residential Lighting Controls Market Characterization*. Boston, USA: CEE.
- EDF Energy. (2016a). How electricity is generated. [Online] Available at: <http://www.edfenergy.com/energyfuture/generation-gas> [Accessed: 13/10/2015].

- EDF Energy. (2016b). Nuclear energy. [Online] Available at: <http://www.edfenergy.com/future-energy/energy-mix/nuclear> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- EEA. (2016). Overview of the electricity production and use in Europe. European Energy Agency. [Online] Available at: <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/overview-of-the-electricity-production/assessment> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- EEG. (2012). Facilitating energy storage to allow high penetration of intermittent renewable energy. Munich, Germany. Store-project - Intelligent Energy Europe programme. [Online] Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/intelligent/projects/en/projects/store> [Accessed: 20/11/2015].
- EESI. (2016). What Is District Energy? [Online] Available at: <http://www.districtenergy.org/assets/pdfs/White-Papers/What-IsDistrictEnergyEESI092311.pdf> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- EIA. (2015). Annual Energy Outlook 2015, with Projections to 2040. Washington, USA: U.S. Energy Information Administration.
- EIA. (2016a). Weekly Natural Gas Storage Report. U.S. Energy Information Administration. [Online] Available at: <http://ir.eia.gov/ngs/ngs.html> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- EIA. (2016b) The Basics of Underground Natural Gas Storage. U.S. Energy Information Administration. [Online] Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/naturalgas/storage/basics/> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- Electropaedia. (2016). Battery and Energy Technologies: Energy efficiency. [Online] Available at: http://www.mpoweruk.com/energy_efficiency.htm [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- El Saadany, A. M. A., Jaber, M. Y., & Bonney, M. (2011). Environmental performance measures for supply chains. *Management Research Review*, 34(11), 1202–1221.
- Energy Gov. (2016a). Solar Energy Technology Basics. [Online] Available at: <http://energy.gov/eere/energybasics/articles/solar-energy-technology-basics> [Accessed: 13/01/2016].
- Energy Informative. (2016). Tidal pros and cons. [Online] Available at: <http://energyinformative.org/tidal-energy-pros-and-cons/> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Energy International, Inc. (2002). *Stirling Engine Assessment*. Palo Alto - California, USA: EPRI
- Energy Storage Association. (2016). Flow Batteries. [Online] Available at: <http://energystorage.org/energy-storage/storage-technology-comparisons/flow-batteries> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- Energy.Gov. (2016). Hydrogen Storage. U.S.A. Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy. [Online] Available at: <http://energy.gov/eere/fuelcells/hydrogen-storage> [Accessed: 23/10/2015].
- Energy.Gov. (2016b). Types of Hydropower Plants. U.S.A. Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy [Online] Available at: <http://energy.gov/eere/water/types-hydropower-plants> [Accessed: 25/01/2016].
- EnergyStar.gov (2016). ENERGY STAR Most Efficient 2016 — Boilers. [Online] Available at: https://www.energystar.gov/index.cfm?c=most_efficient.me_boilers [Accessed 10/01/2016].
- Eurelectric. (2016). Water and Electricity: How it works. [Online] Available at: <http://www.eurelectric.org/water> [Accessed: 25/01/2016].
- European Commission. (2007). Energy Technologies, Knowledge – Perception – Measures. Brussels, Belgium: Directorate General for Research.
- European Commission. (2011). Energy Roadmap 2050. Luxembourg: Joint Research Centre. [Online] Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2012_energy_roadmap_2050_en_0.pdf [Accessed: 11/10/2015].
- European Commission. (2012a). Background Report on EU-27 District Heating and Cooling Potentials, Barriers, Best Practice and Measures of Promotion: Luxembourg: JRC Scientific and Policy Reports.

- European Commission. (2012b). Best available technologies for the heat and cooling market in the European Union. Luxembourg: JRC Scientific and Policy Reports.
- European Commission. (2012c). 2013 Technology Map of the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan: Luxembourg: JRC Scientific and Policy Reports.
- European Commission. (2016a). Nuclear energy. Safe nuclear power. [Online] Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/nuclear-energy> [Accessed: 12/01/2016].
- European Commission. (2016b). EU to invest €150 million in energy infrastructure. [Online] Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/news/eu-invest-%E2%82%AC150-million-energy-infrastructure> [Accessed: 12/01/2016].
- European Commission. (2016c). Funding. [Online] Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/funding-and-contracts> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- European Commission. (2016d). Energy Efficiency: Buildings. [Online] Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/buildings> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- European Parliament, Directorate General for Internal Policies. (2015). Energy Storage: Which Market Designs and Regulatory Incentives Are Needed? Brussels, Belgium: European Parliament Publications office.
- European Solar Thermal Industry Federation. (2016). Solar District Heating. [Online] Available at: http://www.estif.org/st_energy/technology/district_heating/ [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Eurostat (2016a). Consumption of Energy. [Online] Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Consumption_of_energy [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Eurostat (2016b). Electricity Production, Consumption and Market Overview. [Online] Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Electricity_production,_consumption_and_market_overview#Electricity_generation [Accessed: 26/01/2016].
- Eurostat (2016c). Electricity and Heat Statistics. [Online] Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Electricity_and_heat_statistics#Production_of_electricity [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Eurostat (2016d). Greenhouse Gas Emission Statistics. [Online] Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Greenhouse_gas_emission_statistics [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Evans, R. (2007). *Fuelling Our Future: An Introduction to Sustainable Energy*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- EWEA. (2015). Wind in Power, 2014. European Statistics. Brussels, Belgium: EWEA.
- ExtremeTech (2016). This fully transparent solar cell could make every window and screen a power source. [Online] Available at: <http://www.extremetech.com/extreme/188667-a-fully-transparent-solar-cell-that-could-make-every-window-and-screen-a-power-source> [Accessed: 20/01/2016].
- Farahani, H., Wagiran, R., & Hamidon, M. (2014). *Humidity Sensors Principle, Mechanism, and Fabrication Technologies: A Comprehensive Review*. Sensors, 14(5): 7881-7939. doi: 10.3390/s140507881.
- Ferreira, V. J., Lopez-Sabiron, A. M., Royo, P., Aranda-Uson, A. and Ferreira, G. (2015) Integration of environmental indicators in the optimization of industrial energy management using phase change materials, Energy Conversion and Management, 104: 67-77
- Fehr, R.L. (2009). *Guide to Building Energy Efficient Homes in Kentucky and Mixed Humid Climate Zone*. Lexington: The University Press of Kentucky.
- Fink D.G. and Wayne Beaty H. (2007). *Standard Handbook for Electrical Engineers (15th Edition)*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Freimark B. (2006). Six Wire Solution. Transmission & Distribution World. [Online] Available at: <http://tdworld.com/overhead-transmission/six-wire-solution> [Accessed: 11/12/2015].
- GEODH (2016). Geothermal district heating. [Online] Available at: <http://geodh.eu/about-geothermal-district-heating/> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Genus, A., & Mafakheri, F. (2014). A neo-institutional perspective of supply chains and energy security: Bioenergy in the UK. Applied Energy, 123, 307–315. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.01.084> [Accessed: 3/12/2015].
- Global Energy Network Institute. (2016). Concentrator PV: Harvesting More, Spending Less. [Online] Available at: <http://www.geni.org/globalenergy/library/technical-articles/generation/solar/renewableenergyworld.com/concentrator-pv-harvesting-more-spending-less/index.shtml> [Accessed: 7/01/2016].
- Goetzler, W. (2007). Variable Refrigerant Flow Systems. ASHRAE Journal, April 2007, pp. 24-31. [Online] Available at: <http://docplayer.net/10557491-Variable-refrigerant-flow-systems.html> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Grainger, J.J. and Stevenson W.D. Jr. (1994). *Power System Analysis and Design, (2nd Edition)*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Grübler, A. (2012). Energy transitions research: Insights and cautionary tales. Energy Policy, 50, 8–16. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2012.02.070
- Guertler, B. and Spinler, S. (2015) Supply risk interrelationships and the derivation of key supply risk indicators, Technological Forecasting & Social Change, 92: 224-236
- Gunaesekaran, A., Patel, C. and McGaughey, R. E. (2004) A framework for supply chain performance measurement, International Journal of Production Economics, 87: 333-347
- Gunasekaran, A., & Chung, W. W. C. (2004). Editorial: Special issue on supply chain management for the 21st century organizational competitiveness. Int. J. Production Economics, 87, 209–212. [Online] Available at: [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273\(03\)00215-9](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273(03)00215-9) [Accessed: 7/12/2015]
- Gunasekaran, A., & Spalanzani, A. (2012). Sustainability of manufacturing and services : Investigations for research and applications. Intern. Journal of Production Economics, 140(1), 35–47. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2011.05.011> [Accessed: 5/12/2015]
- Gunasekaran, A., Patel, C., & Mcgaughey, R. E. (2004). A framework for supply chain performance measurement. Int. J. Production Economics, 87, 333–347. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2003.08.003> [Accessed: 5/12/2015].
- heatpumpcentre.org (n.a.). Energy sources. [Online] Available at: <http://www.heatpumpcentre.org/en/aboutheatpumps/energysources/Sidor/default.aspx> [Accessed: 10/12/2015].
- Highview Power. (2016). Cryo-Energy System. [Online] Available at: <http://www.highview-power.com/> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- Ho, A. (2015). The European Offshore Wind Industry Key Trends and Statistics 1st half 2015. Brussels, Belgium: EWEA.
- Honorio, L. (2003). Efficiency in Electricity Generation. Brussels: EURELECTRIC “Preservation of Resources” Working Group’s “Upstream” Sub-Group in collaboration with VGB.
- Hsion Lim, C., & Loong Lam, H. (2016). Biomass supply chain optimisation via novel Biomass Element Life Cycle Analysis (BELCA). Applied Energy, 161, 733–745. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.07.030> [Accessed: 11/12/2015].
- HydraTech. (2016). Techniques for the Quantification of Methane Hydrate in European Continental Margins. [Online] Available at: <http://www.hydratech.bham.ac.uk/> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].
- ICCT. (2014). European vehicle market statistics, Pocketbook 2014. [Online] Available at: <http://autotraveler.ru/en/spravka/fuel-price-in-europe.html#.Vp4ns1JYZSo> [Accessed: 11/01/2016].

- Iddrisu, I. and Bhattacharyya, S. C. (2015) Sustainable Energy Development Index: A multi-dimensional indicator for measuring sustainable energy development, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 50: 513-530
- IEA (2016). *Technology Roadmap. Hydrogen and fuel cells*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA Clean Coal Centre. (n.d.). Pulverised coal combustion. [Online] Available at: <http://www.iea-coal.org.uk/site/2010/database-section/ccts/pulverised-coal-combustion-pcc?> [Accessed: 11/12/2015].
- IEA. (2008). *Combined Heat and Power, Evaluating the benefits of greater global investment*: Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2012a). *Technology Roadmap, Bioenergy for Heat and Power*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2012b). *Technology Roadmap, Geothermal Heat and Power*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2012c). *Energy Technology Perspective*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2012d). *Technology Roadmap, Solar Heating and Cooling*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2013a). *Technology Roadmap, Wind energy*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2013b). *Thermal Energy Storage. IEA-ETSAP and IRENA Technology Brief, E17*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2013c). *Technology Roadmap, Energy-efficient Buildings: Heating and Cooling Equipment*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2013d). *Technology Roadmap, Solar Photovoltaic Energy*. Paris, France: IEA Publications.
- IEA. (2016). *District heating*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.iea-dhc.org/the-technology.html> [Accessed: 30/01/2016].
- IFL Science. (2015). *Solar Fuels: How Planes And Cars Could Be Powered By The Sun*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.iflscience.com/technology/solar-fuels-how-planes-and-cars-could-be-powered-sun/> [Accessed: 30/11/2015].
- Indiegogo. (2016). *Vortex Bladeless: a wind generator without blades*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.indiegogo.com/projects/vortex-bladeless-a-wind-generator-without-blades--3#/> [Accessed: 30/01/2016].
- INSEE. (n.d.). *International prices of imported raw materials – Heavy fuel oil (Rotterdam) – Prices in US dollars per tonne*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.insee.fr/en/bases-de-donnees/bsweb/serie.asp?idbank=001642883> [Accessed: 28/11/2015].
- Institute for Energy Research. (2014). *Overhead vs. Underground – Information about burying high-voltage transmission lines, Colorado’s renewable energy future*. Electricity Transmission.
- International Union of railways. (2012). *Railway Handbook – Energy Consumption and CO2 Emission*. Paris, France: OECD/International Energy Agency and the International Union of Railways.
- IPCC. (2014). *Global warming potential of selected electricity sources - Annex II*. [Online] Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Life-cycle_greenhouse_gas_emissions_of_energy_sources#2014_IPCC.2C_Global_warming_potential_of_selected_electricity_sources [Accessed: 30/11/2015].
- Issu, I. I., Pigosso, D. C. A., McAlloone, T. C. and Rozenfield, H. (2015) *Leading product-related environmental performance indicators: A selection guide and database*, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Article in press
- Jayalakshmi, M., & Balasubramanian, K. (2008). *Simple Capacitors to Supercapacitors. An Overview*. Hyderabad, India: *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 3.
- Jothilingam, D., Suresh, G. (2015). *Non-conventional energy sources sustainable power generation*. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Science & Engineering (IJIRTSE)*. ISSN: 2395-5619, Volume – 1, Issue – 3. May 2015

- Kagel, A., & Bates, D., & Gawell, K. (2007). *A Guide to Geothermal Energy and the Environment*. Washington, D.C, USA: Geothermal Energy Association.
- Karangwa, E. (2008). Estimating the cost of pipeline transportation in Canada. Published on Canadian Transportation Research Forum.
- Kempener, R., & Neumann, F. (2014). *Tidal Energy. Technology brief*. Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates: International Renewable Energy Agency.
- Kern, F. (2012). Using the multi-level perspective on socio-technical transitions to assess innovation policy. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, (79), 298–310.
- Kerskes, H., (2011). *Thermal Storage: State of the Art and Future Aspects*. RHC Workshop on Thermal Energy Storage. Belgium, Brussels: workshop presentation.
- Kiefner, J. F., & Rosenfeld, M. J. (2012). *The Role of Pipeline Age in Pipeline Safety*. INGAA Foundation final report.
- Laird (2012). PV technology developments 2011 and beyond. [Online] Available at: <http://www.renewableenergyfocus.com/view/23695/pv-technology-developments-2011-and-beyond/> [Accessed 5/12/2015]
- Lako, P. (2010). *Coal-Fired Power*. Paris, France: IEA ETSAP.
- Lazard. (2014). *Lazard's levelized cost of Energy analysis-version 8.0*. (n.p.): LAZARD
- Lee, J. H. (2014). Energy supply planning and supply chain optimization under uncertainty. *Journal of Process Control*, 24, 323–331. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprocont.2013.09.025> [Accessed 13/12/2015]
- Lehtonen, M. (2013) The non-use and influence of UK Energy Sector Indicators, *Ecological Economics*, 35: 24-34
- Lexus. (2016). Lexus CT combined cycle data. [Online] Available at: <http://www.lexus.it/car-models/ct/ct-200h/#Introduction> [Accessed: 30/11/2016].
- May, G., Barletta, I., Stahl, B. and Taisch, M. (2015) Energy management in production: A novel method to develop Key Performance Indicators for improving energy efficiency, *Applied Energy*, 149: 46-61
- Marrero, T. R. (n.d.). *Long-Distance Transport of Coal by Coal Log Pipeline*. Capsule Pipeline Research Center, University of Missouri.
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology. (n.d.). *Vibro-wind*. [Online] Available at: <http://web.mit.edu/jociek/www/vibroWind.htm> [Accessed: 01/12/2015].
- Meadowcroft, J. (2009). What about the politics? Sustainable development, transition management, and long term energy transitions. *Policy Sciences*, 42(4), 323–340.
- McKetta, A. n.d. *Coal Transportation*. University of Texas Department of Chemical Engineering lecture Notes, Chapter 4.
- Microgreening (n.a.). *Condensing Boilers*. . [Online] Available at: <http://www.microgreening.com/insulating-heating-and-cooling/condensing-boilers.php> [Accessed: 01/12/2015].
- Miller, T. (2010). *Understanding Chillers: Which is Right for Your Application?* [Online] Available at: <http://www.conairgroup.com/> [Accessed: 10/12/2015].
- National Institute of Building Science. (2016). *High-Performance HVAC*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.wbdg.org/resources/hvac.php> [Accessed: 10/01/2016].
- National Institute of Building Science. (2016). *Web site, Natural Ventilation*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.wbdg.org/resources/naturalventilation.php> [Accessed: 10/01/2016].
- NaturalGas. (2016). *History*. [Online] Available at: <http://naturalgas.org/overview/history/> [Accessed: 10/01/2016].

- Navigant Consulting, Inc. (2012a). Life-Cycle Assessment of Energy and Environmental Impacts of LED Lighting Products. (n.p.): U.S. Department of Energy.
- Navigant Consulting, Inc. (2012b). Life-Cycle Energy Consumption: Incandescent, Compact Fluorescent, and LED Lamps. (n.p.): U.S. Department of Energy.
- Oberhofer, A. (2012). Energy Storage Technologies & Their Role in Renewable Integration. Global Energy Network Institute. <http://www.geni.org/globalenergy/research/energy-storage-technologies/Energy-Storage-Technologies.pdf> [Accessed: 01/12/2015].
- Odesie. (n.d.). Boilers types and classifications. [Online] Available at: <https://www.myodesie.com/wiki/index/returnEntry/id/3061> [Accessed: 01/12/2015].
- Oellrich, L.R. (2004). Natural Gas Hydrates and their Potential for Future Energy Supply. Karlsruhe, Germany: XVII National and VI ISHMT/ASME Heat and Mass Transfer Conference, IGCAR, Kalpakkam, Jan. 5-7, 2004.
- Okten, G., & Kural, O., & Algurkaplan, E. (2013). Storage of Coal: Problems and precautions. Istanbul, Turkey: Energy storage systems – Vol. II, Encyclopedia of life support systems (EOLSS)
- Olesen, B.W. (n.d). Indoor environmental Quality related to comfort, health and productivity. Lyngby, Denmark: ICIEE.
- OTA. (1978). Coal Slurry Pipeline and Unit Train Systems. [Online] Available at: <https://www.princeton.edu/~ota/disk3/1978/7817/781706.PDF> [Accessed: 10/01/2016].
- Overholm, H. (2015). Spreading the rooftop revolution : What policies enable. Energy Policy, 84, 69–79. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.04.021>
- P.C. McKenzie Company (n.a.). Firetube or Watertube? What's the difference?. [Online] Available at: http://www.mckenziecorp.com/boiler_tip_8.htm [Accessed: 10/01/2016].
- Park, J. (2013). Comparative analysis of the VRF System and conventional HVAC Systems, focused on life cycle-cost. Atlanta, GA-USA: Georgia Institute of Technology.
- PCM Products Ltd. (2016). Phase Change Materials: Thermal Management Solutions. [Online] Available at: <http://www.pcmproducts.net/> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- PetroWiki. (2013). Oil storage. [Online] Available at: http://petrowiki.org/Oil_storage#Types_of_storage_tanks [Accessed: 21/12/2015].
- PICS Supply Chain Council. (2015). SCOR Framework. [Online] Available at: <http://www.apics.org/sites/apics-supply-chain-council/frameworks/scor> [Accessed: 15/11/2015].
- Portland Energy Conservation. (2011). The Building Performance Tracking Handbook. California: California Commissioning Collaborative
- PowerScoreCard. (2016). Electricity from coal. [Online] Available at: http://powerscorecard.org/tech_detail.cfm?resource_id=2 [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- Pöyry Energy Consulting. (2009). The potential and costs of district heating networks. Oxford, UK: Report to the Department of Energy and Climate Change.
- PPIAF. (2016). Railway reform: toolkit for improving rail sector performance. [Online] Available at: http://www.ppiaf.org/sites/ppiaf.org/files/documents/toolkits/railways_toolkit/download.html [Accessed: 15/01/2016].
- Quora. (2016). How is a supercapacitor different from a capacitor? [Online] Available at: <https://www.quora.com/How-is-a-supercapacitor-different-from-a-capacitor> [Accessed: 15/01/2016].
- Radhakrishnane, Rm. (2012). Enhancing power plant productivity through coal stockyard management. RSTPS

- Renault. (2016). Renault Zoe technical data. [Online] Available at: <https://www.renault.it/veicoli/gamma-ze.html?ORIGIN=SEM&CAMPAIGN=sem2015&gclid=CMYhxailuMoCFVQaGwodeqgBtA> [Accessed: 18/01/2016].
- Renewable Northwest Project. (2006). Tidal energy levelised costs from North American Tidal In-Stream Energy Conversion Technology Feasibility Study. EPRI, TP-008-NA.
- Renewable Northwest. (2009). Wave & Tidal Energy Technology. [Online] Available at: <http://www.rnp.org/node/wave-tidal-energy-technology> [Accessed: 21/12/2015].
- Rezaie, B., & Rosen, M. A. (2012). District heating and cooling: Review of technology and potential enhancements. *Applied Energy*, 93, pp. 2–10.
- Rip, A., & Kemp, R. (1998). Technological change. In *Human choice and climate change* (pp. 327–399).
- Robur S.p.A. (2016). Heat Pumps Comparison: basic principles. [Online] Available at: http://www.robur.com/technical_dossiers/heat_pumps_absorption_technology/heat_pumps_comparison_basic_principles [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Sandia National Laboratories, (2016). Advantages of Using Molten salt. [Online] Available at: <http://www.webcitation.org/60AE7heEZ> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Searcy, C., Karapetrovic, S., & McCartney, D. (2005). Designing sustainable development indicators: analysis for a case utility. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 9(2), 33–41. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1108/13683040510602867> [Accessed: 21/11/2015].
- Seebregts, A. J. (2010). Gas-Fired Power. IEA ETSAP - Technology Brief-E02.
- Shahriar, S., & Erkan, T. (2008). When will fossil fuel reserves be diminished?. *Energy Policy*, 1, pp.181-189.
- Shahin, A., & Mahbod, M. A. (2007). Prioritization of key performance indicators. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 56(3), 226–240.
- Shepherd, C., & Günter, H. (2006). Measuring supply chain performance: current research and future directions. *Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 55(3/4), 242–258.
- Simpson, G., & Clifton, J. (2015). The emperor and the cowboys : The role of government policy and industry in the adoption of domestic solar microgeneration systems. *Energy Policy*, 81, 141–151. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.02.028> [Accessed: 23/11/2015].
- Sivadasan, S., Efstathiou, J., Calinescu, A., & Huaccho Huatuco, L. (2004). Supply chain complexity. In S. New & R. Westbrook (Eds.), *Understanding Supply Chains* (pp. 133–163). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Smith, A., Stirling, A., & Berkhout, F. (2005). The governance of sustainable socio-technical transitions. *Research Policy*, 34(10), 1491–1510. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2005.07.005
- Solomon, B. D., & Krishna, K. (2011). The coming sustainable energy transition: History, strategies, and outlook. *Energy Policy*, 39(11), 7422–7431. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.09.009
- Slant/Fin. (2016). Differences between Boilers & Furnaces. [Online] Available at: <http://www.slantfin.com/homeowners/difference-between-boiler-furnace.html> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Sofregaz US Inc., & LRC. (1999). Commercial potential of natural gas storage in lined rock caverns (LRC). Topical Report SZUS-0005 DE-AC26-97FT34348-01.
- SolarReserve. (2016). Molten Salt Energy Storage. [Online] Available at: <http://www.solarreserve.com/en/technology/molten-salt-energy-storage> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Spirax Sarco Limited. (2016). Steam Accumulators. [Online] Available at: <http://www.spiraxsarco.com/Resources/Pages/Steam-Engineering-Tutorials/the-boiler-house/steam-accumulators.aspx> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Staller, H., & Tisch, A. (2010). New technical solutions for energy efficient buildings. SciNetwork-State of the Art report.

- Stank, T. P., Dittmann, J. P., & Autry, C. W. (2011). The new supply chain agenda: a synopsis and directions for future research. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 41(10), 940–955.
- StratoSolar. (2016). Gravity Energy Storage. [Online] Available at: <http://www.stratosolar.com/gravity-energy-storage.html> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- SuperPower. (2016). Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES). [Online] Available at: <http://www.superpower-inc.com/content/superconducting-magnetic-energy-storage-smes> [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Tahir, S., & Moulin, J., & Coral, N., & Uku, B., & Posner, H. (2014). (PRO-LITE) State of the art, Technical report. London, UK: Isle Utilities.
- Taticchi, P., Tonelli, F., & Pasqualino, R. (2013). Performance measurement of sustainable supply chains. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 62(8), 782–804.
- The Association for Decentralised Energy. (2016). What is combined heat and power? [Online] Available at: http://www.theade.co.uk/what-is-combined-heat-and-power_15.html [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- The Green Age. (2016). Mechanical ventilation in building - what you need to know. [Online] Available at: <http://www.thegreenage.co.uk/mechanical-ventilation-in-buildings-what-you-need-to-know/> [Accessed: 16/01/2016].
- The Telegraph. (2016). Gasometers: a brief history. [Online] Available at: <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/newsbysector/energy/oilandgas/10473071/Gasometers-a-brief-history.html> [Accessed: 19/01/2016].
- Thimsen, D. (2002), Stirling engine assessment. Bellevue, WA.
- Tidal power. (2016). Tidal power. [Online] Available at: <http://tidalpower.co.uk/> [Accessed: 12/01/2016].
- Tidal power. (n.d.). Tidal power. [Online] Available at: http://www.esru.strath.ac.uk/EandE/Web_sites/01-02/RE_info/Tidal%20Power.htm#streams [Accessed: 16/01/2016].
- Tomia. (2007). Hydroelectric Dam. Wikipedia Commons file. [Online] Available at: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Hydroelectric_dam.svg [Accessed: 28/01/2016].
- Trench, C. J. (2001). *How Pipelines Make the Oil Market Work – Their Networks, Operation and Regulation* New York: Allegro Energy Group.
- UH IELE. (2016). LNG Frequently Asked Questions. University of Houston Institute for Energy Law & Enterprise publication.
- Union of Concerned Scientists. (2016). Coal power: air pollution. [Online] Available at: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_energy/coalvswind/c02c.html#.Vp-4BfnhCM8 [Accessed: 19/01/2016].
- Union of Concerned Scientists. (2016). Environmental impact of coal power: fuel supply. [Online] Available at: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_energy/coalvswind/c02a.html#.Vp-4BfnhCM8 [Accessed: 19/01/2016].
- Union of Concerned Scientists. (2016). Environmental impact of Wind Power. [Online] Available at: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_energy/our-energy-choices/renewable-energy/environmental-impacts-wind-power.html#.VpJ8n_nhDIU [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- Union of Concerned Scientists. (2016). Environmental Impacts of Renewable Energy Technologies. [Online] Available at: http://www.ucsusa.org/clean_energy/our-energy-choices/renewable-energy/environmental-impacts-of.html#.VpJ8hfnhDIU [Accessed: 19/01/2016].
- UOL-VENTILATION. (2016). Mechanical forced ventilation. [Online] Available at: <http://uol-ventilation.weebly.com/mechanical.html> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- US Dept. of Energy. (2005). *Liquefied Natural Gas: Understanding the Basic Facts*. Office of Fossil Energy publication.

- Vogel, R., & Roberts, P. R. (1979). Operating and Maintenance Costs of Underground Colliery Conveyors Environmental and Pollution Aspects of Coal Slurry Pipelines. Environmental Protection Agency Technical Report
- VV. AA. (2006). Micro CHP systems: state-of-the-art. Green Lodges Project-Technical report.
- VV. AA. (2009a). Lifetime of White LEDs. US Department of energy - Building Technologies Program.
- VV. AA. (2009b). Natural Ventilation for Infection Control in Health-Care Settings. WHO publications/guidelines.
- VV. AA. (2010). Building Performance Tracking in Large- Commercial Buildings: Tools and Strategies. Building Commissioning: Strategies and Technologies – Technical Report.
- VV. AA. (2010). VRV/VRF Variable refrigerant volume (or flow) technology. Air Conditioning and Heat Pump Institute publication.
- VV. AA. (2010). Whole Building Design Guide, Federal Green Construction Guide for Specifiers. [Online] Available at: <http://fedgreenspecs.wbdg.org> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- VV. AA. (2011a). Le agevolazioni fiscali per il risparmio energetico. Agenzia delle Entrate – Handbook.
- VV. AA. (2012a). Best available technologies for the heat and cooling market in the European Union. JRC Scientific and Policy Reports.
- VV. AA. (2012b). Evaluating energy storage options: a case study at Los Angeles Harbor college. Donald Bren School-Project Report.
- VV. AA. (2012c). Direttiva 2012/27/UE del Parlamento Europeo e del Consiglio del 25 ottobre 2012 sull'efficienza energetica, che modifica le direttive 2009/125/CE e 2010/30/UE e abroga le direttive 2004/8/CE e 2006/32/CE. Gazzetta ufficiale dell'Unione europea L 315/51.
- VV. AA. (2013a). Grid Energy Storage. U.S. Department of Energy report.
- VV. AA. (2013b). The power sector in Phase 2 of the EU ETS: fewer CO₂ emissions but just as much coal. CDC Climate Report, 42.
- VV. AA. (2013c). Thermal Energy Storage. IEA-ETSAP and IRENA Technology Brief, E17.
- VV. AA. (2014a). Energy in Transport. Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland, 2014 Report.
- VV. AA. (2014b). Market Observatory for Energy. Quarterly Report on European Electricity Markets, 7.
- VV. AA. (2015a). Overview of purchase and tax incentives for electric vehicles in the EU in 2015. ACEA publications.
- VV. AA. (2015b). Improvement of Energy Efficiency in Technology Parks of the Med Area through Intelligent Models and Uses. SmartMEDParks. Which. (2016). Petrol vs diesel buying guide. [Online] Available at: <http://www.which.co.uk/cars/choosing-a-car/buying-a-car/petrol-or-diesel/petrol-vs-diesel-buying-guide/> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- VV.AA. (2004). Final report on technical data, costs and life cycle inventories of advanced fossil power generation systems. NEEDS Project Technical Report.
- VV.AA. (2011b). L'efficienza nel settore delle reti energetiche. ENEA publications
- VV.AA. (2011c) IPCC: Special Report on Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation
- Wagner, M., & Schaltegger, S. (2004). The Effect of Corporate Environmental Strategy Choice and Environmental Performance on Competitiveness and Economic Performance : An Empirical Study of EU Manufacturing. European Management Journal, 22(5), 557–572. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2004.09.013> [Accessed: 25/11/2015].
- Wee, H., Yang, W., Chou, C., & Padilan, M. V. (2012). Renewable energy supply chains, performance , application barriers , and strategies for further development. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 16(8), 5451–5465. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.06.006> [Accessed: 21/11/2015].

- World Nuclear Association. (2016). Nuclear power in European Union. [Online] Available at: <http://www.world-nuclear.org/info/Country-Profiles/Others/European-Union/> [Accessed:21/01/2016].
- Worldwatch Institute (2012). Use and Capacity of Global Hydropower Increases [Online] Available at: <http://www.worldwatch.org/node/9527> [Accessed: 21/01/2016].
- Wüstemeyer, C., Madlener, R., & Bunn, D. W. (2015). A stakeholder analysis of divergent supply-chain trends for the European onshore and offshore wind installations. *Energy Policy*, 80, 36–44. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.01.017> [Accessed: 20/11/2015].
- Xuequn, M. (2015). Three Gorges breaks world record for hydropower generation. [Online] Available at: http://news.xinhuanet.com/english/china/2015-01/01/c_127352471.htm [Accessed 10/12/2015].
- Yu, H. (2015). Global LED Lighting Trends Reveal Significant Growth and Product Development. [Online] Available at: <http://www.ledjournal.com/main/blogs/global-led-lighting-trends-reveal-significant-growth-and-product-development/> [Accessed 18/12/2015].
- Zhao, C., & Chen, B. (2014). China's oil security from the supply chain perspective: A review. *Applied Energy*, 136, 269–279. [Online] Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.09.01> [Accessed: 23/11/2015].